

Did a single god or a huge number of quanta, constitute nature and the world

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The authors declare that no funding was received for this work.

Received: 20-November-2025

Accepted: 30-January-2026

Published: 11-February-2026

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This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (MSIJMR)** ISSN 3049-0669 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume: 3, Issue: 2 (February-2026)

ABSTRACT: Geological records and astrophysical data show that nature and our world have developed over a period of billions of years. Physics and chemistry show that the most basic particles of matter, called atoms, are forming higher levels like molecules and cells. Quantum physics experiments show that the factor that triggers and directs all these formations and developments is energy, being in the form quanta as the most basic elements of interactions and vitality. Dynamical–systems-physics show that these most basic elements of vitality, called quantum, are knowledgeable - conscious, interrelated with each other at the universal level and stimulate the capacity to create information. It turns out that there is a development system in nature starting from the lower levels towards the upper levels. In any organisation the higher level depends upon the lower level. In life, the individual is the lower-level, the state is the upper-level. If the rule of the natural system were valid, the state would have to be dependent on individuals. However, individuals are dependent on the state. This does not fit into the natural system at all. When the origin of such an application, which is completely contrary to the natural-system, is investigated, it is understood that there is a misconception that the creation in nature is carried out by a system of power at the top called God

or natural-selector. Such a mistake has divided humanity into many races and religions that are at war with each other.

Keywords: *Geological records, genomes, quantum, exponential-information, paleontology, synergetic, archaeology, history, anthropology.*

1. CHAPTER- INTRODUCTION

I am a retired professor who researches and teaches the history of the earth and the development of the life system on the earth (palaeontology). In one of the lectures I gave in the 1970s, one of my students said, "Teacher, you have shown us how life is formed and developed on earth. So, what is life? Why are we born and why do we die?" Since then, I have been doing research on this topic. As a result of those long years researches, this book has been prepared.

The first thing I noticed was that the concept of TIME was misperceived by people. Life = life-span; and life-span is a slice of time. He who solves the secret of the concept of time also solves the secret of life.

Time has been accepted as an eternal process that operates according to the ticks given by an eternal being, without a beginning or end, and natural events are developments that take place according to these ticks. The reason why this is thought is that nature and the world were created and directed by an eternal being. If this eternal being dies, nature and the world will not survive.

The concept of TIME has always been misinterpreted by physicists. The reason why physicists misinterpret the concept of TIME is that there is no such parameter as INFORMATION in the developments of nature. In other words, beings are unconscious, robot-like elements that obey the laws of nature. So how did the laws of nature come about? Physicists have no answer to this question.

In this book, all these issues will be explained logically based on natural scientific research.

Humanity is wondering how our world and the life system on it were formed and developed. The world means "earth". Since geology = earth-science, GEOLOGY is

the only source from which information can be obtained on this subject. The science of geology has been known for 2-3 centuries. People, on the other hand, continue to live according to their traditions and customs, and there is no geological information in these traditional customs. Traditions and customs are transferred by being processed into the subconscious. If an elephant was accustomed to being chained to a place by its foot when it was little, this behavior is copied into the elephant's subconscious, and the elephant continues to live in compliance with this copied conditioning after that. People also copy the behavior of people around them until the first-6-7 years old, and when they grow up, they live according to these conditions, just like an elephant. Since the people in the environment are also programmed-conditioned according to information copied from older generations, this cycle continues in this way.

However, there is a balance and order in nature, and this order is formed by mutual interactions between beings. How this balance and order is formed begins to be enlightened after the 1980s. In 1983, German physicist Hermann Haken put forward mathematical and physical formulations of how the formations and developments in nature take place with a system he called -SYNERGETICS, which means "co-operation" and in (2000) he laid the foundation of the physics of dynamical systems, which is summarized as "information & self-organization".

As can be understood, everything in nature is constructed with information. But natural scientists such as physicists and biologists have never used such a parameter as information because they have seen everything as robot-like beings that obey the laws of nature. No information is given about how the laws of nature are formed.

This is due to the fact that natural-scientists conceive of the constructive-constituting-directing power system in nature as an external system independent of entities. As a matter of fact, for this reason, the concept of time has been accepted as an eternal process that operates according to the ticks given by a supernatural power system and has no beginning or end. Because there is a belief that if this power dies, nature and the world will not survive.

The following facts indicate that time is the 4th DIMENSION in nature. Lifespan is the period between birth and death. Since the process from the beginning of the development of all beings in nature to the present day is called time, lifetimes are slices of time. Therefore, time is a result of changeovers in nature, and if there is no changeovers, time does not occur. In other words, birth and death are the sine qua non of the formation and development of nature. Nothing that is eternal does not exist and cannot be. This is the cause that TIME is the 4th dimension of matters.

Now let's first look at the issue of creating and owning something in nature. Humanity believes that the nature has a creator, and therefore an owner. How are thing created? And who is the owner of this thing?

The creator of a thing is the one who makes it. Human are formed by its cells, and these cells are formed by molecules. Humans have been around for 3 million years, but the eukaryotic cells that make up us have been around for 2 billion years. There is another group of cells that are older than eukaryotic cells, they are called prokaryotic cells, and they have a history of 3.5 billion years. Therefore, the ancestors of all living things in nature are prokaryotic cells that emerged 3.5 billion years ago and are still alive today as bacteria. Prokaryotic cells are nucleus-free, very small (about 1 micron, that is, one thousandth of a millimeter) in size. Eukaryotic cells have a nucleus and are 100 microns in size, while animals are meters in size. Therefore, there is a development in living things in the form of the combination and growth of small elements. That is, the size and chemical composition of entities in nature are not fixed, but variable.

Human development in 4 dimensions

Let's examine this issue of variability. You make a table, the width-length-width is fixed. The composition of your table is also fixed, its shape is also fixed, it does not change. In other words, the products we make are 3D. However, both the chemical composition and the shape of what the natural system does are constantly changing. You will say that bacteria 3.5 billion years ago were 1 micron in size, and today's bacteria are 1 micron in size. Yes, their size has remained the same, but their chemical composition has changed. There are species of eukaryotic cells such as

amoebas and slippery animals that still live in 100 microns in size, their sizes have remained the same, but their internal chemical composition has changed. In addition to these groups, which do not change in size, there is both a chemical composition and a constant change in size and shape in the creatures we call animals and plants. Now let's illustrate this phenomenon of size or shape change with examples.

Figure 1: Human development

It begins to form by the proliferation of a fertilized cell called a human zygote. The growth-proliferation stages of this cell are shown in the Fig. Then after 40 weeks a child is born. When a human being is born, it is a creature as small as 2 kg. Then it grows, reaches a body of 50-60 kilograms, becomes adult, enters a very active phase. Changes occur in his body chemistry, forcing him to mate and pass on his hereditary knowledge to a future generation. The two cells from the mother and father merge and a new body begins to be formed. The fertilized cell multiplies in a geometric sequence such as 2-4-8-16 and forms a new human being and birth takes place. When a person gets older, he collapses again, his energy decreases, the cells age, stop multiplying and disperse. As can be seen, assets are not fixed-size. There is a 4-dimensionality in continuing changeovers. Time represent this 4-dimensionality.

Changeovers in nature lead to changes in the genetic records of living things. Since these changes in genes are passed on to children born with sperm and eggs, the offspring differ from their parents. A temporal evolution called the 4th dimension occurs between the ancestor and the baby.

Now let's think about it this way: Raising and educating children takes a lot of effort. What happens if parents don't take on this challenge? What will be the result if no parent has children? The creature called human disappears. However, every living thing wants to live, this urge to live exists in every living thing, and therefore a desire to continue its lineage is present in every living thing. Since the geological layers of our Earth show that life has been constantly evolving for 3.5 billion years, there must be an inner drive in all shrubs to continue their lineage.

This timely changeovers in humans also exists in the plant kingdom. Lifespans are also very different: some plants have a lifespan of hundreds of years, while others have only seasonal-annual lifespans. Different lifespans also exist in the animal kingdom. Some animals have a lifespan of hundreds of years, while others have a daily-monthly lifespan.

Figure 2: Growth of a salt crystal

There is also a 4-dimensional change in inanimate beings. Transformation in nature exists not only in living organisms, but also in the realm of inorganic beings, which we call inanimate. If you put a tiny salt crystal in a very salty environment, after a while you will see that tiny crystal grow. But if you throw that tiny salt crystal into pure water, your tiny crystal will melt and disappear over time. That is, natural beings behave, grow or shrink in a way that suits their environment.

Are nature and the world also 4-dimensional?

Figure 3: 4-dimensionality of the world

It is understood from geological data that our world is also in a 4-dimensional change and transformation. In the Fig, the changes of the geography of our world for the last 250 million years obtained as a result of geological research are seen. 250 million years ago, all the continents on Earth were united. It begins to break down 200 million years ago and comes to the present day by passing through the phases in the Fig. The Himalayan mountains are the highest mountain range in the world today and were formed about 10 million years ago. Going back further, it has been determined that India broke away from Afrika and migrated in northeast. 80 million years ago, India was a continent separated in the ocean south of the equator. In other words, there was a huge ocean between Asia and India 80 million years ago. Towards the present day, India gets closer and closer to the Asian Continent and 30 million years ago, it started to hit Asia, so the layers on the ocean floor between them started to squeeze and rise between Asia and India and come out of the sea. As India approaches Asia, the layers on the seabed rise higher and form the highest mountain

belt of today. The most important evidence that this is the case is the marine environment fossils found in the rocks of the Himalayan mountains.

Time is formed as a result of the change and transformation of the natural system, that is, beings cannot remain in 3 dimensions, they are constantly changing and transforming. Nature, is in constant change and transformation, every being changes and transforms. These changes-transformations lead to a constant change of assets. Therefore, entities cannot remain static, 3-dimensional, and their size changes over time. In other words, nature is a 4-dimensional system.

This 4-dimensionality starts with the fundamental constituent parts of nature, called quantum. Quanta are the most basic life-elements constituting the nature. In other words, all formations in nature are formed by combining the internal components of beings with information based on mutual agreement and compromise in order to become more comfortable. Physicists say, "We don't understand quantum physics!" Because the quantum system is alive, physicists cannot explain this life in them with mathematical-physical formulas. Because they can't come up with a formula, they say, "nobody understands quantum physics."

Humanity has been gradually developing and multiplying in the world since 2.5 million years. The entire natural system is based on the basis of reproduction and growth, called QUANTIZATION. For this reason, a structuring system called "Lower-Level - Upper-Level" has emerged in nature. For this reason, a structuring system called "Lower-Level - Upper-Level" has emerged in nature. In this order in nature, the power to make belongs to the lower-levels (Feibleman (1954)) and the physics of dynamical systems, summarized as "information & self-organization" (Haken 2000), states that the rules that will apply at the Higher-Level will be formed by the mutual interactions of all the lower-level elements. The higher-level system that multiplying people will create is a common life called SOCIETY. Therefore, the rules of PUBLIC life have to be created by all the people in that society. But humanity has been divided into different religions and races by believing that the rules of public life will be created by special people with sacred essence due to a false view of the natural system.

In today's world, there are no longer clear borders between states, all the peoples of states are in relations and dependence on each other. Technology has advanced to such an extent that a member of a state, through a friend in another state, can perform a very harmful function to the people of that state. For this reason, all the people of the world turned into people traveling in the same ship. There is nothing in nature that is not based on mutual interaction. The task of creating a society is the task of us people. There is a life system based on the cycle of birth and death, and a natural system that is in constant change and transformation. It is the task of scientists to describe this system, explain how it works, and help regulate the functioning and regulation of the social system according to the principles of this natural system. As long as scientists who identify themselves as naturalists, physicists, chemists, biologists, geologists, paleontologists, physicians, etc., do not fulfill this task, no one will be able to prevent the religious merchants who peddled the information of the natural system builder of 3-4 thousand years ago from carrying out these works, and all the blame for this will be on the scientists who call themselves naturalists. We're all in the same "boat," and if this ship sinks, we all sink."

2. CHAPTER- METHOD

There is a life system based on the cycle of birth and death, and a natural system that is in constant change and transformation. It is the task of scientists to define this system, to explain how it works, and to help regulate the functioning and organization of the social system according to the principles of this natural system. As long as scientists who identify themselves as naturalists, physicists, chemists, biologists, geologists, paleontologists, physicians, etc., do not fulfill this task, no one will be able to prevent the religious merchants who peddled the natural system-building information of 3-4 thousand years ago from carrying out these tasks, and all the blame for this will be on the scientists who call themselves naturalists.

Now I would like to briefly summarize the history of humanity's levels of knowledge about nature and the world.

Article 1: The people of 2-3 thousand years ago believed that nature consisted of the quartet of "air, water, earth and fire" and that the constituent force was a divine

power outside of beings. Biblical religions emerge as a continuation of this basic view.

Article 2: This view continued until the 18th century, when a French chemist named Lavoisier discovered that substances in nature are composed of basic chemical elements such as oxygen, nitrogen, hydrogen, iron, etc., and developed in the 19th century when a Russian chemist named Mendeleev laid the foundation of the periodic table of elements.

Article 3: At the beginning of the 20th century, physicists and chemists revealed that substances are made up of molecules, and that molecules behave in accordance with the laws of thermodynamics. The laws of thermodynamics predict:

The first law of thermodynamics: The amount of energy in the universe is constant.

The second law of thermodynamics: Energy can neither be created nor destroyed. It can only be transformed from one shape to another. There is an "irreversible heat loss" when a job or action is performed in developments in nature.

And since then, these two laws of thermodynamics have been considered the cornerstones of physical science.

For example, when traveling by car, a small part of the fuel in the tank is converted into kinetic energy, while the remaining part is scattered to the environment as heat energy due to friction, etc. In other words, a hundred percent efficient energy transfer is not possible. For this reason, some energy is constantly lost as waste = unusable energy in formations in nature or in engines made by people. This lost energy will gradually increase over time, this is called ENTROPY increase. In other words, entropy will increase over time in the universe . Since these two basic principles are accepted as true, it has been and is still being defended by physicists that the end of the universe will end in chaos due to the increasing amount of irreversible energy.

Article 4: Thermodynamics is valid only in molecular systems. However, since substances are made up of atoms, atomic properties are also effective in their behavior. Atoms are in the micro-realm and molecules are in the macro-realm.

Therefore, entropy behavior, which is used in the sense of "intrinsic orientation", must be defined in a way that includes both realms.

Based on this basic idea, Ludwig Boltzmann (1872-1875) proposed that there is a definite connection between the entropy of an object and the probability of its macroscopic state, and defines entropy in a different way: $S = k \cdot \ln W$

In this formula

S = entropy,

\ln = logarithm

W = Wahrscheinlichkeit = probability = probability. That is, it is the number of states that a system can enter.

k is the Boltzmann constant.

This definition of entropy is in line with the developments in nature, because nature is the result of the combination of a large number of small and large sub-systems into more advanced super-systems. This means that nature will not go towards disorder and chaos, but will move in an orderly and developing direction.

However, since people in his time were conditioned by dogmatic thought systems, they were very opposed to this new view of Boltzmann. A relentless opposition, which he finds very difficult to deal with, causes Boltzmann to fall into depression and commit suicide.

Article 5: As can be seen at the beginning of the 1900s, there was no consensus on whether we were moving towards a naturally disordered system (chaos) or an orderly system (evolution) guided by the inner impulses of beings. Darwin (1859) showed that there was an evolutionary development in the world with his work "On the Origin of Species". However, the influential-decision-making power system was thought to belong to an external entity called the "natural selector". At this time (1901), Max Planck published the view that the most basic interaction elements of the forming power system in nature, which he called "quantum", constitute the entities in nature through the unification-reproduction system called "quantisation".

In other words, it reveals that the element called energy cannot be used indiscriminately, and that energy necessarily functions as the most basic interaction elements called quantum. Why was this opinion important? Because until then, there was a view that a power that created nature could use energy by increasing and decreasing it as it wished. The concept of quantum was the opposite: energy was like a living entity, indisintegrable and could always be used as a whole. In order for Planck to put forward this view, it should be known that he did not introduce the concept of entropy according to the law of thermodynamics, but according to Boltzmann's formula $S=k \cdot \ln W$.

After quantum physics determined that atoms consist of smaller elements called subatomic elements, and it was revealed that these quant elements operate with information and probability calculations, the term Shanon-entropy was coined and entropy began to be used in the sense of "information = information". As a result, the physics of dynamical systems, which is summarized as "information & self-organization" with Haken (2000), develops. Dynamical systems physics, on the other hand, predicts that the "maximum information principle", that is, the ability to create information, will develop gradually in nature. In other words, the 2nd phase of thermodynamics. It is experienced in a nature that is the opposite of its law. Nature is not heading towards disorder, but towards regularity.

Article 6: All theoretical physicists and natural scientists, including Einstein, did not think that beings were knowledgeable and conscious in the formation and development of nature. According to them, beings are robot-like elements that obey the laws of nature. They have no answer to the question of who created the laws of nature. Because physicists did not use a factor called INFORMATION in nature, they defended a view that everything in nature occurs through random events as a result of the collision of substances, and that a supernatural power system selects the good ones. However, in nature, every being has an impulse to live, and this impulse enables the being to perceive its environment and create KNOWLEDGE that will guide it according to the situation. For this reason, in parallel with the increase in the diversity of beings in nature, the development of knowledge has also increased

continuously. Since the growth of assets is in the form of a geometric series, the increase in knowledge has also increased exponentially.

Article 7: Physicists have thought of the concept of TIME as a process that operates according to the ticking of a clock. However, time emerges as a result of the accumulation of the lifetimes of beings. Because life is a cycle of birth and death. Life = life-span, and life-span is a slice of time. For this reason, time is the succession of changes and transformations that beings have undergone during their lives, that is, it is the 4th dimension.

The reason why people cannot be given a rational view of life in today's world is that scientists see beings as robots that obey the laws of nature. When scientists are unable to explain the mechanism of formation in nature, and when everything in nature is the result of random collisions without knowledge and consciousness, and when quantum physics reveals the extraordinary behavior of elements in the atomic world by measuring their surroundings with oscillation-steps, making probability calculations, acting consciously, interacting and communicating with each other on a universal scale, etc., creationists immediately jump on these data and say: "Look, there is an intelligent design in nature". They have dominated all debates. "Creationists = religionists" who advocate the knowledge-based view of "intelligent design" have always prevailed, because "knowledgeable and conscious" behaviour is indeed the basis of all formations and developments in nature. However, "creationists = religionists" have applied a complete double standard here: In the view of creation, knowledge belongs only to an eternal being conceived outside of beings, whereas knowledge in nature arises from the quantity within beings. Today, the blame for the continuation of this situation lies on all scientists, because they blindly continue their old conditioning, even though they find no data or logical errors in their knowledge of the of Dynamic Organisation Mechanism (DOM) in Nature. I call this "scientific prejudice, bigotry."

In order to understand the concept of "quantum" discovered by Planck (1901), it is necessary to know the basis of the formation-development system in nature. As shown in the Archive-Pages section, there is a system of formation in nature based on the creation of knowledge, from small to large, in the low-level – high-level style.

However, traditional views are that formations in nature are made and directed by an external power system. If it is under the control of a non-nature entity, that entity can use energy as it wishes, increasing or decreasing it as much as it wants. The concept of QUANTUM, which Planck discovered, revealed that energy transfers in nature could not be random. In other words, the processes in nature depended on an element of life called QUANTUM at the very base, and everything had to be formed in the form of QUANTIZATION of this element, that is, its multiplication by merging. In a nutshell: this element was alive and nature was made up of the combinations of that living element.

Physicists have found it difficult to understand the extraordinary behavior of the quantum system, as they have been conditioned by thousands of years of tradition that an external power system directs all formation and development in nature. Nobel Prize-winning physicist Feynman expressed this situation as follows:

"As you can see, my physics students don't understand either. That's because I can't understand (these) either. No one can understand. The other reason why you won't understand what I'm going to tell you is that I'm trying to explain to you how the natural system works, you won't be able to understand how the natural system works. But, as you can see, no one understands this. I can't explain why nature behaves in such a strange way."

What is the reason for such a helpless cry out of a Nobel Prize-winning physicist like Feynman?

There is only one reason: it is the view of the natural system that has been transmitted to him from the environment since childhood. In the traditional view of the natural system, entities are inanimate elements that obey the rules set by an external power system like robots. How would you expect a person to behave if such knowledge is ingrained in his subconscious?

As we go back to the past, the so-called information signals disappear more and more, neither radio waves, nor a birdsong, nor a rustling of leaves, nothing remains. There is neither the earth, nor the other planets, nor a star, they have all disappeared, and everything we call matter, such as minerals, water, stones, and soil, has

decomposed into its components. In other words, when you go to the beginning of the universe, you are faced with a chaotic energy aggregation consisting of a huge number of basic elements, such as 10 over a hundred-odd. The eternal longevity of the quanta is as follows: They also change and transform according to the changes and transformations in nature. That is, they support the "best knowledge formations" and leave the bad ones.

3. CAPTER- How To Get Information About The Development Of Nature?

Geological data provides us with precise records about both how our world was developed and when and where humanity was created. Now, to understand life and how the natural system developed, we must learn what our world's past was like. The way to find out is to make use of geology (Fig.4).

Figure 4: Mountainous area are constantly eroded, and those that are eroded are carried to the seas by rain and winds and stored.

Nature and the world are constantly changing and transforming. Land-areas are constantly eroded, and the eroded materials are transported and stored in the seas. For example, today's plastics, objects such as spoons and knives mix with the mud carried to the sea. In the layers formed a few thousand years ago, these substances are absent, because at that time the production of these substances was unknown.

In about 15-20 thousand years, layers with a thickness of several cm's are produced. The upper layer is younger, the lower layer is older.

In the layers, every event in the world is recorded.

Where and when an earthquake occurred,

Where and when a volcano erupts,

Where and when what kind of creatures lived in the world, when this creature appeared and when it disappeared; etc.

Events and formations that take place in nature are constantly recorded in layers in the seas. In this way, the history of our world is written in geological layers. By sequencing and examining these natural records of the past, the formation and development of nature and our world (and humanity) can be revealed in a way that is in accordance with the facts!

Archive Pages of the Earth

Events and formations that take place in nature are constantly recorded in layers in the seas. In this way, the history of our world written in sedimentary layers are presented as a geologic book.

What is told about our past in the ARCHIVE PAGES of our world? (Fig 5)

Figure 5: The layers formed in the seas accumulate on top of each other over time and form the ARCHIVE-PAGES of our world's past.

Let's look at the archive pages of our world and see what has changed as we go back to the past, that is, what has not been seen. If something does not exist, it means that the knowledge to do that thing has not yet been generated.

Archive pages show that our world is about 4.6 billion years old, that life began to develop 3.5 billion years ago and entered the phase of explosive development 550 million years ago, and that humanity has existed only for the last 2.5 million years.

When you go back 20,000 years, things that people used to do, such as spoon, fork, radio-TV, cars, planes, disappear. Because the people of that time lacked the knowledge to do these things.

When we go back 5 million years, there is no living thing called human. To disappear means to decompose into its atoms and molecules. Let's call it decomposition into its components. In this way, the elements that come together with KNOWLEDGE in an orderly structure disperse, an orderly higher-level system disappears and disorder increases.

Going back 100 million years, horses, cows, and fruit trees disappear and decompose into their constituents. In this way, the elements that come together with KNOWLEDGE in an orderly structure disperse, an orderly higher-level system disappears and disorder increases.

Going back 300 million years, creatures like dinosaurs disappear and decompose into their constituents. In this way, the elements that come together with KNOWLEDGE in an orderly structure disperse, an orderly higher-level system disappears and disorder increases.

Going back 700 million years, all vertebrates and invertebrates disappear and decompose into their components. In this way, the elements that come together in an orderly structure with KNOWLEDGE are dispersed, an orderly higher-level system disappears, and the disorder increases even more.

Go back 4 billion years, and the entire living world disappears. They are decomposed into their components. In this way, the orderly structures of the living world are destroyed, and everything is transformed into its components.

As can be seen, as we go back in time, the knowledge of how to make something is completely lost. So, as you go back in time, the ability to do something called KNOWLEDGE disappears.

If you go back 5 billion years, our world and our solar system are also destroyed. When the world disappears, molecules such as H₂O, CO₂ and quartz in the world decompose into their components and return to the star-galaxy phase. Galaxies and stars are composed of 75% hydrogen and 23% helium and 2% other elements. In other words, galaxies and stars are made up of simple chemical elements with one or two protons.

By 13 billion years ago, all stars and galaxies were disappearing, disintegrating into their constituent parts. When it comes to components, an explanation should be made. Hydrogen consists of a proton and an electron. Helium consists of 2 protons, 2 neutrons and 2 electrons; Carbon consists of 6 protons, 6 neutrons and 6 electrons. In other words, nature and our world consist of subatomic elements called protons-neutrons-electrons.

When we go back to the beginning of the universal system, everything is broken down into its smaller, most basic components. In 1900, a German physicist named Max Planck showed that this most fundamental element, called quantum and denoted by the symbol (h), is an "Elementares Wirkungsquantum = the least amount of action". Planck stated that these most fundamental action makers can never be divided and will be added together in the form of quantization to form larger higher-level systems. Researches in the following years showed that those quanta were the basic constructing units of nature. Then Heisenberg uncertainty principle require that it is impossible to measure the momentum and the position of quanta simultaneously. They must obey uncertainty principle $\Delta p \cdot \Delta x \geq h/4\pi$.

It is necessary to give the following information to explain why the concept of quantum and quantum physics are very important. Until the 1900s, it was thought that the agent called energy was something that could be increased as much as desired and decreased as desired. The concept of quantum and quantization, on the other hand, created the opposite situation: everything in nature revealed that this

most basic element called quanta could never be broken down and should always be used as a whole.

Quantum physics is incompatible with traditional views, as the traditional views are dominated by the view that the creator of nature and the world can use everything as he wishes, and therefore can regulate the distribution of energy as he wishes.

These most basic components, which emerge because of the decomposition of all beings in nature, reach a huge number. In other words, it is understood that the universe has begun to consist of a huge number of basic elements, such as quanta of a huge number, 10 to the power of hundred-odd.

Quantization can be in the form of arithmetic series such as 1,2,3,4,5,6, or in the form of geometric series such as 1-2-4-8-16-32-64, or in the form of the Fibonacci sequence known as the golden-ratio, 1-2-3-5-8-13-21-34-55. There are examples of these in nature.

As we go back in time, the information signals become less and less, there are no radio waves, no birdsong, no rustling of leaves, nothing. There is neither the earth, nor the other planets, nor a star, they have all disappeared, and everything we call matter, such as minerals, water, stones, and soil, has decomposed into its components. In other words, when you go to the beginning of the universe, you are faced with a chaotic energy aggregation consisting of a huge number of basic elements, perhaps “10 to the power of 120 (10^{120})”.

Was this chaotic cluster of energy scattered throughout the universe, or were they all collectively together? Astrophysicists believe that this cluster of energy is collectively held together, because there is evidence that there was a large expansion at the beginning of the universe.

Everything in nature happens through the COMBINATIONS of this most basic component called QUANTUM, and these combinations are called QUANTISATION. In other words, nature does not consist of nothing, but more than “10 to the power of hundred-odd” constructive basic elements. Physics experiments have shown that these most fundamental elements, known as subatomic elements, are

VERY SHORT-LIVED, and VERY MOBILE balls of energy. These are called as Quantum realm.

Archive pages and astrophysical data show unequivocally that nature and the world, as well as all living and non-living things on it, were decomposed into their components as we went back to the past, and that they were decomposed into the smallest structural elements in nature, called QUANTA, when it reached 13 billion years ago, which is the beginning of the universal system.

We are also looking for our Creator.

Among today's people, there are two opinions on this issue:

The First View: The Biblical View of Creation

The second view is the view of evolution based on Darwin's "Origin of Species" published in 1859.

Both views have one thing in common, which is that the creator is a system of Supernatural Power outside of beings. In the view of creation, this power is called GOD, and in the view of evolution, it is called NATURAL SELECTOR.

The difference between these two views is this: The creator of the Holy Books, like a sculptor, creates substances by combining them according to the information in his own mind, or everything comes into being when he says that he wants it to be. Evolutionists' natural selector, on the other hand, has established the laws of nature. Beings live according to these laws like robots. Changes occur in genes with random mutations. Those that are compatible with the environment are selected. In other words, in both views, beings are unconscious. Their fate depends on the Supernatural-Power system.

In this book, the opposite view is presented, which is that creativity in nature is initiated by QUANTUM elements. In other words, there is no Supernatural Power system in nature, there is a Lower-natural power system. This power system is the QUANTUM system.

As we go into the past, regular beings and things decrease and disorderly beings and things increase. In other words, nature and the world are not heading towards disorder, as physicists say. On the contrary, nature is moving more and more in the direction of orderly existence.

Nature and the world were not created out of thin air and suddenly by a being who knew everything in advance, but on the contrary, they were created and developed over a period of billions of years. First, the most basic elements such as atoms were formed, then molecules were formed by the combination of atoms, cells were formed by the combination of molecules, and other living things such as plants and animals were formed by the combination of cells. Thus, an integrated system has emerged that must evolve and develop in the form of lower-level, higher-level system, and dependent on each other.

Formations in nature are carried out by creating INFORMATION. Knowledge creation is gradually developed and diversified through the efforts of beings to SPECIALIZATION to specific fields and adaptation, and an evolutionary process is established.

Thus, the question "Has nature been created or is it developing?" is answered: Nature is developing!

Now, the following question is very important:

You are at the beginning of the universe, you are very dynamic, you are born and die in a fraction of less than a quadrillionth of a second, but you are resurrected after death. There is no relief for you. You have a huge population; you are struggling each other. You don't know anything, and there are no sources from which to get information. What should you do so that you can reach a more comfortable state?

The quanta that constitute the bodies of us and all other beings were completely ignorant and alone 13 billion years ago. What did they do to create our world and us? Since we have been brought up with the lie that nature and the world were created by a great creative power system, we always ask other questions. But don't reason and logic require us to ask the above question?

Now let's see the properties of these miraculous beings called quanta.

3.1. Important properties of quanta

Since quanta are the creators of the natural system, it is necessary to recognize this miraculous power system called QUANTUM.

The thing called quantum, denoted by the symbol (h) by Max Planck in 1900 has very important peculiarities as shown below. Nature is not formed from nothing, but from a huge amount of living beings called quanta through QUANTISATION processes.

Now, by giving examples from physics research that shows that the quantum realm is alive, let's show that the most basic element we call quanta is really the most basic life-elements.

The following information is based on FEYNMAN's (1985) "The Strange Theory of Light and Matter". Another version of this experiment is known as the "double-slit experiment". But there is a very important difference between them: in the double-slit experiment, many photons or electrons are passed through the slits, while in the "2 holes" experiment, only 1 element is passed.

As shown in the Fig 6, an experiment is prepared.

Figure 6: Experiment showing that the quantum system is alive and conscious (Modified from Feynman 1963).

A source is placed at point (S) and two curtains are placed in front of it. A detector (D) is placed at point (5) on the rearmost curtain. A hole is drilled on the curtain in between, at point (A).

The size of the hole is adjusted so that when 100 items are sent from source (S), only one item can pass through the hole.

A second hole (B) of the same size is drilled at a point slightly lower. When hole (A) is closed, it is verified that only one of the 100 items submitted has passed through the hole (B).

When both holes are kept open together, it is seen that the detector, which previously recorded an element (in position (5) shown in the Fig), no longer detects any element at all.

Surprise! When the holes were open one by one, one could pass through each hole, now both holes are open, but nothing goes through the hole. How does this work?

As the position of the detector is shifted, it is noticed that it begins to detect items. For example, it is revealed that four photons are detected at position (1).

Again, astonishment: the number of items that could pass through a hole was one. When both holes are open, how is it possible to have 4 items instead of 2?

Now let's think without prejudice: Are the beings that behave in the way described above unconscious-inanimate-soulless beings or conscious-living-souled beings?

When it is investigated according to which rule this change is, it is revealed that the sub-atomic units determine their behaviours by making a probability calculation.

In quantum systems, physicists speak of a wavelength. This concept of "wavelength" is not really a wavelength, but the measurement and evaluation steps of quantum elements. Quantum elements evaluate their goals with these steps. The step varies between values such as zero (0), (0.5), (1), (0.5), (0), (-0.5), (-1), (-0.5), (0). They look at which of these values they arrive at the target.

There are two options for those who want to reach (D) in position (5):

It will either go through hole (A) or hole (B). Both options are evaluated on a case-by-case basis:

Quanta begins to calculate its path from (A) to (D) according to its step; When it arrives at its destination, it looks at what value the oscillation step is located. Let's say it ended with a maximum value of (+1). Now it begins to calculate the other path (B) in the same way; Let's say it ended with a minimum value of (-1). The item adds these two values: $+1-1=0$. It squares zero: zero again. And the element makes its decision: In this case, there is no sense in arriving at the destination. Of the 100 items sent from (S), none can pass through the holes, and no items reach the detector (D).

For a quantum that wants to reach (D) at position (1), the value reached at the end of the (SAD) path is (+1), and the value reached at the end of the (SBD) path is (+1); $+1 +1 = 2$. 2 is squared: it equals 4.

In this case, 4 out of 100 items sent from (S) pass through the holes, and the detector records 4 items. Although the holes are normally large enough to pass only one item, 4 items pass through the holes that would normally let 2 items!

As can be seen, quantum elements behave according to probability calculations. The interesting aspect of probabilistic operations is the following. Let the normal value be considered 1 = one. When the calculation result is squared for values greater than 1, the result is greatly increased. When result values less than 1 are squared, they become smaller and smaller. For example, the square of 1.5 gives a growing value of 2.25, while the square of 0.5 gives a shrinking result of 0.25.

All events and operations in nature are also carried out according to the result of such a probability calculation. So why do quanta change behaviours? Because they are given the option to choose:

When only a hole is open, the item goes to that destination shown, since there is only one option in front of the item.

But when the two holes are open together, the item is given a choice. And the element behaves by calculating a probability.

Another miraculous feature of the quantum realm is the ability of quanta to make these probability calculation without going to the target. Quanta instantly perceive everything around them INSTANTANEOUSLY, they don't need to go there to measure and evaluate.

Imagine a creature that instantly perceives everything around them. Imagine a creature that understands how much and what kind of energy the entity has and acts accordingly, without going near it.

We understand that quanta have such a property from the following experiment: If the detector used to observe the quanta is defective, the quanta also detect the distortion rate of the detector and interfere according to the disturbance rate! The quantal properties presented above continue not only in the most basic element called quanta, but also in higher-level elements such as proton-neutron-electron, which are formed by their combinations.

Among other important features of quanta, it should be emphasized that they have extraordinary abilities, such as:

Quanta perceive the most ergonomic structures and migrate there: the "Tunneling effect".

Physicists have determined that quantum elements cross a seemingly insurmountable obstacle and migrate to more ergonomically located places (from A to B). Since they could not explain this phenomenon with physical logic and formulations, they produced a concept called "tunneling" and made a comment as if a tunnel was opened from A to B and the electron used that tunnel and passed.

Quantum elements can instantly communicate with each other on universal scale, EPR-Effect.

This property is known as Quantum-entanglement or EPR-Effect. One of the two quanta produced from the same source is sent to a laboratory in Japan and the other

to a laboratory in America. When these two quanta are examined at their arrival moment, it is seen that they show exactly opposite energetic properties to each other, indicating an energy balance. In other words, there is no limit for them, such as the speed of light for communication. **There is instant communication between them.**

Quanta are aware of whether they are being observed or not. This is called the Observer effect.

Nature is managed and developed by such an architect. Therefore, where the natural system will go depends on the information potential of the entities in it. For this reason, the future of our world depends on the knowledge we humans will create.

3.2. Quantum Elements Begin to Construct the Universe

It is understood from the earth's archive-pages and astrophysical data that everything in nature begins with the most basic elements of life called QUANTUM. Since the beings of today's world are made up of about a hundred basic chemical elements called atoms, atoms are made up of quanta. QUANTA are the most fundamental living beings at the beginning of our universe. Since they are the most basic living beings, they cannot be broken down into smaller units, that is, they cannot be broken down. Therefore, they must always begin to form the natural system as whole-complete individuals. This process of creation takes place in the form of their merging called QUANTISATION to form new higher-level systems.

So why do quanta come together and form a partnership?

Quanta are very short-lived and very dynamic. They are born and die in as little as a quadrillionth of a second. For this reason, they have the urge to unite into longer-lived and less mobile higher-level systems. This impulse is called the "relaxation drive". First, let's explain this impulse by giving the example of human life.

A person living alone must produce vegetables and grains, grind grains and make flour, provide meat for food, and make ovens and pottery. Such a person does not have time to rest. But by forming partnerships, dividing labour, and exchanging their products, they have reached a more comfortable level of living. This is called the

urge to relax, and it is formed based on mutual agreement and compromise. It is present in all beings in nature.

The huge number of quanta at the beginning of the universe begin to form new higher-level-systems by combining with quantization to relax. Each new higher-level-system is a product of new knowledge creation and should be seen as a SPECIALIZATION. For example, each of the chemical elements called atoms formed by quantization is a speciality. Molecules formed by the combination of atoms are different specialized elements.

We call these mini-tiny creatures quanta. QUANTIsATION has created a Lower-level Higher-level systems (Fig 7).

Figure 7: The growth of quanta in the form of quantization has led to the creation of new higher-level-systems.

First, let's explain what is meant by the terms Lower-level – Higher-level. We know that everything in nature is made up of atoms. For example, the water we drink is made up of hydrogen atoms, denoted by the symbol (H), and oxygen atoms, denoted by the symbol (O), and is denoted by the formula H₂O. The number (2) next to H in the formula indicates that there are 2 hydrogen atoms. There is one of the oxygen atoms. The Quartz molecule, known as flint, consists of 1 silicon and 2 oxygen atoms, indicated by the symbol SiO₂. As can be seen, the number of atoms in a molecule is indicated by a small-sized number added immediately at the end of the atom-symbol. Our food salt, on the other hand, is indicated by the formula NaCl, which consists of one sodium (Na) and one chlorine (Cl) atom.

The philosopher Feibleman (1954) formulated in his book "Theory of integrated levels" the most important relations between the lower-level and the higher-level as shown below:

- i. *In any organisation the higher level depends upon the lower.*
- ii. *For an organisation at any given level, its mechanism lies at the level below and its purpose at the level above.*
- iii. *A disturbance introduced into an organisation at any one level reverberates at all the levels it covers.*

"In every system, the upper level is dependent on the lower level. The power to make something is on the lower-level. The higher-level have to show a goal". This dependency is illustrated in the Fig 4. The molecule is the higher-level of atoms, and the power to form molecules belongs to its lower-level, atoms, etc.

3.3. The Oldest Page of Our History - The Formation of the Universe

Formation of matter from energy

Geological data, which contains records of our world's past, reveal that our world began to form about 4.6 billion years ago. Physics and astrophysics research provide information about the times before that. According to that information, the universe is a little more than 10 billion years old, and at that time there were only energy

elements called quanta in the universe. In other words, the universe does not consist of nothing, but of an energy system.

Now let's consider this very old past of ours as a bit of a fairy tale.

Once upon a time, when the griddle was in the straw and the earth, the sun and the stars in the sky did not form, there were very, very small energetic elements (living things) in the universe.

They were so small that they were 10^{-35} meter big. Numbers with many zeros are displayed in abbreviated form as follows:

$$\text{Thousand} = 1,000 = 10^3$$

$$\text{Thousandths} = 10^{-3}$$

$$\text{Million} = 1,000,000 = 10^6$$

$$\text{Millionth} = 10^{-6}$$

So a value of 10^{-35} is just one of a value divided by a value with 35 zeros=
1/100000000000....

The lifespan of these tiny creatures was so short that they were born and died in less than one quintillionth of a second.

Quintillionth = 0.000.000.000.000.000.001. The name given to such a short period of time is the atto-second.

The short representation of numbers with such small values is as follows: 10^{-18} This short notation reads as follows: 10 to the power of minus (-18).

These tiny creatures were so fast-moving that they could travel 300,000,000 meters per second.

In laboratories, the transformation of quantum energy into matter can be observed. With the so-called "pair-production", energy can be transformed into what we call matter (Fig 8).

Figure 8: The conversion of quantum energy into matter can be observed in laboratories.

To form an electron-positron pair, the total energy of the photons must be at least $2m_e c^2 = 2 \times 0.511 \text{ MeV} = 1.022 \text{ MeV}$; This value is an energy value corresponding to soft gamma-ray photons. (m_e is the mass of an electron, and c is the speed of light in vacuum).

The creation of a much larger pair, such as a proton and an antiproton, requires photons with an energy greater than 1.88 GeV (hard gamma-ray photons).

Laboratory experiments show that very energetic quantum elements such as gamma rays, that have no mass, turn into mass-rich fermion elements such as positrons and electrons if they pass around an atomic-nucleus. This phenomenon is called pair production. In other words, energy can be transformed into matter and anti-matter.

It is understood from the stages of geologic times described in the 1. chapter, that these energy clusters at the beginning of the universal system passed to form material beings in nature by producing matter and its antimatter by the method of pair production.

All these tiny creatures were together and therefore very uncomfortable colliding with each other. That's why they thought of a system that would create groups but still stay connected with each other.

3.4. The first step in creating matter from energy - the creation of an atomic nucleus.

It is understood from the earth's archive-pages and astrophysical data that everything in nature begins with the most basic elements of life called QUANTA. The formation of nature and the world has been progressed step by step within billions of years of knowledge-development and experience.

All beings in nature consist of an atomic nucleus and electrons located far away from that nucleus. The difference of atoms from each other is determined by the number of protons they contain; An atom with 1 proton is hydrogen, if it has 2 protons it is helium, if it has 6 protons it is carbon, etc.

Now let's look at this issue.

The proton is electrically (+) charged. Since the same charged elements must repel each other, it is impossible to create different chemical elements by increasing the number of protons in a nucleus. Thousands of different substances in nature cannot be formed with a single protonic element; but two protons can't come together because they have to repel each other because they have the same electric charge.

The strong interaction is the force that holds the protons together. Namely: it consists of smaller elements called quarks, proton consist of 2 up quarks and 1 down quark. The neutron is also made up of 3 quarks, but 2 down quarks and 1 up quark. Between these subatomic elements, called quarks, there is a system of attraction called "quantum-chromodynamics", which is based on the exchange of a colour-charge. A binding factor called gluon changes the colour-charges of quarks, converting up-quark into down-quark and down-quark into up-quark, thus converting protons into neutrons and neutrons into protons, preventing protons from repelling each other (Fig 9).

Figure 9: Strong-interaction functioning.

In other words, atomic nuclei are made up of boiling cauldrons, and protons are prevented from repelling each other by converting neutrons into protons and protons into neutrons in very short periods of trillionths of a second (Fig 10).

Figure 10: Chemical elements can be formed by converting protons into neutrons and neutrons into protons in atomic nuclei.

Since the elements of the quantum system are in a constant oscillation, i.e. cyclical motion, there is no fixed energy-potential value for them, because their energy-potential increases or decreases according to their level of motion. Therefore, the energy-potentials of subatomic elements are calculated as the value corresponding to the "rest mass = inertial mass" at which they are most stagnant.

The inertial mass value of the up-quark (u) is about $2.3 \text{ MeV}/c^2$

The inertial mass value of the Down-quark (d) is about $4.8 \text{ MeV}/c^2$.

The mass of the proton consisting of 2u and 1d quarks should be $2u+1d = 9.4 \text{ MeV}/c^2$.

However, the rest mass value of the proton, which consists of 2u and 1d quarks, has an enormous value of approximately $938 \text{ MeV}/c^2$.

So where did the investment come from to create proton (or neutron) extra-mass? In other words, there is a 100-fold mass increase. In other words, an enormous amount of energy is stored in the proton (and neutron), and the resulting nuclear energy according to the formula $E = mc^2$ is due to this strong-interaction effect.

A type of energy called color-charge has been used to hold quarks, the most basic element of matter, together. In as little as one zillion of a second, energy-balls with three different energy levels formed a continuously variable energy-gradient system, giving rise to protons and neutrons, which are the basic building blocks of all things in nature, called strong-interaction. The largest part of the energy in nature (99.2%) is devoted to this powerful interaction. $E=mc^2$ is the formula that shows how large this energy is. The source of nuclear energy comes from this powerful force.

In other words, 99.2% of the energy in nature is stored in atomic nuclei as strong forces. This energy stored in the nucleus enters the service of the assets in the form of "virtual particles" according to the needs of the asset, and the assets try to become compatible with nature by creating very different structures. Since all formations in nature are formed by the quantisation system, that is, by increasing or decreasing a certain value, the energy required for these increase or decrease processes is provided by the stored energy in the nucleus.

The miraculous state of knowledge in nature starts from this point. That is, if you assume the "constituting" power system in nature as a whole of 138 units, 137 units of these 138 units of energy are allocated to an interaction system called "strong-force". The remaining 1 unit is left for all other interactions, such as electromagnetic, weak-interaction, and gravity. Therefore, when the strong interaction is considered to be 1, the electromagnetic interaction takes on a value of 1/137, while the other forces are much, much less, such as one millionth to one billionth.

The electro-magnetic force, which is 137 times weaker than strong-interaction, is a type of interaction that has a certain volume and mass and makes up the 3-dimensional natural system that we call matter in the real sense. Electric charge works with this system, and the relationships between negatively charged electrons and positively charged nuclei are sustained by this force system. 1/137 is a valid

interaction coefficient on a fixed and universal scale. It is known as the fine-structure-constant. Due to this interaction factor, electrons are located at a distance of 1/137th of the square of the nucleus and never approach the proton in the nucleus.

With this powerful interaction system, nuclear elements such as protons and neutrons were created. How did these core elements turn into what we call matter, molecules? (Fig 11)

Figure 11: Atomic nuclei are formed by quarks, while atom-clumps in the form of molecules are formed by electrons binding nuclei.

The quantum system, which is in the form of balls of energy, has allocated the largest part of the energy to the smallest and innermost part of matter, which is called the atomic nucleus and is on the scale of the femtometer 10^{-15} m, in order to create longer-lasting and more comfortable structures (Fig 12).

Figure 12: After atom-nuclei are formed with strong-force electromagnetic interaction comes into play, and the formation of molecules that we know as matter produces an expansion of a millionfold.

On the other hand, there is an electro-magnetic interaction force between the positively charged nucleus and the negatively charged electrons, which have to stand at a very far distance from it, and they regulate their relationship with the interaction factor called photons. This electromagnetic interaction is 1/137th of the strong interaction, so it is very weak compared to it.

Negatively charged electrons make up the peripherals and can be at 3 different energy levels. The electron is at the lowest energy level, the "muon" has an energy that is ~200 times higher than it, and the "tau" has an energy that is ~3500 times higher. These high-energy "electron" versions are formed for a very, very short time when cosmic rays hit the atmosphere, when atoms break apart, and then dissociate into lower levels (Fig 13).

Figure 13: Forming matter Quantum elements are at 3 different energy levels, the lowest level of which are representatives of substances in nature, and the others are auxiliary.

The nucleus, on the other hand, consists of positively charged protons and neutral neutrons. These protons and neutrons, on the other hand, are made up of smaller elements called quarks, and they can have 3 different levels of energy. Quarks in normal matter in nature have the lowest energy-levels; Just as electrons are environmental-elements with the lowest energy level. High-energy quarks form during the disintegration of nuclei, and again for a very, very short period of time, and then dissociate again into lower-energy elements.

In other words, the realm of quanta, which consists of subatomic elements, is very short-lived and very mobile; They have a birth-death cycle. Since their life spans are

very short, they come together in upper-level-systems such as atoms, molecules, cells, and bodies to form longer-lived and less mobile beings.

A coefficient of approximately $1/137$, defined as "fine-structure-constant", plays a very important role in interactions in nature. So why $1/137$?

The fine-structure-constant is a value coined by Sommerfeld in 1916, taking into account the very small interval between the electromagnetic signals emitted by atoms – the atomic spectral lines – and specifies the amount of electromagnetic force change required for the exchange of photons in which electrons interact with their surroundings.

E.g.:

- This coefficient of $1/137$ is a universal value and is known as fine-structure-constant (coefficient). The fact that the electrons do not come close to the nucleus, but are located at a certain distance is related to the same factor ($1/137$ squared).
- Electrons take this coefficient into account when emitting or receiving a photon.
- The square root of the ratio of Planck, which is the most basic energy-exchange element, to the proton charge, called elementary charge, is $1/137$.
- The potential energy charge of the hydrogen atom, defined as Hartree-energy, is 27.2 eV; the energy of the electron in the normal state is 511 keV. The square root of the ratio of these two values is also $1/137$.

This mysterious $1/137$ constant has been defined as Fine-structure-constant. It is an extraordinary interaction factor that occurs not only in quantum physics relations, but also in all natural phenomena between gravity-force-electrostatic repulsion relations, weak-interaction and electromagnetic interactions.

In other words, the ratio of force systems that affect and direct nature is $1/137$.

The force, which is 137-fold effective and defined as "strong-interaction", is the force that holds the protons and neutrons together in the nuclei of our atoms and

works with a gravitational force called gluon. In other words, the natural system has made the greatest energy investment in atomic nuclei consisting of protons and neutrons. The electromagnetic force, which is 137th of this, corresponds to the type of force we use the most. Electro-magnetic interactions are made by signals called photons.

In other words, this constant value is an effective constant value in all electro-magnetic phenomena in the universe.

4. CHAPTER: Everything in Nature is made with Information

Information, on the other hand, is formed by inner components of beings.

How KNOWLEDGE is formed by its internal components.

When we see something new, that novelty around us is transferred to our cells. The cells in our brain also create a new protein that symbolizes that innovation and transmit this information by making new connections with other cells.

All human actions are carried out by cells inside the body. We are just a device that they have created to perform certain operations. Our cells are both the designers and repairers of our bodies. When we are injured, they begin to close the wound; when a harmful microbe enters our body, they train the "soldiers" to fight the harmful microbe, and they determine the "number of armies" that will be formed. When we get up from our house by the sea and start living on a plateau of 2-3 thousand meters, it is our cells that perceive that the oxygen rate decreases at that altitude and increase the number of red blood cells required to carry as much of this low density of oxygen as necessary. Those working in a satellite in space rise 3-5 meters with each jump and hit their head on the ceiling, due to the decrease in gravity. It is our cells themselves that decide that there is no need for so many muscle cells and make the excess muscle cells commit suicide!

How do CELLS, the internal components of our bodies, record, and store information?

The knowledge of how living things do a job is written in their genetic information booklets called genomes. Genomes also contain data on how that creature's body is

made. All features and functions such as how many arms and legs the creature will have, its colour, height, how it will digest food, and how the respiratory system will function are also written in the genomes. The living thing is created according to that information (fig 14).

Figure 14: The genomes of living things are made up of chemical elements called atoms. Whatever your chemistry is, you are "It".

Genetic information consists of DNA sequences in chromosome strands. These sequences contain written information with codons consisting of triplet nucleotides such as ATC, GTA, TGA, etc. These 3-codons are known as AMINOACIDS. Some of them, e.g. ATG (methionine) means START command; Some, e.g. TAA or TAG stands for "STOP". These words are used in the same sense by all living things. In this way, all the necessary letters are written 3 by 3 and the actions to be taken are described. DNA sequences consist of A (adenine) -T (thymine) and G (guanine)-C (cytosine) pairs. These A-T and G-C pairs are made up of chemical elements such as nitrogen, hydrogen, carbon, and oxygen. Therefore, all knowledge is written by chemical elements, that is, by combinations of basic elements that we call atoms. In other words, the creator of the natural system has booklets called GENOME, and every living thing has its own booklet.

Now let's look at how the beings in nature are formed. As shown in the previous section, at the beginning of the universal system there are only quantum energy elements, and everything arises as a result of their combination. The first to appear are the subatomic elements called proton-neutron and electron. All chemical elements are made up of this triad. Since all information is recorded as chemical

element-combinations, which we call atoms, and since atoms are made up of quanta, which are the most basic components, all information is recorded in the quanta alphabet. In other words, the works of the creator are written entirely in the quantum alphabet.

4.1. How was knowledge developed in the living world?

In the archive pages, it is seen that life began about 3.5 billion years ago with prokaryotic single-celled organisms such as archaea and bacteria. The genomes of these creatures consist of a rosary-shaped chromosome strand in the cell cytoplasm. Not much information can be stored in a rosary-shaped structure, because in rosaries that are too long, the beads mix with each other and form blind knots (Fig. 15).

Figure 15: The gene of prokaryotes, such as bacteria, is shaped like a rosary.

The genome of prokaryotes is shaped like a prayer beads.

About 2 billion years ago, eukaryotic single-celled organisms such as amoebas appeared. In eukaryotic cells, a special section called the nucleus is reserved for chromosome strands. The chromosome strands protected in the nucleus are not in the form of rosaries, but in the form of chains of genetic information wrapped in a set of proteins called histones (Fig 16).

Figure 16: In eukaryotic cells, a special section such as a nucleus is formed, and genetic information is stored by wrapping it in special structures such as a spool called histone.

In this way, genome information is stored in the form of strands wound on a reel, and the storage capacity of INFORMATION is increased tremendously. Since eukaryotic cells have enormous information storage capacities, they have reached the knowledge that the way to use energy more effectively is to unite and form partnerships, and they created the first multicellular organisms about 700 million years ago.

4.2. Knowledge increases Power, creates Wealth, and new HIGHER-LEVEL systems emerge.

To understand this, think of it this way: You have an apple and I have a pear. If I give you the apple and you give me the pear, there will be no enrichment. But if you give me the knowledge you have, and I give you the knowledge I have, we will both be enriched and our power will increase.

Quantisation is the formation of power increase as a result of overlapping coherent signals (Fig 17).

Figure 17: Quantization creates a power boost

The formation of beings in nature has also taken place with knowledge. The growth of a living being begins with the reproduction of a fertilized cell. 1 cell divides, multiplying information, 2 cells are formed; those two cells proliferate to 4 cells; those 4 cells proliferate to 8 cells and in this way a body consisting of billions of cells emerge. In other words, bodies are formed by the proliferation of cells. When such a development is graphically shown, the following Fig emerges (Fig 18).

Figure 18: Growth develops exponentially, and after 15-20 generations it takes an explosive shape, paving the way for the formation of a new higher-level – the Body is formed from the cell.

Knowledge therefore develops exponentially. Now let's see the scientific data showing that the increase in KNOWLEDGE has been in a continuous increase and development for 12-13 billion years.

Chaisson Diagram

Chaisson (2001, 2010) conducts research showing that developments in nature can be measured and evaluated by a parameter he defines as Energy Rate Density. Chaisson's research has shown that the trend from simple to complex structures in nature has developed due to increasing the intensity of energy flow.

Figure 19: Information also shows exponential growth on a universal scale.

Energy-Rate-density is defined as the amount of energy flowing through a gram of mass in one second (erg/s/g). While the energy flow density is around 1 erg per second in galaxies, it is 3-4 ergs in stars, 70-80 ergs in planets, 700-800 ergs in the plant kingdom, about 10 thousand ergs in animals, about 100 thousand ergs in our brains, and around 500 thousand ergs in social life. As can be seen in the (Fig 16), the times of the emergence of these different entities indicate that the energy-flow-density has been increased over time.

Since work is done with energy, doing larger work in a shorter time requires intensive and harmonious use of energy, which is called energy rate intensity (Chaisson, 2001).

It can be seen from the Chaisson diagram that there is a progress towards the more ergonomic use of energy over time by creating information in the universe. The Chaisson diagram also shows that atoms and molecules are combined differently on planets like our world to create more information.

4.3. There is also an increase in KNOWLEDGE in the formation of the living beings throughout the world.

Sharov (2006) thinks that this progression from simple to complex beings in the living kingdom must also be based on the knowledge-forming capacity in the living kingdom. Since it is known that the information about living things is found in the genetic records of living things, how does this information change in the living world?

This question was answered by Adami et al. (2000). They showed that complexity is proportional to the size of functional and non-redundant genome in the genetic record of living things.

Based on this resolution, Sharov (2006) investigates the capacity for knowledge in this transition from simple to complex beings in the living world. He compares the data on the "functional and indispensable genome sizes" of important groups in the living kingdom with each other and realizes that the information capacity (and therefore the level of complexity) increases exponentially.

Sharov's data can be seen in the diagram (Fig 20).

Figure 20: The development of information of living things is written in a 4-unit system of molecules called nucleotide-pairs.

Genome sizes are given as nucleotide-pairs = base pair = bp.

The molecules adenine (A), thymine (T), guanine (G) and cytosine (C) are known as nucleotides.

Since they are conjugate with A-T, G-C, they are called nucleotide-pairs.

If the above data are placed on a diagram according to the time of the appearance of these living groups on earth, it is seen that they multiply as an exponential function. In other words, KNOWLEDGE multiplies like a living entity.

When the genome size data is represented in a logarithmic-scale diagram, the distribution line is linear (Fig 21).

Figure 21: Genome-size time relationship graph from Sharov 2006

As can be seen, as we go back in the living world, the size of the genome (information capacity) is gradually decreasing. But it doesn't happen zero.

So, when does it become zero? So when does it become zero? Whenever the linear line in the diagram reaches a value of zero (0), the genome value becomes zero. The calculation method is shown in the Fig below. According to this calculation, the beginning of life on Earth must have begun much earlier than the 4.5 billion years ago of the formation of our world (i.e. about 9.8 billion years ago) (Fig 22).

Figure 22: Diagram showing the time of the beginning of life taken from Sharov & Gordon (2013).

The implication of Sharov's view is that the system of life begins with a prokaryotic organism with a value of 5,105 bp in our world. It takes a while for these 5,105 (i.e. 500 000) bp (nucleotide-pairs) to form. If the time required for such a large record of genetic information to occur is calculated, it must take as much time as shown in the Fig 19. Therefore, life began to form about 10 billion years ago, and the information to form the first nucleotide pairs must have formed at that time.

In other words, the first amino acids began to form in space about 10 billion years ago.

As can be seen, nature is formed by combining elements by creating information in a way that creates more ergonomic structures of energy. And the fact that the information that makes up living things is made up of chemical elements called genes confirms this.

4.4. The development in the Sharov diagram is also supported by paleontological findings, and an explosive, exponential development is observed in the living kingdom.

Nature and the world began to be formed by the quanta about 10-12 billion years ago with the information-based system summarized above. About 5 billion years ago, the solar system and our Earth were formed. 3.5 billion years ago, the world of living things was started in our world with nucleated single-celled bacteria, and then single-celled organisms with nuclei such as amoebas were created. Then multicellular organisms such as worms are created, then marine organisms such as insects, fish, corals, mussels, snails, etc (Fig 23).

Figure 23: By reading the Earth's archive pages, it is possible to determine exactly when the groups of living things on our world appeared.

In other words, until 500 million years ago, life existed only in marine environments. There is no living thing on land. Between 400 and 500 million years, life also transitions to terrestrial environments.

What does this mean?

The ability to create knowledge is not yet at a level that will initiate life on land. This shows us that the creative system in nature is not a system that knows everything in advance.

The first creatures to cross land were plants called lichens. In the course of time, more advanced plants emerge and the amphibian group of animals, insects, etc., that follow them, develop terrestrial life.

Then, 300 million years ago, huge animals like dinosaurs were created. And about 2.5 million years ago, humans were formed. Human beings are the species that prioritize the creation of KNOWLEDGE. All these formations, on the other hand, are organized and developed by a dynamic system summarized as "information & self-organization- (Haken 2000)" by the most basic quantum system.

As can be seen, nature is moving in the direction of using energy in a way that creates more ergonomic structures. This is achieved by combining elements with INFORMATION. And the fact that the information that makes up living things is made up of chemical elements called genes confirms this.

4.5. The knowledge increase of humans is also developing exponentially.

2-3 centuries ago, it would have taken dozens of horse-drawn carriages and weeks to carry a 10-ton load from Ankara to Istanbul. However, nowadays, we can do this job in 5-6 hours with a truck. Over time, molecules and substances were put into such a combination that energy was used more effectively with those new combinations.

This was achieved thanks to the "knowledge" factor. 300 years ago, there were atoms and molecules in our world, and today there exist too. The only thing that has changed is that those molecules are assembled in a truck fashion, not a in horse-and-buggy fashion. In this way, people can do bigger things in a shorter time (Fig. 24).

Figure 24: The information generated by humans increases exponentially over time.

In other words, nature and our world are a dynamic system. It is the quantum system that initiates and sustains all this dynamism. Our bodies are made up of cells, molecules, atoms, and subatomic elements that we call quantum systems. There are 100,000 chemical processes per second in each cell of our body (McTaggart 2008). In these processes, chemical elements such as C, H, O, undergo changes-transformations according to the changing energy states in their environment and form new material combinations suitable for changing environmental conditions. The impulse that causes all these changes and transformations is described as the "relaxation impulse" and is realized in the form of increasing the "energy-rate-intensity" (Chaisson 2001, 2011). How to increase the energy-density must be done by creating "knowledge", as is clearly evident from the fact that the development of knowledge is exponential, as shown in the Fig above. Information, on the other hand, is stored and transferred by integrating it into the chemical compositions of entities, as Kandel (2001) proved.

For this reason, the increase in knowledge has been developing for 12-13 billion years. Since nature is a dynamic system in continuing change-over (transformation), beings have to perceive the changes-transformations in their environment and make

changes in their own structure (composition) in accordance with it. Therefore, the formation of knowledge is constantly increased. The genetic record data of living things show that this increase in information develops exponentially (Fig 25).

Figure 25: Information is a factor of exponential growth. Molecules are formed, re-informed and organized; Cells are formed, informed and reorganized, etc. $e^{\lambda x}$

Namely:

If something is developing exponentially, there must be a factor that constantly pushes it. Since knowledge develops exponentially, the urge to "create knowledge" is a factor that must be at the basis of all developments in nature.

One of the basic principles of mathematics is related to this issue and has a basic rule that "Exponential functions are $y=e^x$, and the derivatives of exponential functions always remain e^x and never reset".

What this means is that the ability to generate information cannot be limited only to living beings such as humans or cells but will continue down to the smallest particles of matter.

4.6. How was life started? What and where does vitality begin?

The phenomenon of quantum energy lies at the basis of the constant changes and transformations in nature. Experiments in Quantum physics show that fundamental

entities such as protons, neutrons, electrons, and photons, which we call subatomic elements, are not dead or inanimate, but on the contrary, they are chirping, that is, alive. With the prejudice created by the static-system perspective, physicists define these fundamental entities as "particles". In their experiments with them, they determined that these elements have the feature of "particle" like a marble or "fluctuation" like a moving element. When they were investigated when they were a particle and when they were a "wave", they realized that they were a particle if they were observed, and a "wave" if they were not. They called this dual property "wave-particle duality". They explain this change in behaviour as "the observer collapses the wave function".

Now let's put a point here and think about it. All subatomic elements such as proton-neutron-electron-photon, as well as atoms, exhibit "wave-particle duality". The factor that directs the entities we call force is formed by the flow of energy from one place to another. All energies in nature originate from the most basic subatomic elements called quanta, such as photons.

The so-called observer is a detector, a sensor, an instrument that serves to detect a photon or electron. That instrument doesn't send an energy (or force) to the electron or photon, it just tries to sense the energy coming from them. There is activity, an event: the "fluctuation" property of the subatomic element is lost. It takes energy to create or lose (to destroy) something. Energy, on the other hand, is in the "lost element". The detector does not emit energy to the environment, it is used to perceive the energies coming from the environment. In this case, it is not the detector that is active, but the electron or photon, they perceive that there is a detector in their environment that wants to establish a relationship with them; It even detects how intact or distorted the detector is and behaves as a wave or particle depending on that distortion rate!

Have you been able to form a basic idea in your mind about where life in nature is and what it starts with? Vitality and life in nature begin with the world of subatomic elements and continue with million-billion-year processes in the form of lower-level higher-level system formations with factors such as dynamical systems physics, which is summarized as "information & self-organization".

Scientists still don't know how life started on Earth, and did it come from space, and if so, how did it develop in space? They are dealing with such questions. But they still ignore the miraculous QUANTUM power system in front of them and treat them as "particles". This is a typical indication of how blind the logic of humanity has become.

The ARCHIVE-PAGES of our world show that the creators of the natural system began with a most basic element of life called QUANTUM. The fact that quanta migrate to the structures formed according to the best information and abandon the bad ones shows that they attach great importance to the information factor. For this reason, the formation of KNOWLEDGE in nature develops both at the universal level (the realm of inanimate things) and with an exponential function in the world of living things.

5. Chapter: Dynamical Systems Physics summarized as Information & Self-Organization

In this section, the method of creating nature and the world by the realm of quanta, which is the constituent of the natural system, will be explained. The most important of these is the principle that the rules that will be valid in an higher-levelsystem must be constructed by the mutual interaction of all participants.

QUANTA are the most basic life-element in nature and everything in nature is formed by the combination of QUANTA via quantisation. So why do quanta want to come together into a partnership?

Quanta are very short-lived and very dynamic. They are born and die in as little as a quadrillionth of a second. For this reason, they have the urge to unite into longer-lived and less mobile higher-level systems. This impulse is called the "relaxation drive." First, let's explain this impulse by giving the example of human life (Fig 26).

Figure 26: The natural system is developing in the form of the combination of quanta, which is the most basic element of vitality, to form more comfortable higher-level systems

A person living alone must produce vegetables and grains, grind grains and make flour, provide meat for food, and make ovens and pottery. Such a person does not have time to rest. But by forming partnerships, dividing labour, and exchanging their products, they have reached a more comfortable level of living. This is called the urge to relax, and it is formed based on mutual agreement and compromise. It is present in all beings in nature.

Relaxation of atoms by working together

When beings are in a difficult situation, they mutually compromise and act together. Laser light is an example of this (Fig 27).

Figure 27: Laser light is the product of molecules entering into a harmony-partnership relationship with each other.

Certain molecules are trapped in a tube. One end of the tube is covered with a fully reflective mirror and the other end is covered with a semi-reflective-semi-permeable mirror. Then, a beam to which these molecules are sensitive begins to be sent from the outside to the molecules inside the tube. The electrons of the molecules that receive the rays beam first swells their halo, but then they have to relax by emitting it back to the environment. The rays emitted to the environment are reflected from the mirrors. Since the radiation coming from the outside is continuous, the molecules in the tube enter a very overwhelming state with the addition of the rays reflected from the mirrors.

There is only one way out of this difficult situation: If the electrons of each molecule send the rays they will release into the environment in the direction of the semi-reflective mirror and at the same phase and frequency as each other, these rays will overlap on top of each other, their power will add to each other, and they can go out of the semi-transparent mirror.

And the molecules that are cramped in the tube thus reduce the pressure in the tube, and the people who make the assembly get a very powerful laser light.

Laser light is a COHERENT light. It comes from the Latin word *cohaerere*. Co = together, haerere = sticking. Therefore, it is the behaviour of elements within a system to act together and form a partnership with each other. Cells in living bodies have also formed a system of partnership by communicating with a coherent signal called a "biophoton" in order to ensure that the work in the body is in accordance with the common interests of all cells (Popp 2002, 2003).

When the signals emitted by atoms or molecules are compatible, they pierce the semi-reflector at the end of the tube and come out, and the tube is relaxed. In other words, in the natural system, beings solve their problems by making partnerships.

Based on his observations in the examples presented above, Haken (1983 and 2000) realizes that the formations and developments in nature take place in the form of new higher-level systems by combining as a result of the inner impulses of beings, and that this formation mechanism is provided by the creation of a new "KNOWLEDGE". Until then, no physicist had used a factor called

"INFORMATION" in the developments in nature, but Haken broke new ground by putting the parameter "INFORMATION" at the center of the formations and developments in nature.

The most basic parameters of the of Dynamical Systems Physics

The physics of dynamical systems describes the events that occur during the formation of an higher-level system. The most important of these events is the issue of how to create the "CONSTITUTION" that will be valid in the higher-level system. To illustrate: Cells intended to form a body. How should the "laws = order-parameter" that will apply in this body be established? This will be explained below.

Informator (Order Parameter) = Partnership-law

How are the FORCE-fields that guide the entities formed (Fig 28)?

Figure 28: Entities that want to live together in a system establish the rules of partnership by agreeing among themselves (From Haken 2000).

Haken (2000) begins by creating a new term called "informator, or order-parameter" for the factor that affects entities. Informator means something like "informative" and is the information on how to determine the behaviour of the elements in question, meaning the "law of partnership" that will apply within a system. Since the informator is provided by consensus of all participants, all interested parties (or participants) comply with it. For this reason, it has been said that "the force field

enslaves atoms". Instead, it would be more appropriate to "atoms obey the consensus they have formed."Symmetry Breaking-Enslavement-Fixation.

The transition from the state of "does everything" to the state of "does a certain thing" is called "symmetry-breaking" (Fig 29).

Figure 29: Symmetry breaking is when lower-level elements change from doing anything to doing something to a behavior that can do something in order to form a higher-level entity.

This object at the top is nothing like a marble. On the contrary, it is the most basic element of life in nature.

Now let's see the symmetry break that the cells undergo while the body is being formed. In lower-level - Higher-level relationships the ability to do something is at the lower levels, they behave in such a manner that they reach the target that is shown to them (or to do the task assigned). For example, there are more than a hundred organs in our body, such as liver and kidney. All these different organs are initially made up of a single cell. This cell, which we call a stem cell, behaves in a way that does the task in whichever organ is targeted (Fig 30).

Figure 30: The transition to the Gastrula stage in multicellular organisms is the stage of symmetry breaking.

Cells begin to multiply in the form of geometric sequences such as 2-4-8-16-etc., and the foundation of the body is laid. Until this stage, called the blastula, all cells

multiply in such a way that they are the same and form a spherical shape filled with fluid. Thus, the first stages of growth of all multicellular animals are completely like each other.

If you take any of the cells at this stage and start replicating again, that cell will multiply again in the form of 2-4-8-16- etc. and can form a new organism.

But when this structure begins to form an inward «abdominal cavity», the fate and characteristics of all the cells that will make up the body change! Cells undergo such a radical change that if these cells are detached from the body and left to reproduce again, they cannot reproduce in the form of 2-4-8-16 and form a new body again, like their brethren in the previous stage. The reason for this loss of ability is symmetry breaking. How to make something, what shape it will take, etc., is always based on information, and information is stored in the chemical composition of molecules.

In other words, stem cells have a versatile ability to perform different tasks in all the different organs in the body; But when they are asked to function in one organ, they act in such a way that all other abilities are turned off and they only perform the task in the organ shown. The medical method called stem cell therapy takes advantage of this symmetry breaking. Stem cells placed in a diseased organ repair that organ again.

Maximum Information principle (MIP)= Ocean of signals that we call ETHER and MIP

It is necessary to explain the term "ether" to describe how information increases in nature.

Every place around us (atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere, outer space, etc.) is filled with various radiations. We can't perceive it directly, but when we slide the knob of a radio receiver left and right and pick up the waves of the different broadcasts we hear, we notice how many different signals are around us. What we call Ether is made up of this ocean of signals.

Beings change their structure according to the changes and transformations in their environment. When their structure changes, the signals they emit to their

environment also change. For this reason, the signals in the ether ocean are also in constant change.

Today, there are many new types of signals in this ocean of ether, such as mobile phones, the Internet, televisions, and so on. However, such signals did not exist in the atmosphere of hundred years ago, because the materials that produced these signals did not yet existed in nature. Therefore, for a signal to exist in space, the substance that makes up that signal must have been formed in nature.

Beings determine their behaviour by leveraging signals within the ether. For example, migratory birds, fish, etc., use the earth's magnetic field to determine their direction, and in this way, they travel from one point in Africa to another in northern Europe and never lose their way. All living things know when to multiply and when to go into sleep mode by sensing the signals in the ocean of ether around them. In short, ether is the news source of all beings.

The principle of Maximum Information is the most important feature of dynamic systems, because in a world where everything changes and transforms, the collection of «Information» about changes and transformations is at the forefront (Fig 31).

Figure 31: Everything in nature is constructed with INFORMATION

(We see and know that everything in nature is in a constant change and transformation. So, do we know how these changes and transformations happen and why? No! With the PHYSICS OF DYNAMIC SYSTEMS, which is summarized as "information & self-organization", the German physics professor has shed light on this issue and revealed that everything in nature is done by inventing KNOWLEDGE

and information is constantly being improved. In this way, the KNOWLEDGE factor is introduced into physical science. But how many physicists are aware of this? What is taught in Schools and Universities? None of that.)

The urge to relax and the Dynamic-System relationship.

The reason why beings combine to form greater higher-levels over time is because of the RELAXATION IMPULSE.

Consider the very ephemeral quantum elements that were in constant motion at the beginning of the universal system. Very moving, right-left, up-down, forward-backward; What should these quantum creatures, which interact with zillions of other quantum creatures around them, in a constant oscillation and vibration, do so that they can reach a more comfortable state (Fig 32)?

Figure 32: The urge to relax

To answer this, let's look at people's behaviour: If people lived alone, they would have to do everything on their own and they wouldn't have time to scratch their heads. But by forming partnerships, dividing labor, and exchanging their products, they have reached a more comfortable level of living. This is called the urge to relax, and it is present in all beings in nature. The path to relaxation is the SPECIALIZATION event.

In the dynamical system, the influencing-directing factor is in the intrinsic components of beings, and the innermost component, the quanta, are alive and form and direct all of nature. Nature and the world are in a constant change-transformation

and these changes-transformations are made by creating KNOWLEDGE. KNOWLEDGE, on the other hand, is formed by the intrinsic components of beings. For example, a person's information is generated by cells in their brain. The innermost components of beings are the QUANTUM system, which consists of subatomic elements. Experiments show that the quantum system behaves in a knowledgeable and conscious manner.

Since the development of knowledge develops exponentially, and since the most basic subatomic elements are also knowledge-conscious, other entities in nature are formed by their quantization (i.e., their growth by adding to each other). Therefore, knowledge and consciousness exist in every being, but their proportions and imaginations are very different. There are enormous differences between the imagination of a bacterium and the imagination of a mussel, of a human.

In the dynamic system, the rules that will apply to the higher systems are made by mutually agreeing with the lower-level elements.

Therefore, orientation in the natural system is in the form of creating information by evaluating the environment and regulating its structure-state according to that information. Elements are not fixed-immutable, dead thing, but on the contrary, they are very mobile and alive. It is an energy-field that is constantly changing and developing according to the changes in nature. This system, which is in constant change-transformation, is called DYNAMIC SYSTEM.

6. CHAPTER: Time-Information-Energy Relations and Eternity

In this section, it will be shown that today's concepts of TIME and INFORMATION are not compatible with the developments of TIME and INFORMATION in the nature.

Time-Information-Energy Relations

Let's start with the concept of TIME.

What is time, how is it formed?

Imagine a game where everyone must stay silent as if they are completely dead when you say "click". Now imagine that this game is played on a universal scale. Humans are frozen, all the cells and molecules in the human body are frozen, so bodily events such as the feeling of hunger do not occur. The Earth does not rotate, it always stays in the same position, so there is no such thing as day and night. The Earth does not revolve around the sun either, so the concept we call a year does not occur. The Moon does not revolve around the Earth, the Sun is stationary in the Milky Way galaxy, etc.

In such a case a concept called "time" does not occur.

Now let's look at the concept of KNOWLEDGE

Knowledge factor was explained in the 3. chapter. The information acts as a traffic sign that determines where the energy will flow from where. In this way, each newly formed being creates new information and tries to reach a more comfortable level of life by using energy more ergonomically. As a result, information is constantly increasing in nature.

Genetic information consists of DNA sequences in chromosome strands. These sequences contain written information with codons consisting of triplet nucleotides such as ATC, GTA, TGA, etc. These 3-codons are known as AMINOACIDS. Some of them, e.g. ATG (methionine) means START command; Some, e.g. TAG stands for "STOP". These words are used in the same sense by all living things. In this way, all the following words are written 3 by 3 and the actions to be taken are described. DNA sequences consist of A (adenine)-T (thymine) and G (guanine)-C (cytosine) pairs. These A-T and G-C pairs are made up of chemical elements such as nitrogen, hydrogen, carbon and oxygen. Therefore, all knowledge is written by chemical elements, that is, by combinations of basic elements that we call atoms. In other words, the creator of the natural system has booklets called GENOME, and every living thing has its own booklet.

Now let's see if a relationship can be established between these two different concepts.

The concept of time requires that there be a factor that requires beings to move. What could this factor be? ARCHIVE-PAGES and astrophysics data provide information on this subject. Let's look at these sources. The ARCHIVE PAGES of the Earth are the works of the creative system that created nature, and they are certainly the records of the creator we call GOD. There is nothing to dispute or suspect about this, because it is widely accepted by all the nations of the world.

The ARCHIVE-PAGES records shown in the Fig show that our world has a history of 4.6 billion years. This process, called the geological TIME-TABLE

CENOZOIC = current-living epoch (65 million years to the present)

MESOZOIC = Medieval Age (between 65 million and 250 million years)

PALEOZOIC = ancient-age (between 250 million and 550 million years ago)

PRECAMBRIAN = Precambrian period (between 550 million and 4600 million years ago).

The first living things on our 4.6-billion-year-old Earth were prokaryotic archaeobacteria, approximately 1-micron in size, found in layers 3.8 billion years ago. Then, when prokaryotic bacteria merged, eukaryotic cells (amoeba, etc.) 100 times larger in size appeared about 2 billion years ago. Then, 550-600 million years ago, multicellular plants and animals were formed by the union of eukaryotic cells. All these formations have always been in the seas. About 420 million years ago, the transition of life from the seas to the land took place.

The fact that life could develop both in the seas, on land and in the air leads to an increase in the diversity of life, with a gigantic animal like the Dinosaur in the Mesozoic.

Then, 65 million years ago, a very large meteorite hit our world, and because of a tremendous climatic disaster, 3/4 of the creatures (including dinosaurs) in both the seas and the land disappeared.

After this great extinction, life thrives again, and MAMMALS begin to fill the ecological void left by the dinosaurs.

The formation of all these new living species has always been due to the fact that beings perceive the changes and transformations in their environment and try to create new body designs that are compatible with them. The importance of living things to creating KNOWLEDGE makes it a very important stage about 50 million years ago, and the formation of living things called PRIMATA, which prioritizes KNOWLEDGE CREATION, begins. HUMAN, on the other hand, is a cellular design that prioritizes giving importance to information and begins to form about 5 million years ago. And it develops to a level that will change the world.

As can be seen in the Fig, the phenomenon called time is based on the differences in appearance that arise due to the change in the composition of beings. If the compositions of the beings never change, if all the beings continue with the same composition, time does not occur. This fact has never been noticed by all mankind, including physicists and biologists.

The data of the archive pages show that the change-transformation factor called TIME emerges with a factor called INFORMATION, when substances gain different properties. Physics experiments and astrophysics data show that all formations and developments in nature were initiated by an element of life called QUANTUM, which was defined by Max Planck in 1900 as "elementares WirkungsQuantum = the most basic intrinsic impulse, the amount of motive element in nature" (Fig 33).

Figure 33: The natural system is initiated with a most basic element of life called QUANTUM.

In other words, at the beginning of the universal system, everything begins with the most basic elements of life called quantum. It is calculated that their number should be much more than 10 to the power of 100. The important characteristics of this enormous number of basic organisms, which are shown in a very simple way in the Fig 30 (such as their ability to instantly evaluate everything around them, to communicate instantly on a universal scale, etc.), have been shown in the previous files.

As can be seen in the Fig, the most important feature of basic living things called quanta is that they are in a change-transformation in the form of positivity-negativity and have a purpose-goal. The achievement of this basic goal and goal started about 12-13 billion years ago and is developing with QUANTISATION (Fig 34).

Figure 34: The most fundamental living thing called quanta begins to form the natural system by forming a proton-neutron-electron triad.

Since the formation of the natural system was initiated by the most basic element of life called quanta, the subsequent developments have always been in the form of the exponential multiplication of this most basic element, which is called quantisation. Since quanta are basic living things, they cannot be divided, they are not fragmented, they always continue to exist as a whole.

With the quantization method, subatomic elements such as protons-neutrons-electrons are first created. Then, with the combination of these subatomic elements, the basic chemical elements that we call atoms are formed. Then, in their combinations, larger entities such as molecules are formed and the formation of the natural system is maintained.

As you can see, there is a very close relationship between INFORMATION and TIME. A new formation of existence takes place in information, and since quanta prefer entities formed according to the best information and abandon the bad ones, a development called evolution emerges.

The most basic element of life called quanta was discovered as a result of investigating how energy is transferred in nature. In other words, quanta are the most basic energy sources in nature. Therefore, all formations in nature are directed by the factor called ENERGY. Energy and spirit are equivalent meaningful concepts and are explained in the chapter "Spirituality – quantity connection".

Since the concept of God is a term that creates and directs everything in nature, today's term QUANTUM is synonymous with the term GOD of our ancestors.

All beings perceive their environment and form bodies that are compatible with environmental factors. The genome of every living thing is adapted to the conditions of the world by making changes at the quantum level. In our world, land and sea are constantly shifting. Our world is in constant motion and takes on different shapes over time. This situation is presented as an animation in the Fig. As can be seen in the animation, 250 million years ago, all the land masses in the world were in a unity called PANGEA. Then this great continent begins to disintegrate into present-day continents such as North America, South America, Antarctica, Australia, Europe, Asia, Africa, etc (Fig 35).

Figure 35: Geographical changes in the World

This fragmentation creates very different geographical conditions. The genomes of living things undergo changes according to these changing natural conditions. As an example, let's look at the group of living beings called MAMMALIA, of which we humans are also members. In this group, known as mammals, most mammals develop their young in the womb and then raise them by feeding them with their breasts after birth. But a group called marsupialia develops its offspring a little in the womb, but then carries it into a "bag" formed in its body and continues its breastfeeding in that bag. Animals such as kangaroos and koalas living in Australia are examples of this.

As can be seen in the animation on the right, Australia separated from the other continents about 150 million years ago and became an independent continent in the ocean. Mammals on the continent isolated from these other continents also form special mammals that are unique to it. Therefore, after humans arrived in Australia 50,000 years ago, mammals such as wolves and sheep belonging to our world migrated to Australia and began to live together with the native animals of that country.

Why did I have to provide such information?

Nature entities create the rules and conditions of life through their mutual interactions among themselves, and the subatomic elements in their genomes continue their lives by taking their energy from the quanta, the constituent of the natural system, and making corrections and changes in their genomes according to the information they have created through their own experiences. There is no external creator who influences and directs them. Their scriptures are the INFORMATION recorded in the sequences of chemical elements in the chromosome strands. Therefore, Time-Knowledge-Quanta are intertwined factors, and the concept that our ancestors conceived as GOD must definitely be QUANTUM.

The most wrong thing in our traditions is that they misunderstand time. Time is considered to be a process that operates according to the ticks given by an eternal being, and the formations in nature are considered to be the formations that take place according to these ticks. All physicists, including Einstein, thought so. However, the formation of forces that affect and direct substances is caused by chemical atom changes in the composition of substances and the energy transfers occurring by these changes. In nature, every being perceives what to do and when and acts accordingly. It adjusts when a sheep mates and gives birth by sensing environmental conditions (so that it calves when grass is most abundant). When a plant will bloom and spread its seeds, it makes it by taking into account the climatic conditions. In the structure of each entity, information on how it should behave, what and when it should do, etc., is recorded.

In other words, the concept of time has been the most misunderstood concept so far. Time is a concept in the sense of the order of occurrences and developments in nature. Our ancestors believed that the universe was created by a Supernatural Force, that is, by a power-force system that is external to beings. Such a belief requires that time be an eternity indexed to the lifetime of this Power system, because if it is finite, the creator is dead. Then there would be no such thing as nature. This wrong view of nature has been the most fundamental mistake that has misled humanity.

Physicists are at the forefront of this mistake. Physicists always think of time in relation to the process by which an object moves. The term (t = time) used is always a change-transformation process measured with an instrument we call "clock", such as hours or seconds. However, change-transformations do not develop according to the ticking of a clock, but depending on a guidance factor called "INFORMATION". However, there is no such factor as "KNOWLEDGE" in the formulations of physicists (except for the Information & Self-Organization). For this reason, most physical designs do not correspond to the natural system.

One should not believe everything physicists say, who are ignorant of the information-factor that acts as traffic signs that direct the flow of energy. Especially imagine how sound the logic of physicists is who create theoretical formulas based on the assumption that the phenomenon of TIME is an infinity indexed to the life of an eternal being. Because of this fundamental error, the relations between the branches of science, which are closely related to each other, such as classical physics, quantum-physics, chemistry, geology, biology, neurophysiology, etc., are not known at all. However, our cells continue their lives by using all of these basic branches of science and form a living species that prioritizes information like us humans. We, on the other hand, think of this realm of cells as uninformed and unconscious creatures.

Changing the chemical composition and structural texture occurs in the form of perceiving the changes-transformations around the entity and making changes in its own structure (composition) in accordance with it, which is the result of the formation of a dynamic system, which is summarized as "information & re-self-organization". That is, "information" is reflected in the chemical structure and physical tissue. The information reflected in the structure of the entities directs the flow of energy by creating polarization or anisotropic (such as hot-cold, plus-minus, male-female, etc.) properties. With the change of the structure, the image of the entity changes, and the change of the image occurs as time. Therefore, the factors of information + chemical-composition + physical-tissue + energy + time are intertwined with each other.

The importance of living things to creating KNOWLEDGE makes it a very important stage about 50 million years ago, and the formation of living things called

PRIMATA, which prioritizes KNOWLEDGE CREATION, begins. A cellular design called HUMAN, which prioritizes giving importance to living information, begins to form about 5 million years ago and develops to a level that will change the world (Fig 36).

Figure 36: The human genome, which has a history of about 2.5 million years, represents a living thing that knows best the importance of information generation and therefore attaches the most importance to information creation. (From BLOOM & LAZERSON 1988)

In animal brains such as mice and cats, the section divided into (brown) sense and (blue) movement organs covers a very large part of the brain. The region of "interpretability" shown in white is partially developed in the monkey and abnormally enlarged in the human. That's why we can't move as fast as animals, we can't see, hear, smell, etc. But thanks to the abnormally developed "interpretation" ability, we can produce enormous scenarios.

Due to the information explained above, it is seen that the clergy and state administrators in our country are in betrayal of society and humanity. For this reason, it is necessary to raise awareness of our people.

Is eternity possible?

There is nothing in nature that does not change and transform, and everything has to undergo a cycle of birth and death over time. People's longing for an eternal life stems from a complete misinterpretation of the natural system. What is this fundamental mistake?

The only reason why human beings have formed a concept called eternity is that they do not know the development basing on the most basic fundamental units in nature and that they assume this development by supernatural-power-system outside of beings. Scientists believe that formations in nature are formed by random collisions, not by the conscious behaviour of beings, and that a supernatural power system selects the best ones. This is the reason why the concept of time is perceived as an eternity without beginning and end. When the phenomenon of time is indexed to the lifetime of this supernatural power system, it is accepted that this supernatural force must be eternal, otherwise nothing can come into being and develop in nature (Fig 37).

Figure 37: LIFE, which started in the seas 3.8 billion years ago, has been in an evolution based on KNOWLEDGE that has spread to the land 420 million years ago and continues to the present day.

Why can't it thrive? Because it was assumed that the creation was directed from an external being outside of all things. If this being dies, who will direct the developments?

This is why the concept of eternity was created. However, there is nothing eternal in nature, because formations are directed from lower-level elements, not from a higher-level system. Everything gets its energy from the elements inside of them. Bodies need to be constantly renewed, as the most basic subatomic elements (the quantum system) always prefer the most efficient structures created according to the best information and migrate by "tunneling" to them. For this reason, life is based on a birth-death cycles. The cells in our bodies are always renewed every few months and new ones are formed in their place. This renewal always occurs in a shorter time in molecules and in an even shorter time in atoms. Therefore, there is no such thing as eternity in the natural system.

Our bodies are formed and directed by our cells. We depend on our cells, they regulate our lives. All we learn and think is transferred to our cells and processed by them. All the information we create by interacting with our environment is transferred to our cells, and they direct our lives by blending the hereditary information inherited from their ancestors with the data we transfer to them. When bodies age and decompose into cells-atoms, the information stored in them is blended with the natural system, calibrated with them, and mutual information transfers take place between them. Based on this new blending of information, beings interact with each other again and begin to rebuild the natural system. And so the cycle continues. Nature and the world evolve as described in the first chapters, ensuring the continuity of life. In other words, there is no such thing as death in nature, there is a recycling.

We clearly see this "recycling" event in the functioning of our digestive system. Namely: All living things break down the food they eat in the digestive system and convert them into basic molecules called amino acids. Amino acids are the basic molecules at the very beginning of the life system. In other words, recycling has gone back to basic elements 3-4 billion years ago. Every living thing begins to rearrange these basic amino acid molecules according to their own genetic information records; Some creatures make bodies that will live by clinging to hard rocks such as mussels, some make durable threads like a spider, and some make

organs such as hair and wings. And all these formations are a recycling and rearranging event.

In reality, this is the case and life continues in constant change and transformation. When bodies age and have difficulty adapting to changing natural conditions, recycling is initiated, and the body decomposes back into its cells and molecules. Calibration takes place with the natural system and the world is recreated every day.

Death and the fear of death is a faulty program placed in our subconscious because of the transfer of a completely wrong view of life to traditions.

Everything happens in the form of the fusion of subatomic elements, which are very short-lived and very mobile, into longer-lived and less mobile super-systems (atoms, molecules, cells, bodies). Nothing created can be eternal, it decomposes into its sub-components after a certain life-cycle, and nature develops in a continuous change-transformation system in this way.

Since nature is in a constant state of change and transformation, no higher-level being can have an eternal life. If the entities formed become eternal, the quantum elements are imprisoned within these eternal beings, and the creation of new higher-level beings is prevented, because they are all imprisoned. Therefore, all beings have a cycle of birth and death.

There is nothing in nature that does not undergo change, because everything begins with the most basic element of life called quanta. Since quanta are the most basic element of life, everything in nature takes place in the form of their reproduction. This is called quantization. Atoms are products of this quantization. Molecules are formed by the combination of atoms, cells are formed by the combination of molecules, and the whole world of living things, including humans, is formed by the combination of cells. Thus, an evolution in the style of lower-level – higher-level has emerged. The power of making and creating always belongs to its lower-level elements, that is, the cell forms the body, the body cannot form cells. We can't make a cell, but cells form thousands of different bodies according to their genetic information.

Why do we have to die?

1. It is not clear in advance where the universal system will go, it is proceeding according to the probability calculations of the quantum system.
2. As quanta merge into higher-level systems such as atoms, molecules, and cells, they undergo symmetry breaking according to the goals shown to them by the higher-level system they enter, and they obey the rules in that higher-level system. If we explain this in the example of the water molecule: H is flammable, O is combustible; but in water with H₂O composition, these properties are completely lost. In other words, H and O underwent symmetry breaking to form the water molecule.
7. If the quanta that make up the universal system are free, they can invest in the most appropriate systems according to probability calculations. The quanta inside a person are not free, their symmetry is broken to fit the goals indicated by that person. Therefore, in order to continue to evolve on a universal scale, human beings must die and decompose into atoms so that quanta can interact with the universal system and continue universal evolution based on knowledge.

1. CHAPTER: "Kervran-Effect" = Mechanism of transformation between atoms.

Energy is required for all events and formations in nature; Energy, on the other hand, is in the quantum system, that is, in the world of subatomic elements. The realm of quanta is constantly interacting with its environment, and they themselves change in accordance with the changes and transformations in the environment. The transfer of the effects of these changeovers in quanta to molecules or higher-system entities must take place by chemical elements called atoms. Therefore, atoms cannot be constant, they must be in a state of changeovers. In other words, if the atoms do not change and transform, the "bridge" between the world of subatomic elements (the quantum-realm) and the upper-level systems such as molecules-cells-bodies is closed.

Figure 38: The chemical elements must undergo changeovers too.

Because:

There is nothing in nature that does not change;

Our bodies, cells, and molecules receive the necessary guidance (information, energy signals, etc.) from their atoms for their changeovers; the signals emitted by atoms into the aether-medium must have changed so that molecules, cells, etc., can change and transform to match these changes.

The directions necessary for the change-transformations of atoms arise from subatomic elements; Since subatomic elements provide interaction between beings on a universal scale, they perceive the energy-level relations between all beings in nature and decide in their own situations in the most appropriate way, and in this way they form the basis of development in nature basing on knowledge and consciousness.

Therefore:

While there is a change-transformation in the most basic subatomic elements;

While there is a change-transformation in both upper-level systems (cells, bodies, etc.);

Is it possible that there is no change-transformation in atoms, which are their intermediate system?

Kervran expresses this issue as follows: (1972, p. 120)

"A dogma that our world will forever remain unchanged as it was originally created is the legacy of the Bible. We are informed that so much chromium, so much iron, etc., were created in creation. Since no other creator came later, "nothing else was created", everything remained as it was. Therefore, "nothing is lost". Such a belief has been accepted by everyone since the time of Moses. We can only smile at the "reasoning" of the so-called "scientists" in this way today. Because, since the beginning of the twentieth century, radioactive natural transmutation has been known. And in 1919, the first artificial transformation was carried out. But haven't there been other transformations in nature, at various times, unknown to classical nuclear physics? We have experimentally shown that all living things carry out elemental transformations, and geology has shown that there are many other types of transformations. This means that there is no question of the eternity of atoms. There are no chemical reactions in which one atom in one molecule does not transform into another atom in another molecule, but substances (atoms) are formed and disappeared in the same way that they transform into each other."

It is exemplary to show how traditional dogmatic views affect even scientists, who are supposed to act objectively and without prejudice. As the famous astrophysicist Carl Sagan said of another scientist, Kervran: "A reaction like the one you predict is chemically impossible. You need to read basic textbooks on nuclear physics."

Dogmatic views can make people so blind and deaf and irrational.

Information is created and recorded in chemical components such as atoms and molecules. Therefore, atoms and molecules must have a very variable property. However, physicist-chemists say that atoms are fixed, unchanging elements.

According to this dogmatic view, which is still prevalent in the scientific world, the formation of chemical elements in nature occurs only under the effects of enormous pressure-and-temperature within stars. The mass resulting from the transformation results also releases enormous energy according to the formula $E=mc^2$. Therefore, element-transformations are not possible under biological or normal laboratory conditions.

Kervran is a professor of physics and is aware of this dogmatic view that prevails in the scientific world. Therefore, he proposes a new idea that there must be another interaction system, which he calls "low-energy-nucleus-reactions = low-energy-nuclear-reaction = LENR".

The reasons for putting forward such a radical view will be briefly summarized below.

Corentin Louis Kervran, a professor of physics, recounts a childhood memory:

1)- "My family had chickens in a coop with a free exit to a yard. We used to live in central Britain where my father was a civil servant. There was no limestone in the area and only schists and granites. The chickens were never given limestone, but the chickens produced eggs with chalky shells every day. However, I was intrigued by an observation I made. As the laying hens roamed the garden, they were constantly swallowing mica flakes on the surface. Mica is a silica compound with Potassium. I had noticed that mica was obviously picked by chickens, especially after a rain, because after the rain they glowed in the sun like a mirror. The hundreds of mica-scales that appeared in every square meter were like miniature mirrors washed away by light rain, and it was easy to follow how the chickens swallowed them. After a chicken was slaughtered, my mother would open the chicken's gizzard bag and see small stones and grains of sand inside, but I could never see mica. Where had mica gone?

Figure 39: Chickens make eggshells by obtaining Ca from mica in environments where there is no lime.

When C. L. Kervran, who grew up with such a childhood memory, became a professor of physics, he focused on how chickens produced the element Ca (calcium) from the element K (potassium) found in mica grains and conducted various experiments.

Leaves chickens to live on floors where there is no lime. After a few days, he notices that the egg-shells of the chickens have lost their firmness and become softer. Then he feeds the chickens mica flakes and determines that the eggshells have regained their normal hardness.

To find out if chickens have the knowledge to recognize mica, they take newborn chicks and raise them in environments where there is no mica at all. When they begin to lay eggs, soft-shelled eggs are again formed. Thereupon, he sprinkles mica flakes around these chickens, who have never seen mica before, and looks at their behaviour: Chickens that have never seen mica flakes before attack mica and swallow them with great appetite. "The next day, the eggs had normal shells," he notes.

There is no Ca (calcium) in the mineral mica that chickens ingest; but there is K (potassium). By adding a proton to the K element, the Ca element is formed. This process takes place in the chicken body, and the cells of the chicken make the element Ca necessary for the egg-shell by adding a proton to K.

2)- Kervran analyzes the oat seeds in advance and determines the K, Ca, ratios.

Then he germinates and grows those seeds in pure water and when he determines the amount of elements in the grown plant again, he sees that there is a decrease in the amount of (K = potassium) and an increase in the amount of (Ca = calcium). Based on the fact that the amount of decrease in potassium is equal to the amount of increase in calcium, he states that a transmutation (element conversion) in the form of ($39\text{K} + 1\text{H} \rightarrow 40\text{Ca}$) must have taken place, Kervran 1973.

3)- Transmutations during the drying of fruits

After it was seen that chemical elements were transformed into each other in the growth and development of plants, it was also determined that transmutations occurred in the opposite case, that is, during the drying of fruits.

The research was carried out in environments that were completely isolated, that is, where no substance was entered, only the water content was extracted.

In the study, 100 gr. fresh fruit was used. Abnormal increases in the amount of some elements were detected in the chemical element content of fresh fruits and dried fruits. In the analysis of fresh fruits and their dried forms large increases in the amounts of Na, Mg, P, K, Ca, Mn, Fe, Cu, Zn elements were encountered.

Since drying is carried out in a closed system, since there is no entry of elements from the environment, the increases must have occurred as a result of the transformations of other atoms such as carbon, oxygen and silica. ($2\ ^{16}\text{C} + 2\ ^{12}\text{O} \rightarrow\ ^{56}\text{Fe}$ (Kervran 1973))

Feige	Frisch	Trocken
Wasser (g/100g)	81,80	30,70
Natrium (mg/100g)	3,00	86,30
Magnesium (mg/100g)	15,00	52,50
Phosphor (mg/100g)	15,00	87,00
Kalium (mg/100g)	200,00	900,00
Calcium (mg/100g)	38,00	167,00
Mangan (mg/100g)	0,10	0,395
Eisen (mg/100g)	0,30	2,41
Kupfer (mg/100g)	0,06	0,265
Zink (mg/100g)	0,30	0,514
Selen (µg/100g)	< 2,20	Spuren
Jod (µg/100g)	1,50	2,55

Figure 40: The chemical elements ratio of a fresh fruit is different from its dried form.

4)- Most creatures belonging to the arthropod group (crabs, crayfish, ostracods, etc.) have to change their shells as they grow.

In marine research laboratories, crayfish have been found to still form their shells perfectly when grown in an environment chemically free of the element Ca. Since there is no element Ca (calcium) used in the production of their shell in the aquatic environment they live in, the animal must have produced the necessary element Ca from other elements.

5)- It has been clearly proven by experiments in the following years that cells and micro-organisms convert chemical elements into each other.

Namely: Vysotskii has been working on biological element-transformations since the 1990s. Vysotskii and Kornilova, who used very new analysis methods such as Mossbauer Spectroscopy, experimented with Bacillus subtilis, Escherichia coli and yeast fungus in heavy-water (D2O). They observed that when micro-organisms added MnSO4 to their living environment, 57 atomic-weight Fe (iron) was formed in the spectrometer. Therefore, they clearly observed that the reaction (55 weights Mn + 2 weighted Deuterium = 57 weighted Fe) took place. They reveal that the symbiotic (partnership) relationships of bacteria, which they call "microbial catalyst converters", play an important role in these element conversion processes, Vysotski and Kornilova (2010).

6)- Converting the 3-phosphate ATP molecule into the 2-phosphate ADP molecule in order for our cells to do the job.

Figure 41: The cells in our bodies are able to convert the elements sodium and potassium to each other for their function.

Scientists still hold the "law of fixed proportions" proposed by Proust in 1799 that the proportions of chemical elements in nature relative to each other are constant. In other words, the view that chemical elements cannot transform into each other in the species shown above is still dominant among today's scientists.

In order for a cell to perform its functions, the ratios of potassium (K) and sodium (Na) in the cell must be changed thousands of times per second. Until now, it was thought that this process was carried out with the mechanism shown in (A), and in recent years, it has been understood that this is possible with the (B) shape.

The ability of our cells to do their work is possible with a phosphate energy released as a result of converting the 3-phosphate ATP molecule into a 2-phosphate ADP molecule. This is possible by pumping sodium ions inside the cell out of the cell and pumping potassium ions from outside the cell into the cell in each process.

These processes require enormous ion-flows, both inside and outside the cell, such as abruptly increasing and decreasing the density of Na and K ions by a factor of 10-15. Considering that up to 100,000 processes take place in the cell per second, it becomes clear how often there must be an ion-pumping traffic in the cell membranes. It is highly unlikely that pumping operations based on such ion-densities will be possible.

This phenomenon is reinforced by Pappas' 1998 publication. In his publication "Electrically Induced Nuclear Fusion in the Cell", Pappas proves that the changes in the Na-K ratio within the cells do not occur in the form of "sodium-potassium pumping" from outside the cell into the cell, as has been accepted so far, but by an intracellular element transformation in the form of $\text{Na } 23 + \text{O } 16 + \text{Electrical Energy} + \text{ATP Energy} = \text{K}^{39}$. In other words, potassium can be obtained by fusing sodium and oxygen in the cell.

Scientists, under the influence of a dogmatic view, have been so conditioned that they have been able to accept as a solution the irrationality of the human mind, such as the fact that millions of sodium and potassium ions are taken in and expelled at once, as if the membranes of the cells in our bodies were "passing-by-way"!

An even worse absurdity is that if Na and K ions come into contact with water, there will be a massive explosion and the cells will be shattered, because there is water in both the intracellular and extracellular environment.

There have been many more recent studies proving that cells convert chemical elements into each other, (Ravikumar & Achutha 2012, Kumar 2017), etc.

The transfer of a proton and its neutron from one nucleus to another does not appear to be a radioactive process; it can take place in bubbles in the lungs with the help of a previously unknown enzyme, or perhaps in the membranes of red blood cells as they pass through the bubbles (Kervran 1980, p. 17).

7)- Transmutations of chemical elements in our world

When we look at the distribution of chemical element ratios in our solar system, it is noticed that heavy elements are found only on stony planets such as our earth, and not on other planets and in the Solar system.

98% of galaxies and stars are made up of hydrogen and helium (74% H, 24% He); The proportion of all other elements is about 2%.

Nearly 98% of the compositions of outer planets such as Jupiter, Saturn, Neptune and Uranus, which are located between the vacuum of space and the Sun, also consist of H and He. That is why they are called "Gaseous planets".

On planets close to the Sun, such as our Earth, which are called "stony planets", the situation is completely reversed: Elements such as iron, oxygen, magnesium, silicon, sulfur, nickel, calcium, aluminum are present at a rate exceeding 99%, hydrogen and helium are immeasurably less.

The fact that there is such an inversely proportional chemical composition between the planets and the stars must be the result of nuclear reactions carried out by the Kervran-effect, especially by organisms, and therefore the types and ratios of chemical elements are changed, and a state adaptable to the changing conditions of nature is formed.

This shows that many chemical elements are produced on stony planets such as our earth.

In the light of these basic observations and experiments, he begins to doubt the correctness of the traditionally taught knowledge of physics and chemistry.

Because traditional physics-chemistry knowledge said that all chemical elements in nature were formed at the beginning of the formation of the natural system and could no longer be destroyed or changed after that. That is, potassium or calcium (or all

other chemical elements) were formed as potassium and calcium and could never be converted into another element.

One of the most important of these fixed-structural assumptions in nature is Lavoisier's law of conservation of mass, which states in 1789 that mass does not change during chemical reactions. The other is the law of constant proportions, which was defined by Joseph Proust in 1799 as "there is an unchanging ratio between the masses of the elements that make up a compound". These two laws of chemistry have been in place in the scientific world ever since.

The neutron is made up of 2 down (d) and 1 up (u) quarks, while the proton is made up of 2 (u) and 1 (d) quarks.

A (d) quark that makes up the neutron can be transformed into a (u) quark with the help of a negatively-charged W⁻-boson virtual element, while an electron and electron-anti-neutrino are emitted into the environment. As a result, the neutron is transformed into a proton. This is how the cobalt (Co) element turns into the nickel (Ni) element.

$${}_{27}^{60}\text{Co} \rightarrow {}_{28}^{60}\text{Ni} + e^{-} + \bar{\nu}_e$$

The one (u) quark that makes up the proton can be converted into a (d) quark with the help of a positively charged W⁺-boson virtual element, while a positron and electron-neutrino are emitted into the environment. As a result, the proton is transformed into a neutron. The conversion of magnesium (Mg) to sodium (Na) occurs in this way, that is, by the release of a positron.

Figure 42: The figure shows how atoms can transform into each other with the LENR system.

Atoms are made up of protons and neutrons; Different atoms, on the other hand, are determined by the number of protons. An atom with 1 proton is hydrogen; An atom with 6 protons is carbon, etc.

The neutron is made up of 2 down (d) and 1 up (u) quarks, while the proton is made up of 2 (u) and 1 (d) quarks.

A (d) quark that makes up the neutron can be transformed into a (u) quark with the help of a negatively-charged W⁻-boson virtual element, while an electron and electron-anti-neutrino are emitted into the environment. As a result, the neutron is

transformed into a proton. This is how the cobalt (Co) element turns into the nickel (Ni) element.

The one (u) quark that makes up the proton can be converted into a (d) quark with the help of a positively charged W^+ -boson virtual element, while a positron and electron-neutrino are emitted into the environment. As a result, the proton is transformed into a neutron. The conversion of magnesium (Mg) to sodium (Na) occurs in this way, that is, by the release of a positron.

As can be seen, there are not only real elements such as protons, neutrons, and electrons in nature, but also many virtual particles, such as W^+ , W^- , and Z bosons. Virtual elements participate in a reaction for a very, very small fraction of a second, and then disappear again. W^+ is a collection of W-elements, one of which is "matter" and the other is anti-matter. In the same way, the electron is matter and the positron is anti-matter. (Neutrino matter, anti-neutrino anti-matter.) In other words, the quantum system that forms nature and our world by calculating information and probability is in a mixture and interaction of matter and anti-matter.

Now let's consider the chicken's need for Ca for eggshells. There is no limestone everywhere in the world, and there are no minerals with Ca. But the chicken is obliged to live there. Then the cells inside the chicken are looking for how to provide Ca. The transformation of molecules into each other occurs through the creation of energy gradients. Very small ambient energy gradients are created by single-celled organisms (bacteria, fungi). The same method applies to the transformation of elements into each other, and they are also carried out by single-celled organisms such as bacteria and fungi. Living things cooperate with other small micro-organisms. By creating various small environments by mutual interactions, micro-environments are created in which molecules are allowed to decompose into atoms; Then, by creating smaller micro-environments in which the atoms are converted to each other, the element required by the entity is obtained (see Fig. Komaki H. 1993, Vysotski & Kornilova 2010).

"Life is nothing but chemistry" = Life is just chemistry.

All beings have to get their energy from the quantum system. The quantum system is nature's energy bank, it gives all other beings their energy. Like every banker, quantum bankers look at the intentions and goals of the buyers and invest accordingly so that their energy investment is not wasted.

All super-systems (atoms, molecules, cells, animals, plants, etc.) that develop with the combination of quantum elements have to collect and act according to the intervals and factors at which the fluctuation movements of the sub-system elements to which they are connected. Therefore, life is the act of collecting information about the fluctuations in the energy source and transferring this information to the next generation.

Our thoughts and behaviors are completely formed as a result of chemical changes in the cells in our body. When we talk about chemical transformations, we should not only understand the change and transformation of molecules. Atoms also change and transform. In other words, according to the needs of the cells, potassium can be converted into calcium and calcium can be converted into potassium. This information is known as the Kervran effect, but it is still ignored due to the conditioning of scientists. However, it has been quietly accepted in recent years as LENR = Low Energy Nuclear Reaction. Chemical elements can be converted to each other via LENR. As stated by Kervran (1982), these transformations are triggered by quanta elements called neutrinos. Neutrinos are miraculous quanta capable of transmitting energy on a universal scale. That is, they can arise in a reaction within a substance, they penetrate every being around them, and they can interact with the nucleus of an atom in any entity and cause that atom to change. For this reason, all living and non-living beings in nature are in relationship and dependence with each other and on a universal scale.

It is thought that atoms cannot transform into each other. All we think and do is recorded by making changes and transformations in the cells. And in nature, information increases exponentially. The information of the cells is recorded by making changes in atoms and molecules. If atoms do not change and transform, how

will that fixed atomic realm store and record such exponentially increasing information?

Kervran's view that chemical elements can transform into each other under natural conditions, that is, transmutation will occur in nature, is called Kervran-effect.

Until the 1980s, the prevailing view was that different atomic formations only took place under very high conditions of pressure and temperature within stars. However, since 1963, the French physicist Kervran has claimed that chemical elements can be transformed into each other by the neutrino-induced Low Energy Nuclear Reaction (LENR) system under natural conditions, based on natural observations, and Kervran's view was confirmed by scientific research 30-40 years after his death (1983).

The importance of neutrinos is at this point. Neutrinos can reach a very high level of energy potential during their interactions with the entities they pass through, and when they encounter an atomic nucleus in a suitable environment, they break it apart, giving rise to the formation of very energetic new elements consisting of quarks that behave under the influence of a strong-interaction force.

Figure 43: A very small subatomic element, such as a neutrino, can lead to very large formations.

This was realized in 1974 when it led to the discovery of a new and very energetic subatomic element at the Brookhaven National Laboratory. The figure shows a snapshot of the current observation room.

Only neutrinos can enter the observation chamber from below, because the chamber is insulated to completely prevent the entry of other elements. One of them collides with a proton at point (A). At the end of the collision, 6 elements are revealed: 1 negative muon, 3 positive pion, and 1 negative pion; and a neutral $\Lambda(0)$.

At point (B), the positive pion emits an electron by interacting with its surroundings; At point (C), the negative muon interacts with its surroundings and emits a more energetic electron.

$\Lambda(0)$ interacts with its surroundings in D and transforms into a negative pion and a proton. So, like all other subatomic elements, it is very short-lived. ($\Lambda(0)$, described as Charmed-Sigma, is made up of three quarks, but carries a heavier (energetic) quark known as a "Charme" as the third quark, with the exception of normal up and/or down quarks such as protons or neutrons.)

This event took place in an observation chamber, and one of the neutrinos, which does not normally interact with the materials they pass through, was so affected by the environments it passed through along its path that when it reached point (A) of this observation room, it reached an energy level of 13 billion electron-volts, causing the proton it encountered at that point to break apart, resulting in the formation of a lot of subatomic particles described above.

This phenomenon can also happen in a person's body. How would that person perceive this? Think about this issue very well.

This is how we understand that the phenomenon of information is really reflected down to the lowest realm of subatomic elements, stored and processed by them. When we see something new, a new connection is created between the cells in our brain and a new protein is created that symbolizes that object. In order for this new protein to form, there must be changes in the previous components. Since each compound evolves depending on elements at a lower level, these change-transformations are reflected back to the most basic subatomic elements. In this way, the changes and transformations in the environment are transferred to our cells, molecules, atoms and quanta as "information". This feedback system is thus reflected back into the world of subatomic elements, and nature is reconfigured according to changing information every day.

A subatomic element that wants to reach a more ergonomic place receives enough energy to overcome the obstacle from a system called virtual elements. In other words, in the quantum system, there is a system that functions as a reserve energy store. Since high-energy quarks are formed during the disintegration of nuclear elements such as protons and neutrons, this reserve energy store is expected to originate from the strong-force = strong interaction stored in atomic nuclei.

Very high-energy quarks are formed when normal matter is hit by radiation and other energy elements. In other words, elements such as protons and neutrons in the atoms that make up substances in nature are not constant-invariant. On the contrary, they change and transform with the radiations in nature. These changes and transformations are most common in lightning-stormy weather and in beings exposed to radiation such as gamma rays, etc. But such interactions also occur in the cells inside our body.

In other words, the natural system has been created using the most ergonomic elements. But these most ergonomic components are under the control of an energy balancing system on a universal scale. On a universal scale, the agents of this energy balancing system are a neutral lepton element called a neutrino.

In other words, atoms were born 10-13 billion years ago. And since then, life has begun on Earth, because atoms, like the quantum system, are alive.

2. CHAPTER: Clergy and scientists commit crimes against humanity.

There is a life system based on the cycle of birth and death, and a natural system that is in constant change and transformation. It is the task of scientists to define this system, to explain how it works, and to help regulate the functioning and organization of the social system according to the principles of this natural system. As long as scientists who identify themselves as naturalists, physicists, chemists, biologists, geologists, paleontologists, physicians, etc., do not fulfill this task, no one will be able to prevent the religious merchants who peddled the knowledge of the natural system builder of 3-4 thousand years ago from carrying out these works, and all the blame for this will be on the scientists who call themselves naturalists.

In order to show why scientists and clergymen are guilty, it is necessary to give the following information.

The Story of Whales and Dolphins

First, let's give a brief information about the development of mammals. Mammals have existed for about 200 million years, but since dinosaurs were the dominant group of living things in the world between 200 million and 65 million years, mammals lived and could not develop only by hiding in their shadows, that is, in underground environments. A large meteorite that hit the earth 65 million years ago caused a tremendous catastrophe called the "Cretaceous-Tertiary extinction", as a result of which three-quarters of the living things on Earth disappeared. Among the extinct creatures are DINOSAURS.

The ecological environments emptied by dinosaurs begin to be populated by mammals, and the ancestors of creatures such as horses, pigs, and deer emerge. While most of these new mammals live in full terrestrial environments, some of them have changed to live in watery environments such as lakes and lagoons.

It is understood from paleontological research that these changes take several million years of time. Because fossil findings are seen for the first time in the rocks of mammals living in aqueous environments (Eocene) 50 million years ago.

In 50-million-year-old rocks belonging to the Eocene period, Pakicetus fossils from the Pakicetidae family and many other fossils of organisms living in aqueous environments have been identified. The bodies of these taxa, which lived in aquatic environments such as lakes and lagoons, gained a completely aerodynamic shape over time and took the shape of Basilosaurus 43 million years ago (Fig 44).

Figure 44: Eocene fossils 40-50 million years ago that lived in watery environments. Taken from Thewissen et al. 2009.

This means that it took at least 10 million years for land-dwelling mammals to undergo genetic changes to adapt to watery environments such as lakes and seas.

Nature consists of lower-level and higher-level structures, and thus an integrated system emerges that are dependent on each other. The relations between lower-level and higher-level systems were published by Feibleman (1954) under the title "Theory of Integrative Levels". The lowest level is the realm of quanta (subatomic elements). With their combinations, higher levels such as atoms, molecules, cells, bodies, and colonies are formed. Among the rules that apply at such levels, the most important are:

- i. Each level carries a new feature in addition to that of the level(s) below it.
- ii. The degree of complexity increases towards the higher-levels.
- iii. A disorder that occurs at any level affects all other related levels.
- iv. In every system, the higher-level is dependent on the lower-level; The upper-level indicates the direction (target) to the lower level.
- v. In the formation of any level, the power of creation is by lower-level; the higher-level is obliged to show targets.

These natural system principles reveal that the creative force that our ancestors called God or Allah must be absolutely present in the internal components of beings.

Targeting is done with efforts to do what you want to do with determination and willingness. According to these efforts, the elements within the asset make changes in such a way that they do that operation. In other words, they make the necessary changes for the body to do that job and make the body suitable for that process. It has been seen that living things adapt to the changes and transformations in nature in this way, when terrestrial animals such as whales and dolphins are transformed to live in the sea, and changes have been made in their booklets called genomes. Huelsmann et al. et al. (2019) found that 85 Genes were lost in the genomes of whales and dolphins during their transition from land to water. In other words, 85 genes such as the saliva need gene (SLC4A9), which is useful in land life, have been removed, and genetic

changes have been made to ensure that the lungs and blood circulation system are compatible with the increased water pressure during sea diving. These changes in genomes do not occur through the efforts of a single living being. It can form in groups of organisms (genome pools) that are in constant mutual interaction with each other in the form of a lake, an island, or otherwise.

The cells of animals, which are constantly trying to benefit from the nutrients in the sea by diving into the sea, have changed the genomes that determine the appearance of the body and how the body will be operated in line with the body's wishes, and made them compatible with nature. This research shows the best example of knowledge-based evolution.

In other words, the cells in the living body are constantly changing and updating the genome of the body. Since the behaviour of cells is determined and directed by the atoms and molecules within them, atoms and molecules must also be in a constant state of change and transformation. And so this is projected back into the QUANTUM realm, and they are constantly changing. The following paragraphs will explain the mechanism of this transformation, i.e., how the lower-level elements achieve a goal that is shown to them.

In other words, GOD, who is defined as the creator of nature and the world, has been completely misunderstood to us, because the ARCHIVE-PAGES data show that creativity is initiated by the most basic inner-impulse element = Wirkungs-QUANTUM that is found in the inner beings of beings. This element of inner impulse must be called constructor, because all matter begins to be formed by the quantization of this basic element. The reason why it is called a constructor, not a creator, is that when we say creator, an external being such as a sculptor can be thought.

Below, as a result of millions of years of effort on this subject, the story of how a group of creatures living in the terrestrial environment was made suitable for living in the marine environment will be given.

Notable changes in the anatomy of creatures such as whales and dolphins include streamlined bodies and body hair loss to reduce friction during swimming, much

thicker skin devoid of sweat and sebaceous glands and enhanced physical barrier properties, a thick layer of fat for insulation. In addition to these, the removal of genes that are useless for meaningful and purposeful use of energy has been taken into account in the transition to the marine environment, and many genes have been completely removed, deleted or disabled. Only one example of the 85 gene losses revealed in the research will be shown below, and it will be stated to what extent the adaptation of living things to natural environments depends on the initiative of the cells. That's because similar changes have been made in 84 other genes.

Removal of the SLC4A9 gene

The SLC4A9 gene, located on chromosome 5 (5q31.3), is involved in saliva production. Saliva provides softening of the solids taken into the mouth in land-dwelling mammals by wetting them. For those who live in the sea, this is unnecessary. For this reason, the codons encoding this gene in animals such as whales and dolphins that live in the sea have been completely deleted (Fig 45).

Figure 45: In the Figure, the genome information of mammals specific to terrestrial environments is shown in black fonts, and the genome data of mammals such as whales and dolphins are shown in red fonts.

As can be seen, 6 codons have been completely removed in whales and dolphins.

The removed codons are located at the same point on chromosome 5 in all 7 different taxa. The removal of the same number of such codons in all very different taxa

cannot be explained by a factor called mutation. Such a codon deletion can certainly happen when those creatures deliberately remove these codons. Therefore, evolutionists must now accept that cells behave consciously.

Since it is unnecessary to create saliva in the marine environment, whales and dolphins do not have any.

Animals created to live on land, such as whales and dolphins, have tried to feed on the marine environment for years by constantly diving into the sea. These efforts were targeted by the cells that make up their bodies, and these animals, which were created to live on land, were transformed into a body suitable for living in a marine environment like a fish. This event is of great importance for understanding the relations between lower-level and higher-level beings in nature. It is clearly seen in this event that cells are both the designers and repairers of the bodies of living things, and therefore there is not a sudden creativity in nature, but an evolution-progress-development in constant change-transformation.

A booklet of body-forming information called the genome is constantly being changed and transformed according to the results of the living thing's dealing with nature. A previously created gene information is completely deleted, a letter (nucleotide) is added in front of the information start codon and rendered ineffective, or the command is continued by changing the end-of-information codon. In other words, cells are constantly updating the process of making bodies with a lot of logical operations. As revealed at the end of the ARCHIVE-PAGES section presented above, nature was not created by an outsider all at once, but on the contrary, it is constantly being created by the QUANTUM system, which is the most fundamental component of beings.

Now, it is necessary to ask questions to all scientists, especially to the clergy and evolutionists:

The clergy must answer the following question:

Did the God of the Bibles create whales and dolphins to live on land, or did they create them to live in the sea? According to the view of creation, there can be no change-transformation between living things. So how did creatures created to live on

land turn into whales or dolphins? The holy books were created by the rulers of society to ensure that the people remained passive and acted according to their directions.

Now let's move on to the question that scientists need to answer.

Why can't we live a peaceful and happy life? Because the purpose of life is given to us incorrectly.

“We live in a dynamic nature in a continuous change and transformation. So is there a direction of these c change and transformation? Where are we heading? When you ask a question like ”What is the purpose of life?”:

The answer that a religiously minded person will give is, “The life of this world is temporary, the real life is in the other world. If you live according to the view of the Bible, you will go to Heaven in the hereafter. Otherwise, you will live in Hell under torture forever.”

Showing such a goal is aimed entirely at ensuring that a ruling group of lords frightens the people with punishments such as the torment of hell, to work in a way that serves them, and to accept that their children live in poverty.

The answer to be received from natural-science educated people, especially physicists, is as follows:

Second law of thermodynamics indicate that in nature, energy is required to perform a work-action (production, growth, repair, etc.). When energy is used for action, some of that energy is wasted as useless energy. For this reason, over time, the amount of useful energy in nature will decrease and the useless energy will increase. This means that considering that the amount of energy and mass in the universe is constant, there will be a trend towards disorder (entropy-increase) in nature over time. In other words, according to them, the end of the universe is going to chaos and disorder.

Such an answer by physicists is completely wrong: Let's ask the question again with an add-on: If the second thermodynamics law shows that everything in nature will disintegrate over time, then at the beginning of the historical development of the natural system, there must have been an enormous orderly system in the universe,

and that order has come to the present day by deteriorating, and after that, it will gradually deteriorate and lead to a chaotic end. Nature and the history of our world were shown in the ARCHIVE-PAGES. There it is seen that everything in nature is constantly developing towards more orderly and developed super-systems (i.e., order) based on knowledge and consciousness. So doesn't this view have to be wrong?

Yes, there is a mistake, and that is this: PHYSICISTS THINK IN A STATIC SYSTEM, they do not know that interactions between entities are carried out with INFORMATION

Now let's see the topic "what is a static system?".

3. CHAPTER: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN STATIC (Robotic) SYSTEM AND DYNAMIC (Active) SYSTEM

It is important to note a very important point about creativity: If you design the creator outside of beings, you need to think of that creator as a sculptor. Assets become passive, robot-like elements, and the information to create and design assets is entirely in the hands of the external creator. In such a case, there can be no knowledge-building competition between beings. The so-called evolution would have disappeared. Everything remains as it was originally created. In other words, there is a static situation. Such a system is therefore called a **STATIC** system. The static system is based on the view that everything in nature is created and directed by a system outside and above beings. In the static system, the entities are robots, someone at the top directs them. We think and act according to a static systematic view of life. In this view, all life in nature originates from an unknown mysterious factor called "soul", which has been placed into beings by an extraordinary power, and beings obey the laws of nature created by this supernatural power system like a robot.

However, the data of the Archive-pages show that there is definitely an evolution-development in nature and that the parameter called KNOWLEDGE increases exponentially. In other words, everything in nature is in a constant evolution-development, that is, there is a **DYNAMIC** system. We live in a dynamic systematic nature. In dynamic systematic nature, influencing-directing and-creating power is in

the lower-level system. The higher-level systems monitor the changes in nature and report them to their lower-level systems (cells, etc.), and the lower-level system adjusts its behaviour accordingly.

In nature, the dynamical system applies. IN THE DYNAMIC SYSTEM

1. Constitutive force, energy, etc., are in the quantum realm.
2. They are in constant interaction with the environment.
3. By creating knowledge, new higher-level systems are constantly being built;
4. The best of the new higher-level systems are selected and the bad ones are abandoned.
5. Since all beings are present in them,
6. they are omnipresent.
7. they are omnipotent.
8. It is a birth-death cycle, according to new formations of knowledge, nature is reconstituted and regulated every day.

Our customs and traditions are automatically recorded in our subconsciousness during childhood. If an elephant is accustomed to being chained by its feet when it is young, this behaviour is copied into the elephant's subconsciousness, and the elephant then continues to live in accordance with this copied conditioning. Humans copy the behaviours of the people around them until the age of 6-7, and when they grow up, they live in accordance with these conditioning, just like the elephant. Since the people in the environment are also programmed-conditioned according to the information copied from older generations, this cycle continues. People are compelled to behave under the influence of these copied behaviours, programmed according to them, conditioned according to them. Even if 3-4 different languages are spoken around him, he copies those languages in such a way that he speaks without an accent.

In the static systematic view of life, nature is inanimate, and the "soul" of human beings, which is a sign of life, was given to it by "God", who is supposed to be the owner of Nature and everything in the world. Other beings, like robots, obey the laws

of nature set by this divine being (or the natural-selector of evolutionists). (Evolutionists, too, regard human consciousness as a coincidental occurrence.)

The biggest mistake of scientists is in this false view of nature. Physicists still do not accept that the so-called INFORMATION factor started with the quantum alphabet and began with the quantum realm, and see the realm of quanta and subatomic elements as particles. When subatomic elements behave in a knowledgeable and conscious manner, they apply a double standard by saying that they can behave as particles if observed, and they behave as wave-functions if not observed.

We humans are a self-righteous being assuming that we're the only smart and knowledgeable beings. As physicists have demonstrated, all beings in nature are in constant interaction with their environment; In other words, they know each other's masses, their potentials, the distances between each other, etc., very precisely. To measure this, they use so-called oscillation-steps (wavelengths). This phenomenon, which physicists call "mutual interaction", is actually nothing more than the event of "mutual communication" between entities.

Physicists have never considered a factor called "information" in natural phenomena. E.g. it was thought that when an egg was broken and scattered, this egg could never be brought back, so when the order was broken, there would be no return. However, the creature that made that egg makes an egg again that is suitable for changing natural conditions.

The negative impact of the Difference between the Static System and the Dynamic System on our SOCIETY life

Until now, humanity has believed that everything in nature is created by a system of Super-Natural Power (SNP), which it defines as GOD or LORD (master). He assumed that all the power, energy, and information were in this SNP system. In this belief system, the beings themselves are considered ignorant, and the SNP system, which they assume is outside the entities, is considered alive and knowledgeable. This system of thought is called the STATIC thinking system, because the beings themselves are thought of as robots, and the factor that affects them is considered as a system of STATIC=unchanging power that is outside of them, above them, eternal, that is, never changing.

There is no development of the Static System view in a lower-level – high-level manner. However, the natural system is related to the lower level and the higher level, and everything is formed by the interaction of all elements. The Creator has created everything as He wishes, there is no interaction between beings, so it is completely contrary to the real system of formation in nature.

The answer to the question of whether the first chicken in the world hatched from an egg or an egg came out of a chicken is clear: An egg is a cell, and a chicken is a collection of cells. First the cell is formed, then the chicken, which is a collection of cells (Fig 46)!

Figure 46: Did the egg (cell) appear for the first time in the world, or the chicken? Which one constituted the other?

To sum up: The natural system is strictly lower-level- higher-level related, and everything is formed by the interaction of all elements. Elements are not a constant-invariant, dead thing, but on the contrary, they are very mobile and alive. It is an energy-field that is constantly changing and developing according to the changes in nature. This system, which is in constant change-transformation, is called DYNAMIC SYSTEM.

The traditional view assumes that everything is created by a Supernatural Power (SNP) system. In this belief system, the beings themselves are considered ignorant, and the SNP system, which they assume is outside of beings, is considered alive and knowledgeable. This system of thought is called the STATIC thinking system because the beings themselves are thought of as robots, and the factor that affects them is considered as a system of STATIC=unchanging power that is outside of them, above them, eternal, that is, never changing. There is not a lower-level – high-level manner development of the Static System, because they must be created all at the same time.

The organization of social life was carried out according to the static-system view, and the Authority-Dependent Organization (ADO) was established.

Archive pages and quantum-physics data of the Earth show that nature and the world are in a state of evolution. In other words, there is no external force that knows everything in advance and creates nature and the world according to that knowledge. If there were a power system that knew everything in advance, there would be no changes and transformations in the forms of beings over time, and every being would continue to live as it was first formed. The world would have been created at once and would not have changed after that.

Societies are governed and guided by a leader at the top (king, sultan, president, etc.) in accordance with the view that the system that directs nature is outside and above beings. Even in democracies, the people have given all authority to the president at the top. The level of prosperity of a society depends on the productive capacity of its individuals. In other words, the remedy lies in improving the knowledge and skill levels of individuals. However, in a system with a leader, it is not desirable for individuals to produce ideas, because what the leader says must be done. For this reason, the people are pacified in systems with leaders. It is impossible for the people, who are condemned to laziness of thinking and have no self-confidence, to gain an advantage over other societies by making new inventions and production potential. Because, by its very nature, the system of dependence on the top prevents individuals from thinking and being knowledgeable. Presidents who are in such a predicament, under the influence of their personal ambitions, engage in behaviours

that can be called "looting": Either they divide their own people and engage in activities aimed at the exploitation of one part of the other; or they covet the property of neighbouring societies. They get into fights or wars with neighbouring societies; Of course, those who will fight and die are again the unconscious masses of people. The winning side becomes more advantageous for a while with the spoils it obtains; On the losing side, there is a complete disaster. The leader of the losing side is removed from his post and replaced by someone else. This seesaw game is thus played. The history of humanity has continued with such games.

The standard of living of a society depends on the level of knowledge of its individuals, but leadership requires authoritarian behaviour and does not want individuals to be knowledgeable. For this reason, the problem of all laggard societies is to have been raised with wrong information.

Problems are solved by moving from a static system to a dynamic system, because the static system requires Authority-Dependent Organization (ADO)

(ADO) is the source of all social problems, namely:

1. Since individuals in ADO are raised only in responsibility and dependence on the rulers, people's feelings of dependence on each other have not developed, and their ability to get along and reconcile with each other has become blind. This means the destruction of the ability to agree and compromise. When one says banana, the other understands cucumbers, there can be no agreement and reconciliation.
2. Since some professions are order-giving and some are order-takers, discrimination arises in ADO, such as respectable and non-respectable professions. Therefore, the orientation of people to professions is not according to their abilities, but according to the value of respectability in society,
 - a. People always incline towards professions that are assumed to be RESPECTABLE; People who do not have the talent for that profession cannot show the necessary success in these professions and social development is hindered.

- b. When people's natural talents and occupations are incompatible, people feel unhappy; Unhappy people do more harm than good to their environment, etc.

If everything is determined by those at the top, the ability of those at the bottom diminishes (Fig 47).

Figure 47: The source of all social problems is the system of management from above.

3. Since the responsibility in the ADO is entirely on the shoulders of the leaders, the people are condemned to laziness of thinking. Raising lazy or hardworking people depends on the system. The people, who expect the solution of their problems from a saviour, do not try to generate ideas and solve their problems. Therefore, the capacity of the people to produce knowledge is automatically limited. Knowledge, on the other hand, is the main pillar of efficient production and development.
4. In the ADO, those at the top are both the rulers and the owners of the public property. When leaders own the property of all public goods, the people do not claim communal property. People who damage public property, because they are improperly trained, are not aware that they are cutting the branch on which they are riding. Community goods begin to be despised, and a tool that should last for 10 years is deteriorated in a year and social development is hindered.
5. Those at the top of the ADO see themselves as the owners of the state and think they have the authority to punish those who do not conform to their views. For this

reason, they engage in secret-insidious actions. As a result, "deep-state" mechanisms are created, and people are tried to be silenced by methods such as blackmail, threats, assassinations, etc. In obedience to the orders of those at the top, those who do not think like them are tortured.

6. When the ownership of the state is left to a person at the top, he may have to have his own son killed, as Suleiman the Magnificent did "for the benefit of the state" at the top. In democracies, many intellectuals such as Uğur Mumcu, Abdi İpekçi, etc., are killed in the name of "protecting the interests of the state" because they do not think like those at the top.
7. Since promotion in the ADO is achieved by proximity to those at the "top" rather than talent-capacity, people tend to establish a close relationship with rulers instead of learning something and engaging in a production and mutual exchange of services based on this knowledge. This leads to a decrease in production and the underdevelopment of society.
8. Since the solution of social problems in ADO does not depend on mutual interactions, but on the guidance of those at the top, among people, "what is it to you; what is it to me, is it the property of your father?" behaviours are common. This is evidence that the citizen does not see himself as the owner of the society. Every event in nature concerns all other beings.
9. In every human being, there is an urge to belong to a system, to come together in a group. When society is embraced by a bureaucratic group, the people, who feel excluded, form associations in various ways and form groupings to satisfy their sense of belonging. This is the weakest point of existing social systems and constitutes a disintegrating disease that gnaws society from within. This urge to belong is at the root of all forms of anarchy, mafia, gangs, ethnic or religious groupings.
10. Those with different views in the ADO are in a race to take over the administration (the state). Therefore, they place in the wheel of bureaucracy men who conform to their views. In this way, the wheel of bureaucracy is parcelled out by different opinions. In the 1970s, our security forces were divided into right-wing and left-

wing groups such as "Pol-Bir" and "Pol-Der". Since each of them is in an attitude to defend the interests of those who hold their own views and to undermine the others, the rights-law system is injured: Since everyone considers himself a patriot and engages in attitudes and behaviours that will destroy his opponents, a lot of gangs arise. Susurluk, Ergenekon-Balyoz trials, unsolved murders, inconclusive trials, corruption, gangs, etc. are inevitable.

11. When the state belong to a person at the top, all natural resources, public goods etc are owned by him. The X-state, like the Y-state, is divided into a lot of parts; Then these state-owners parcel the country to various lords. When nature and the world were parcelled out and owned in this way, the people could not protect nature. The seas have been polluted, the air has been polluted, the waters have been polluted, and even our drinking water has been brought from distant mountain peaks in plastic bottles.
12. Ownership continued in all factories and similar workplaces, and workers were forced to work with minimum gain. After the workers unite in organizations such as unions and make their voices heard, the struggles of workers and employers could continue. This leads to conflicts such as strikes and lockouts that paralyze society-life.
13. In the life of society with a static system, the target of people is "money". Is there any evil that cannot be done with money? NONE! Since the control of "money" in the static system is in the hands of the top-rich ones, is it possible to have peace in the world? Since it is possible to make people who are after money do all kinds of evil, there will be no peace in the world unless the static systematic views of life are destroyed.
14. In ADO, the property of the community is owned by those at the top. Since the people do not see themselves as partners in the social system, they tend to behave only in their own interests; Those who govern the state have to put a guard over everyone, and this is impossible; etc.

In summary: Whether the leader placed at the top is the best or the worst, the social problems listed above are inevitable. The ADO system is the main source of all our social problems.

If dependence on the top has such harmful effects on the social system, is there is a mutual interaction system between all beings in nature?

If you had to choose the teacher to raise your children, you would choose the best teacher.

If you were to choose the watchman to ensure your safety, the person to regulate your traffic, the person to do your electrical work, you would choose the most talented, the most knowledgeable.

While people were acquiring a profession, they took their place in society as people who had knowledge and skills by taking on jobs that they could do well, going through a good education.

Those who provided poor service were ostracized and removed.

If society operated on a credit system based on the exchange of services between business and professional members, how would personalities such as counterfeiters, tax-evaders, hired-killers, and saboteurs find jobs?

Wouldn't everything work smoothly in such a social system? Yes!!! Everything is getting better.

Conclusion: The reason why we are drowning in social problems in our country is that we do not know the mechanism of formation in nature and the world. Namely:

It is very important to know the main principle of the system of formation and development in nature. In nature, everything starts with the smallest elements. For example, water is in the composition of H_2O . In other words, when 2 hydrogen atoms combine with an oxygen atom, a water molecule is formed. Which of these came first? In other words, were there atoms or molecules in nature first? Scientific research shows that in nature, first atoms and then molecules are formed by the

combination of atoms. Therefore, large systems are formed by small systems. The power and right to make and manage is in small systems.

This has been stated by philosophers as follows: Feibleman 1954 under the heading "Theory of Integrative Levels" emphasizes that in every system, the upper level is dependent on the lower level; decision-making power is at a lower level; It is obliged to show high-level targets.

Since we do not know this basic principle of nature, we live a social life that is struggling with problems. If people were given this basic view of life, wouldn't all problems go away (Fig 48)?

Figure 48: Society consists of partnerships between business and professional members.

The society is a partnership of business and professional members. Each person takes on a job suitable for his ability, acquires knowledge on that subject and produces a service, this service goes to the community pool. Other people's services and products are also pooled in the community pool, from which people get whatever they need. So the simplest way to eliminate social problems is to give people the knowledge that they own society. Do people who grow up with the knowledge that society belongs to them behave in a way that harms society?

4. CHAPTER: The Place of Human in the Living World

Cells have witnessed many different changes and transformations in their billions of years of history, and it is not clear where the quantum universe will go, because everything is based on probability calculations. CELLS, which have been adapting to the changes in nature by creating information for 3.5 billion years, begin to form the human being who puts information creation at the forefront.

Now let's first see the graph of development of the living world in our world (Fig 49).

Figure 49: The development of living things in our world begins with bacteria, then with the development of the knowledge potential develops exponentially.

As can be seen in the Fig 40, life on Earth started with prokaryotic bacteria 3.5 billion years ago, eukaryotic single-celled organisms formed 2 billion years ago, and with the Cambrian Explosion 550 million years ago, the living groups that dominate

our world emerged one after another, and finally, 2.5 million years ago, living things called HUMAN were developed.

In our world, where life began 3.5 billion years ago, man began to take place only 2.5 million years ago. Moreover, the first human is more an animal than a human being, because he is a child-sized person who has none of the characteristics that we call HUMAN and only walks on two legs and uses the pieces he plucks from hard stones like a knife. People with advanced thoughts and behaviours like us emerged about 70 thousand years ago. Since all of these people originated in Africa, the ancestors of all of us are the people we call negroes.

The Fig below shows the most basic feature that distinguishes humans from other mammals (Fig 50).

Figure 50: The human brain is an attempt by cells to prioritize the formation of information.
(From BLOOM & LAZERSON 1988)

In animal brains such as mice and cats, the section allocated to sensory (brown) and movement (blue) organs covers a very large part of the brain. The region of

"association" shown in white is partially developed in the monkey and abnormally enlarged in the human. That's why we can't move as fast as animals, we can't see, hear, smell, etc. But thanks to the abnormally developed "interpretation" ability, we can produce enormous scenarios.

The first humans appeared in East Africa 2.5 million years ago.

Man originated in East-Africa and lives by hunting and gathering. A family in such a lifestyle requires an area with a diameter of about 10 km. As the human population increases, new generations must migrate to other places. For this reason, the people who originated in East-Africa began to disperse in all directions from there. Of course, they first spread to Africa, but they also spread to countries such as Arabia, Asia, and Europe by migrating along the seaside.

The genus called Australopithecus, with a brain of about 500 cm³, is the world's first bipedal, hunchbacked walking creature. Later, different human species came to life, starting with *Homo habilis* with a 650 cm³ brain, continuing with *Homo erectus* with a 900 cm³ brain, and continuing with *Homo sapiens* with a 1400 cm³ brain. In other words, humanity is a living species that has been freed from primitiveness by increasing its brain capacity (Fig 51).

Figure 51: Various species of bipeds (hominids) over the last 5 million years (Modified from Gedik 1998).

Homo habilis lived only in Africa. *Homo erectus* and *Homo sapiens* also spread to Asia and Europe. The Neanderthal variant of *Homo sapiens* spread to Asia and

Europe around 300,000 years ago. About 70,000 years ago, a newer variant of *Homo sapiens* – *Homo sapiens sapiens* – emerged, which in turn spread to Asia and Europe.

When did our ancestors abandoned wildlife and moved to social life?

Our world went through an ice age between 115,000 and 15,000 years, and during the ice ages, the Geography of Earth was as on the map. In the northern regions of America, Europe and Asia there was a 2.5 km thick ice cap. Since glaciers are formed as a result of the evaporation of water in the seas and storage on land as snow and ice, the water level in the seas is low enough to correspond to the amount of glaciers on land; This means a sea level drop of about 130 m! As such, the seas have receded from the coastal area called the continental shelf, and shallow marine environments have turned into land (Fig 52).

Figure 52: GLACIAL CYCLES play a very important role in the history of human development. BROWN region of Europe and Asia is very cold because it is far from the equator. The region, which is bordered by yellow color, is under constant snow-ice cover because it has a very high altitude.

The ice age coincides with today's BLACK-WINTER: There is snow in all regions of such as the Iranian plateau and Anatolia at an altitude of more than 200-300 meters. Therefore, it is almost impossible to live there. During the last Ice Age, which lasted a hundred thousand years, the regions suitable for human life in Europe and Asia are

also very limited. There are not enough food sources for people who must make a living by hunting animals and gathering wild berries.

Since humanity did not yet know how to make pottery until 8,500 years ago, it could only live in caves or temperate climates located around water sources. Areas that meet these two conditions are places close to the equator and near the edges of a river valley, with a height of less than three to four hundred meters.

For people who do not yet know how to make pottery, the Basra-Hormuz-Plain is an ideal environment, because the Tigris-Euphrates River irrigates the entire plain. It is located closest to Africa and has a temperate climate and is protected from the northern winds by the Zagros mountains. Majority of people migrating from Africa first settle there and begin to multiply.

The Persian Gulf is one of the environments that turn into land. It has been replaced by a huge fertile alluvial plain, which will be called the Basra-Hormuz-Plain. Near the Strait of Hormuz, there is a large lake with many islands on it. People who come here begin to live in two different environments: one part begins to live on the huge flat plain, and the other part begins to live on islands in the lake. The futures of these two groups will be different (Fig 53).

Figure 53: The most suitable place for human life during the ice age is the Basra-Hormuz Plain.

People who settled on the plain of Basra-Hormuz

The plain is very large, but people can only benefit from a 10 km strip of the 200 km wide plain, because it is impossible to find water in the hundreds of km. away from

the riverbank. Since the Tigris-Euphrates, which flows in the plain, flows in the south-east direction starting from Basra, it is possible to open channels along the river and deliver water to all parts of the plain. Realizing this, people began to dig water channels all over the plain, in cooperation, to make room for the growing population. This is a must. Just as atoms in a difficult situation in laser technology enter cooperation, people have taken the first step of socialization by cooperating with each other in the face of this necessity due to the physics of dynamical systems.

The ice age ends about 15,000 years ago and the sea level begins to rise by 1.1 cm every year due to the melting of the glaciers. An annual sea rise of 1.1 cm begins to affect people living on a flat plain very much in a few years. We can explain this as follows.

The Basra-Hormuz-Plain is about 800 km long, but there is only a 70-meter elevation difference between Basra and Dubai. In other words, the plain is almost flat, its slope is $70/800\ 000 = 0.0000875$. When the sea level rises by 1.1 cm each year, the inhabitants of the plains must move meters away from the coast every year. This means a huge loss of living environment. For this reason, those whose environment they live in is covered by the sea have had to flee and migrate every year.

Therefore, people living in this Plain during the ice age until 15,000 years ago were exposed to continuous migration between 14,000 and 7,000 years ago. Because it took so long for the Persian Gulf to be filled. It is understood from archaeological data (Braidwood 1995) that the Fertile Crescent region is at the beginning of the place where the people fleeing from the plain migrate. The culture created by the people of Göbekli-Tepe and Karahan-Tepe 11-12 thousand years ago is definitely an indication that they were experienced in socialization before.

The life of the inhabitants of the islands (SUMERIANS)

The Sumerians were the first people to provide information about their past by creating written documents. In these inscribed clay-tablets, they wrote that they came from the sea to the land of two rivers. (Ceram 1972)

Since humans could not live in the sea, it has always been a mystery where the Sumerians came to the Basra Region. Because until 15,000 years ago, it was not known that the sea completely receded from the Persian Gulf and turned into an alluvial plain during the ice age (Fig 54).

Figure 54: The Persian Gulf, which became completely land during the ice age, begins to be covered by the sea again 14 thousand years ago and the sea transgression continues until 7 thousand years ago. (Meteor ship surveys)

The stages of the refilling of the Persian Gulf with the sea after the ice age can be seen in the research carried out by the Meteor research ship in the region. (Meteor research results. - Borntraeger 1971. Series C. Geology and Geophysics / Editors: E. Seibold and H. Closs No. 4. 1. Geological-hydrological framework and first sedimentological results. By M. Hartmann [u.a.] 76 p., with ktn. : With 47 figs. and 12 tab. in the text)

Where did the Sumerians come from and settle in the Basra region?

The most important of the clay tablets, called the cuneiform script of the Sumerians, which has been preserved without being erased or destroyed until today, is the "List of Kings". On this prism-shaped tablet, it is written who ruled their society as Kings in their past (Fig 55).

Figure 55: Weld-Blundell Prism, King List tablet, Ashmolean Museum, Oxford England, found in
Larsa-Irak

They divided their history into two distinct periods:

Before the flood and After the flood.

In the pre-flood period, they lived in 5 different cities; It is noted that over time, cities "fell" and the ship of the kingdom was moved to another place. It is written that at the end of a great flood, the last city was destroyed, and after this flood, life continued with new kingdoms around Basra.

This information is consistent with geological information because there was a very long ice age until 15 thousand years ago. During this long ice age, some of the people who came to the Basra-Hormuz-Plain lived on the islands in the lake, which is located close to the Strait of Hormuz. The deepest place in the Persian Gulf is 90 m. But an undersea ridge called the Dubai-Bender-E-Lengeh threshold prevents waters deeper than 70 meters from draining. For this reason, a lake with a depth of 20 meters remains, which is shown in the Fig (Fig 56).

Figure 56: ATLAS-LAKE in glacial periods at Basra-Hormuz plain.

Let's call this lake, which does not exist today, the Atlas Lake. There are many islands in the lake because there are layers of anhydrite in the basement rocks of the Basra-Hormuz-region, and when they take water and swell, salt-dome-shaped bumps appear. For this reason, there are many bumps in the entire Basra-Hormuz-plain that will form islands during the rise of the sea.

When the ice age ended, it is understood from the Meteor ship surveys that the sea level rose by 1.1 cm every year in the Persian Gulf because of both the melting of the 2.5 km thick glaciers at the north pole and the melting of the glaciers on the Zagros Mountain tops.

The annual sea rise of 1.1 cm does not affect the Sumerians living on the island, because only 1.1 cm of an island 30-40 meters high is covered by the sea. For this reason, the inhabitants of the island continue to live on their islands for thousands of years. However, there is also a very thick ice cover on the Zagros Mountains in the north of the region, and the melting of these glaciers affects the people living on the islands in the lake, because the melting snow and the soils on the ground under the ice cover also mix with the melting waters, causing muddy floods.

These muddy floods, which are repeated every year, last for years because it takes more than three thousand years for an island 30-40 meters high to sink into the sea. For thousands of years, the inhabitants of the island had to deal with floods of mud of one to a few meters every year. In this long process:

1. It leads to the fact that the mountain slopes covered with plants become more and more bare.
2. The lake gradually fills with mud and ceases to be a lake and turns into a swamp.

These muddy floods, which are repeated every year, cause great damage in places such as gardens on the edges of the island. People must have tried to protect themselves against these disasters by building walls around the island. In this way, the people who lived by building a wall around the island for many years must have understood that their island would be completely submerged in the next few years, so they migrated to another island further north by making rafts and boats (Fig 57).

Figure 57: The Sumerians began to live on islands in the Lake Atlas, and when their island was buried in the sea due to transgression, they migrated to another island further north and landed on the shores of Basra.

The fact that this assumption is correct is understood from the mention of 5 ancient kingdom centers listed in the first part of the Sumerian Kings-list tablet (Eridug-Larag- Sippar- Syrupak- Basra after the Flood). At the end of the ice age, when the sea level rise caused by the melting of the glaciers caused the island in the lake to sink, the inhabitants migrated to another island further north by boat, etc. Thus, life continues in the form of moving to 5 different cities. Finally, life on the island ends with a great flood. Because the glacier masses that remain in the last stage of the melting of mountain glaciers cause the greatest flood disasters, because they are like balloons filled with water (Glacier outburst floods), and when they burst, they drag

everything in their path and carry them to the sea, like dams that collapse. The last pack of glaciers remaining on the tops of the Zagros mountains had this effect and buried the island where the Sumerians lived. These statements are conclusive evidence that the Sumerians lived on the islands and migrated to another island further north as the islands sank.

The Sumerians went out to the vicinity of Basra after the flood and in a tablet they emphasize that they came to the region of "two rivers from the sea" (Ceram 1972). Archaeological findings show that the Sumerians came to the Basra region about 6 thousand years ago. Sumerian tablets were written by Sumerian thinkers-scribes after the Sumerians landed in the Basra region and discovered writing 5500 years ago.

Archaeological data shows that a society called the Sumerians emerged around Basra about 6,500 years ago and established city-states 5,500 years ago. In other words, when the Sumerians came to the Basra region, they did not immediately establish the system called STATE, which was owned and managed from the top, but established holy kingdoms after many years.

If we summarize the data presented above, then the following situation arises:

Humanity took the first step in the transition from wildlife to civilized life in the Basra-Hormuz-Plain.

1. In the part of the Basra-Hormuz-Plain near the Strait of Hormuz, there is a large lake that can be called Atlas, and there are islands in this lake. This lake is located in the interior of the Strait of Hormuz, which opens to the Indian Ocean.
2. There are islands in this Atlas Lake, from which you can pass to each other and to the huge surrounding plain.
3. To the north of the lake there is a very large mountain range (Zagros mountains), which protects the islands and the plain from the northern winds. This high mountain range extends into the sea like a tongue near the Strait of Hormuz. The Tigris-Euphrates River flows next to it.
4. With the end of the ice age, the glaciers on the peaks of the Zagros mountains began to melt and floods occurred every year. Since the melting snow and the

soil under the ice cover were mixed with the floods along with the waters, the mountain slopes were left bare.

5. Muddy floods that lasted every year filled the Atlas Lake over time and turned it into a swamp.
6. Around the lake there is a rectangular plain with a size of 800 x 200 km. Water channels have been opened to benefit from all parts of this plain.
7. Since the plain is an alluvial plain, all kinds of plants can grow in abundance.
8. 14,000 years ago, as the sea began to fill the plain again, the people in the plain began to flee.

The above paragraphs have been prepared according to today's geological and archaeological data.

The following information is a summary of the works “Timaeus and Critias” of the Greek philosopher Platon.

1. Before BC. 9600, there was a sea called the Atlas, which could be crossed by ships; The Atlantis sea is located on the inner side of a strait that opens into a very large ocean.
2. On the side of this Atlantis Sea near the strait, there is an island called Atlas. From this island, you can go to other islands and the land surrounding the lake.
3. The land surrounding the lake is large and covered with very high mountains. These mountains protect the islands and the plain around the lake from the northern winds. This high land (where the strait is) extends into the sea like a tongue and a river flows next to it.
4. There have been many floods in the past, and with these floods there have been such landslides that the slopes of the surrounding mountains have been bare and bare.
5. The Atlantis Sea has become increasingly swampy due to constant floods and floods that last every year.

6. There is a rectangular plain around the lake; its size \approx is 540 x 190 km, this entire plain is surrounded by a deep and wide water channel. There are also many other water channels that cut the entire plain transversely and longitudinally.
7. In the country (on the plains and islands) there is the most fertile land in the world, so that all kinds of plants and vegetables can be grown; And it is so abundant that even animals such as elephants can be fed. The climate is so suitable that all kinds of spices and fruits (pomegranates, citrus fruits, coconut, etc.) are grown.
8. In this land of Atlantis, an empire was established which was effective as far as the strait by the ocean, and on the other as far as Egypt and the Adriatic. One day (11600 years ago) this state first entered the state in the north (?) and then Egypt.

According to the right and law of priority the name of the Basra-Hormuz-Plain should be changed to the Atlantis-Plain, because Plato gave a very concise human development more than 2500 years ago in his books Timaeus and Critias, and what is written is in line with today's knowledge.

For this reason, the term Atlantis-Plain will be used in the future.

5. Chapter- How did the people of Atlantis have their Future?

Humanity has learned mutual interaction, solidarity, and cooperation during the 50 thousand years of life they have spent in the Basra-Hormuz-Plain. It is exactly the expected result that the civilization of the Fertile Crescent region, where points such as Göbekli-Tepe, Karahan Tepe, etc. of South-Eastern Anatolia are the center, was created by people with such an experience.

The language spoken by the Atlantis-people.

In order to understand what the future of the Atlanteans was like, it is enough to know what language they spoke in their past. Because a comparison can be made with the languages spoken by the people scattered throughout our world.

Since humanity originated in East-Africa, it is expected that the language spoken in that region will continue to be spoken in the places where they migrate. As a matter of fact, Atkinson (2011) determined that the oldest languages are in Central and Southern Africa and that other languages closely follow the migration routes of Homo s. sapiens, which spread from Africa to the world, as a result of the analysis of 504 world languages in terms of phonetic complexity. This view has been confirmed by other researchers such as Fort & Perez-Losada 2016, Kacprzak et al 2013, Perreault & Mathew 2012.

As shown on the map, languages belonging to the Bantu language group are spoken in this region today. One of them is the Swahili language. Swahili, like all other Bantu languages, is an agglutinated language, and its characteristics will be presented below (Fig 58).

Figure 58: Birthplace of humanity

As an example, the table below shows how different the English language is, while the similarity of Swahili and Turkish, which are agglutinating languages, is shown (Fig 59).

Agglutinating Languages		Indo-European Languages
Swahili	Türkçe	
Ninakata	kesiyorum	I am cutting
Sikati	kesmiyorum	I am not cutting
Umekata	kestiniz	you have cut
ukimekata	kesseydiniz	if you had cut

Odadakilerdensin.

Oda + da + ki + ler + den + sin

You are one of the persons from the room.

Figure 59: Comparison of agglutinating and Indo-European languages

The main feature of agglutinating languages is that the word "Odadakilerdensin" has been transformed into a sentence such as "You are one of the persons from the room" in Indo-European languages, which are a fragmented language group.

Let's compare these two language groups (Fig 60):

Figure 60: Comparison of the Word order in a sentence in different language groups.

Now let's show how widespread the language of the people living in a very distant Asian region such as Japan and the languages with similar structures and attachments to Turkish are in the world: A native Turkish speaker and a Japanese learner (Selcuk Yilmaz, who works as a programmer in the US) has shown that there are structural

similarities between the Japanese and Turkish languages. For example, the word order is almost identical (Fig 61).

Figure 61: Comparison of two language separated over long distances but belonging to the same group.

Compared to English, the difference is striking: the grammar is also somewhat similar to Turkish. Since both are agglutinated languages, they share the same logic.

The last representatives of the Atlantis people to land on the shores of Basra were the Sumerians. And it is clear from their written documents that the Sumerians used an agglutinating language. So the Atlantis people must have used an agglutinated language. Therefore, the people who fled from the Plain of Atlantis and spread to Europe and Asia must have an agglutinating language.

As a matter of fact, it has been observed that the people who crossed to America through Asia have agglutinating languages. Ex. Among the quechua peoples living in the Peruvian Andes and the mountainous regions of South America, a fully agglutinated language is spoken: Maqachinakurkan = They let each other be beaten.

The following are examples of the prevalence of agglutinated languages (from Wikipedia):

Niger–Congo languages. Bantu languages.

Turkic languages. Turkish.

Basques language,

Finnish, Estonian, Hungarian

Kartvelian languages. (Georgian, Laz)

Dravidian languages. Tamil, Sanskrit.

Austronesian languages. Tagalog.

Indigenous languages of the Americas. Algonquian languages.

Eskimo–Aleut languages.

Berber languages.

In the languages that people speak, words change over time, but the general structure of the language does not change much. It is understood that the ancestors of modern humans, who emerged in East-Africa 60-70 thousand years ago, spoke agglutinated language, such as Turkish or Finnish.

Where did the Atlantis people migrate?

As shown in the previous chapter, the inhabitants of the plain were the first to leave the Plain of Atlantis, because every year the sea began to cover a very large coastline of the plain, which was flat. The people on that coastline have also started to flee (Fig 62).

Figure 62: Migration routes of Atlantis peoples. The Fig shows where the people who fled from the plain migrated and continued their lives.

When the ice age ended 15,000 years ago, the sea level began to rise by 1.1 cm every year and the Basra-Hormuz-Plain began to be covered with the sea again. The majority of people whose plains are covered by the sea fled to the region called the Fertile Crescent and formed the first civilized societies in the world.

How the Fertile Crescent Developed

With the melting of snow and ice cover, the Anatolian plateau becomes suitable for plant and animal development again. These regions, which were previously inhabited by many people, became the new homeland of those who migrated from the Atlantean plain.

People living in the Basra-Plain during the ice age were subjected to continuous migration between 14,000 and 7,000 years ago. Because it took so long for the Persian Gulf to be filled. Regions of Anatolia such as Karahan Tepe and Göbekli Tepe, where the snow and ice cover was removed, were the first places where people who were exposed to migration settled (Fig 63).

Figure 63: The fertile crescent is the region in which humanity started civilized life. It was created by those who came from the plain of Atlantis.

The first settlements in Anatolia are in the Mound style (Fig 64).

Figure 64: Civilized life started in Anatolia after 12 thousand years and lived in common living environments called HÖYÜK in equality and freedom until 4 thousand years ago.

People of 5-10 thousand years ago lived in houses completely adjacent to each other. The walls of the houses were shared, so the heating was more economical. Entrances and exits to the houses were through a ladder through a hole in the ceiling. The dead people were buried in a hole dug in the floor of the house. For this reason, at the end of a certain years, the houses were completely demolished and new houses were built on them. In this way, dome-like images were formed, which gradually risen. These are called MOUNDS today. There is no class distinction in mound-style life, there is a social life where equality and freedom are valid.

We can understand the perspective of the people living in the mounds from the reliefs and sculptures they made. It is seen in the works left by the people of Göbeklitepe, one of the oldest mounds, that they have a belief that can be called animism. By engraving many different animal Figs such as snakes, vultures, pigs and eagles on T-shaped columns weighing tons, they explained that all beings in nature have a soul. Since there is no such thing as nobility in the animistic view of life (Fig 65), there is a common life based on equality-freedom-fraternity.

Figure 65: Societies in Anatolia before 4,000 years ago must have had an animistic view of life.

Why is communal living necessary?

Those who do work or action in nature are always the components of beings. For example, a person does everything through his cells. They form and give the order for the carpenter to swing the hammer in this direction with such and such a force. The process of recognizing an insect that a scientist who is researching insects sees is carried out by the cells in that scientist's brain. The process of recognizing a leaf that a scientist who is researching plants sees is carried out by the cells in that scientist's brain. A man cannot be a carpenter, an insect-expert, and a herbalist at the same time, because there are certain limits to the number of cells in the brain that can be charged with these tasks. For him, professional distinctions called specialization are required. In this way, it is possible to create much more information. Community life therefore has to be a partnership between business-and-professional members.

Since the growth and development of nature begins with the lowest quantum elements and continues in the form of growing systems such as atoms, molecules, cells, bodies, the creation and construction of something new always depends on the capabilities of the base elements (molecules, cells, etc.) that make up that system. Since the elements at the base get their energy from the quantum energy bank and this energy bank always applies the principle of investing in the most economical systems, it has been inevitable that there will be a great competition among living things in adapting to the new environmental conditions in nature. In the competition, the actions of creating a new structure that is compatible with the environment by using the least energy have been the main impulse in increasing species diversity.

For example, the formation of different algae groups such as blue-, green-, red-algae in the seas is intended to facilitate the conversion of light of different wavelengths into chemical energy by photosynthesis. If an algae makes use of both red and blue light, it must constantly change the protein molecules to do so, because a protein of the same structure is suitable for the conversion of a certain kind of energy; When another type of energy is released, changes in protein composition are required. For this reason, concentrating on certain types of energy and going to a structure that will produce protein molecules to benefit from that type of energy has been the most common method applied in nature.

Life is based on a system of mutual interaction and partnership and develops in accordance with it. Let's compare a situation in which a person tries to do everything himself with a situation in which he tries to live with other people by entering into the division of labor and specializing in different fields.

A carpenter hammers a nail with 2-3 hammer blows and can hammer 10 nails in one minute. A person who is not an expert can only hammer a nail in a minute, and in the meantime, he bends and bends 2-3 nails and makes them unusable. A typist can write a page of text in 1 minute, a non-specialist will spend more than half an hour on this task. As can be seen, service partnership based on division of labor is the source of efficiency.

Humanity lived in the wilderness until 12 thousand years ago, that is, it thought only of its own family, considering others as competitors. 12,000 years ago, it made a great leap forward and entered the division of labor by partnering with its neighbours, and the foundation of the partnership system between business and professional members was laid by specializing in a different field. We can say this with certainty, because in the course of thousands of years of development, in addition to the first professional specializations such as stonemasons, painters, animal-skin dressers, sculpture-relief artists, new professions such as plant and animal development, pottery, mining, pot-boiler making, blacksmithing have emerged over time. Members of all these different businesses and professions lived together in Anatolia between 12 thousand years and 4 thousand years, all of which

are adjacent to each other, called HÖYÜK. No one has determined the rules of their common life from above.

The tradition of owning the life of society by people representing a sacred office at the top and managing it from the top called the state started with the Sumerians 4-5 thousand years ago and became widespread in the world after that.

Life is the natural result of the quantum impulse. 13 billion years ago, the entire universe was made up of only quanta. Quanta are the most basic action-elements, they are in constant motion. This kind of life is very difficult, and quanta want to get rid of it. If humans continued to live alone, they would still have hunter-gatherer wildlife and would be in a constant state of stress. However, by mutually cooperating with each other, they specialized in different fields and passed to social-civilized life. Quanta start with protons, neutrons, and electrons and form higher-level systems in the form of atoms and molecules, and continue the dynamical system in nature.

On the other hand, people after 4,000 years have put forward a view of life based on HOLINESS by showing the influencing-directing power in nature as human-shaped kings, etc. For this reason, thousands of years old concepts of equality and freedom have been shelved, and someone's life has been prioritized, not common life. In other words, class distinction began 5 thousand years ago with the introduction of the STATE system with the concept of holiness and nobility by the Sumerians.

The paragraphs cited above show that when the Basra-Hormuz-Plain was covered by the sea between 15,000 and 7,000 years, the people who had to flee from there migrated to the Fertile-Crescent region such as Göbekli-Tepe and created settlements in the style of Mounds.

The cities founded by the Sumerians consist of people who settled around a temple called the Ziggurat and served the gods and nobles living in the temple. The state is the property of the nobles. Inside the ziggurat live humanoid-gods or holy kings. The view that people were created to serve holy kings is instilled in everyone, implanted in their subconsciousness, and they work all their lives and make sure that their masters are happy.

With the Sumerians, a social life system was initiated which based on the distinction between noble- not-noble humans. In all social life systems formed after the Sumerians, this understanding of "state-ownership" has always been maintained. Even today, the people are not being taught that the ownership of society belongs to the people who constitute the state.

This is due to the enormous increase in the human population after 5 thousand years. The easiest way to establish balance and order in communities of thousands is to connect the constituent-creative system in nature to a divine-sacred supernatural-power system assumed outside and above beings.

The Sumerians solved this issue with the belief that "after the Kingdom descended from heaven". Notice that "the king does not descend from heaven", the kingdom descends from the sky. A power system in the sky sends divine commands to the kings through a holy book called ME that people must obey!

6. CHAPTER- The Concept of Holiness and the emergence of Kingdoms

Humanity has lived a wildlife based on hunting and gathering since 2.5 million years. It is understood from paleoanthropological-archaeological research that this humanity, which spread throughout the world, lived a complete wildlife until 12-13 thousand years ago. People who live in the wildlife live scattered. In civilized-social life, people started to live in communities of thousands of people. The transition to community life started when people specialized in different jobs-and-professions and entered into a partnership relationship based on mutual service exchanges.

Each person has a unique talent and is different from others with this feature. Some people have a beautiful voice, they sing, some have the ability to paint, some make all kinds of musical instruments speak, some solve the most difficult mathematical problems, some like carpentry, some have a lot of imagination, write a novel, propose a scientific theory, some swim very well, some run very well, etc. These different abilities are the differences that must be present for social life. People acquire a profession for themselves according to these differences in abilities, and a social partnership emerges according to their mutual exchange of services. No profession is superior to another.

Civilized life based on service partnership started with people entering into partnerships in different jobs and professions. The specialization of each individual in a different field has greatly increased the production potential in the society, so the number of people living in a narrow area has increased rapidly.

As can be seen in the Fig 57, while approximately 4 million people lived in our world 10-12 thousand years ago, 190 million people lived 2 thousand years ago, 1 billion people lived 200 years ago, and 8 billion people live today. Humanity's population growth on Earth is exponential and its transition to explosive increase coincides with about 5 thousand years ago (Fig 66).

Figure 66: The growth of the human population in our world is exponential, and the explosive increase occurred about 5,000 years ago.

In accordance with the population growth, the social lifestyle has changed. Until 5,000 years ago, humanity lived in relations based on mutual service-exchange, that is, in relations of equality and freedom, that is, there was no master-servant relationship between people. This kind of natural development seems to have taken place in Anatolia until about 4,000 years ago, because millers, blacksmiths, shepherds, bricklayers, artists, etc., all lived side by side and in similar houses. Ancient settlements of the mound type are proof of this.

But 5,000 years ago, the Sumerians began to form a system like City-States. City-States are a system in which societies are owned and managed by someone from above. The reason for switching to such an authoritarian system may be that difficulties have arisen in the system based on mutual exchange of services due to population growth. Because agreement and compromise require mutual interaction. This is possible in societies of a few hundred people, but in societies with a population of more than thousands, mutual understanding and compromise is very difficult.

For about 50,000 years, humanity has been seeking to understand life and to form an idea about how the balance and order in nature are formed. Humanity, which lived a life in accordance with the natural system by observing nature and forming very logical life views until 5 thousand years ago, has been stuck in a religious view of life based on the concept of holiness for 5 thousand years. The reason for this is that after 5 thousand years, due to the enormous increase in the human population, they were forced to live in associations called cities, consisting of thousands of people. The easiest way to establish balance and order in communities of thousands is to connect the creator-creator system in nature to a divine-sacred supernatural-power system assumed outside and above beings. When this is considered, it becomes necessary to hand over the management of societies to people with holy spirits. The holy spirits of men are also understood by their miraculous powers.

For this reason, it can be thought that the Sumerians may have left the management of society to someone at the top.

And how will someone at the top claim that he gets the authority to govern society and make the people obedient to him?

The Sumerians solved this issue with the belief that "after the Kingdom descended from heaven". Notice that "the king does not descend from heaven", the kingdom descends from the sky. A power system in the sky sends divine commands to the kings through a holy book called ME that people must obey!

This is how the concepts of KINGDOM, HOLINESS, and HOLY BOOK came into being.

When authoritarian power such as King resides at the top of the society, the wheel of bureaucracy will be filled by people believed to be noble persons such as lords, dukes, duchesses, counts, aghas and masters. Authoritarian societies emerges in this manner that still continue today.

This is how the concept of nobility arises. Sumerian tablet inscriptions confirm the views, that the gods created noble kings to guide and govern societies, and that nobles were created from clay to serve the gods (and therefore themselves, the gods' representatives of the world).

This group of lords, who claim to be nobles, know that they have not a source of energy. In order to overcome this difficulty, they put forward a view of creation that the creator of everything in nature is an extra-natural (or super)-power system located outside of beings (in the sky), and therefore the ownership of everything in the world belongs to this creator. As the representatives of the Creator in the world, the ownership of everything in the land they own belongs to these masters at the top. For this reason, living environments begin to be shared and owned, and the seeds of exploitation in the world are planted 5 thousand years ago.

The conception of holiness constitutes a master-servant system and leads to biblical tradition.

The Holy kingdoms that emerged 5,000 years ago and the biblical religions that emerged after 3,500 years were born in this way.

The Sumerians, who lived in the Atlas-Lake at the end of the Basra-Hormuz-Plain, migrated from one island to another in the Gulf covered by the sea between 15 thousand and 7 thousand years, changed 5 islands and came to the Basra region. The Sumerians did not accept a symbiosis but a system of social life with a holy kingdom ruled from above (Fig 67).

Figure 67: The concept of holiness has led to authoritarian systems in the social life and has been the source of all social problems.

Community management based on holiness was created by the Sumerians 5500 years ago. Community management was founded according to "After the Kingdom Descended from Heaven" view. By following a view expressed in this manner, traditions are established that the right to govern societies belongs to the sacred people. How to identify "holy- sacred" people?

People who had special abilities, such as being very intelligent, very powerful, or had signs on their bodies that were believed to be indicative of holiness, or who were believed to have received special messages from the creator, were considered sacred. Until 3-4 centuries ago, people with such characteristics were considered sacred, and the administration of states was left to certain people who were believed to be noble origin, such as kings and sultans. Since the sons of these kings or sultans must also be sacred, dynasties have arisen and societies have been ruled for centuries by dynasties believed to be holy persons.

For 3-4 centuries, the view that the Creator sent a "holy book" to certain people and gave the right to rule to those who represented that faith was formed, and scriptural religions were revealed.

The group of lords, who claim to be noble, put forward a view of creation that the creator of everything in nature is a super-power system located outside of beings (in the sky), and therefore the ownership of everything in the world belongs to this creator. Those rulers hired soldiers for money to form an army that will protect and expand their property. For this reason, living environments begin to be shared and owned, and the seeds of exploitation in the world are planted 5 thousand years ago.

It is clearly seen in the cultural development graph of humanity that the social management system based on the view of holiness deeply affects the cultural development of humanity. As can be seen in the Fig 59, humanity reached the beginning of the explosion point of exponential functional development 40-50 thousand years ago and entered a very rapid phase of mental development. However, at the point (K), which coincides with 4-5 thousand years ago, this rapid rise suddenly stopped and a slowly developing phase began. This slowdown, called the "Holliness-route", means that there is a deterioration in the logical system of people. By point (R), which corresponds to three centuries ago, there is a bifurcation again: some nations have developed more rapidly, while others have remained on a slowed course. It is known from historical developments that nations that have entered into faster development are in a better development thanks to the renaissance and reform of the medieval mentality (Fig 68).

Figure 68: The graph of human cultural development clearly shows when the right path has been changed with the wrong path.

Since the sacred-minded system of life is the opposite of the quantization growing system of nature, it has been very harmful to humanity and has led to imperialism, which prioritizes war-destruction, not agreement-reconciliation.

7. CHAPTER The Spread of Humanity Around the World

Since fossils of *Homo erectus* have been found in Asia and Europe dating back to about 1.9 million years ago, it must have reached these continents about 2 million years ago.

Homo sapiens neanderthalensis and *Homo sapiens alayensis* have been seen in Asia and Europe for about 3-4 hundred thousand years.

Only *Homo sapiens sapiens*, defined as modern humans, have reached Australia and America. When *Homo sapiens sapiens* arrived in different parts of the world is shown on the map (Fig 69).

Figure 69: Modern human ancestors, who emerged in East Africa 70,000 years ago, spread around the world along the routes shown in the Fig.

Propagation of *Homo sapiens sapiens*

The passage to America is thought to be through the Bering Strait; Because, as seen in the ice age geography map given above, the Bering Strait was land during the ice age because it was under sea water shallower than 90 meters. But people who

crossed into the Americas may have reached it by sea transport or by moving along the coast of the Pacific Ocean.

With the end of the ice age, the 2.5 km thick ice cover on the Northern Hemisphere begins to melt and the melting waters begin to raise the water level in the oceans again. It takes about 7-8 thousand years for glaciers to melt.

Civilizing is the result of people's search for how to deal with a difficult situation when they find themselves in a difficult situation, and it is solved by creating a higher-level system by mutual compromise, in accordance with the principles of dynamical systems physics. Due to the fact that the environment they live in is increasingly sinking into the sea, people who are forced to live in a narrower area have also started the first socialization by reconciling. Sea level rise has occurred not only between Basra and Hormuz, but also throughout the world. For example, much of the land between Australia and Asia was turned into land during the ice age, and the two continents were almost united with each other. When the ice age ended, these regions, which turned into land as a result of the sea receding, began to be covered with the sea again. Depending on their depth, they are covered by the sea again in a process that lasts for thousands of years.

Migrations of the people from Atlantis plain

Where could the people from Atlantis plain migrated to, being forced to migrate as a result of the end of the ice age, due to the transgression of the sea?

The answer is very clear: While the end of the Ice Age makes the Atlantis Plain uninhabitable, it also transforms previously uninhabitable places such as Anatolia, Europe, and Asia into a livable environment. These places became the new homeland of the Atlantis peoples.

Since the language spoken in the region where *Homo sapiens sapiens* was born is agglutinated, the language of the people of the Atlantis-Plains, must also be agglutinating. The data supporting this view is that the languages of the societies (Sumerians, Turks, Azerbaijanis, etc.) that migrated from this plain and settled in the surrounding regions are "agglutinated". As a matter of fact, the Sanskrit language

spoken further east is also agglutinated. Even the languages spoken by the native tribes of the Americas are also agglutinated. In other words, the first language spoken by humanity is definitely agglutinated (Fig 70).

Figure 70: The languages of the societies that migrated from the plain of Atlantis and spread to the world were always from the same language group in the past.

European languages are a new language group formed in the steppe environments between Ukraine and Kazakhstan 5-6 thousand years ago.

People living in the Atlantis Plain were forced to migrate continuously from 14 thousand years ago until 7 thousand years ago. The language spoken by these immigrant people must definitely be agglutinated.

In the past, people usually traveled along river valleys or sea coasts. The main reason for this is the fear of getting lost. Since the north of the plain of Atlantis is surrounded by a very high mountain range, it is very difficult to cross, there is still a snow and ice cover on it, and there is a high probability of disappearing. For this reason, the Atlantis peoples migrated along the following routes:

1. People going along the sea coast must reach in the easterly direction India and along the Red Sea coast direction Egypt. Those who choose this migration route to the east are blended with the Indus valley and Dravidian culture. Those who went in the direction of the Red Sea became the pioneers of the building of Ancient Egyptian culture.

2. Those who migrated to the north-west along the Tigris-Euphrates valley, which would lead to the formation of Anatolian and European societies, will be discussed in a separate section below.
3. Those who go north from the point where the Zagros Mountains end are the Turkic-speaking communities such as Qashqais, Afshars, Halachs, and Khorasans who still live in Iran today on the Iranian plateau and are the first inhabitants of those regions. One branch of them goes to the north-west and forms the Azerbaijanis. Another part of them continue towards Central-Asia and form the Central-Asian Turks. In other words, a tribe that speaks a language called Persian and belongs to the Indo-European language group came to Iran much later (Narasimhan et al, 2019). This topic will be discussed in a later section.

The Atlantis lowlands were subject to continuous migration between 14,000 and 7,000 years ago, because that's how long it took for the Persian Gulf to fill. And 6-7 thousand years ago, a tribe called the Sumerians – which is stated to be at a very advanced level of civilization compared to the other tribes in the vicinity – came to the vicinity of Basra. This tribe later wrote in their cuneiform tablets that they "came from the sea to the region of two rivers" (Ceram 1972).

As can be understood, the tribe called Sumer continued their lives by living on the mounds on the plain of Atlantis until the Persian Gulf was completely filled. However, most of the people living in the flat plain had to leave the plain much earlier and migrate to other regions. (Göbekli tepeli, Çatalhöyüklu, Azerbaijanis, etc.)

The places where the Atlantis people migrated are shown on the map presented above. The evidence that migrations took place on these routes is given by the analysis of the languages spoken by today's societies and the results of genetic haplogrub analysis.

Opening of Anatolia and Europe to settlement by the Atlantis-People.

Today, there is a very wrong view that the first people of Anatolia were Greeks. This is the result of complete ignorance. Because the first indigenous people of both

Anatolia, Thrace, the entire Aegean region and the Balkans were the Atlantis-People, who spoke agglutinated language like Turkish, Ungarish and settled in these regions from 12 thousand years ago until 7-8 thousand years ago. The so-called Greek tribe is an invading society consisting of the Yamnaya-Nomads in the north and descended on the indigenous tribes in the south from the Ukrainian region 3600 years ago. These historical facts will be explained in the following sections. It is very important to know our past-history. If we don't teach these historical facts in schools, how will our children claim and defend their country?

People who had to flee from the Atlantis Plain settled first in the Fertile Crescent region and Anatolia. Turkmens and Yörüks were the first tribes. Those who fled to the north-west along the Tigris-Euphrates valleys became the first inhabitants of the northern regions, such as the Anatolian plateau, which were uninhabitable during the ice age.

Where did the Anatolian-farmers come from?

Recent archaeological findings have shown that the oldest socialization points were 12 thousand years ago in Southeastern Anatolia regions such as Göbekli Tepe, Karahan Tepe, and Hallan Çemi. The people who started social life at these points had not yet discovered agriculture and animal husbandry, but they had reached the concept of "life partnership". And they had attained this ability on the Atlantis plain. Because, in order to be able to live on all sides of the huge plain, they had come to the knowledge of seeing and accepting the people around them not as rivals, but as partners who would carry out the construction of water channels all over the plain. This is how the first social behavior began, and the place where it first started was the Basra-Hormuz plain, in other words, the Atlantis Plain.

With the end of the ice age, when the Atlantis Plain began to be covered with the sea again, people left the plain and began to look for new living environments.

Figure 71: Modern humans reached Anatolia 12 thousand years ago, but they were able to cross into Europe between 8,000 and 6,000 years ago.

Anatolia is one of the new living environments, because Anatolia, which was under snow and ice during the ice age, turned into new living environments with the melting of snow and ice. The people of the plain of Atlantis are also aware of this, because the flint traders based in Anatolia pass this information on to them.

For this reason, the first socialization in the world started 12 thousand years ago in a belt called the Fertile-Crescent, where South-eastern Anatolia is the center, as shown in the map presented (Fig 71).

It takes 3 thousand years for the whole of Anatolia to be opened to settlement. For this reason, the first settlements in northern and western Anatolia began to form about 9 thousand years ago. The whole of Anatolia is therefore the first homeland of the Atlantis Plain immigrants, because the places where they lived before (the Atlantis Plain) were covered by the sea, they were forced to migrate and became the first inhabitants of this previously snow-covered region. This is how the core of Anatolian societies was formed.

8. CHAPTER

We must think about life on universal scale.

1. Point: In the first part, it was shown that the formations and developments in nature and the world began to be formed with a completely informed and conscious

system, and that the constituent power system was the realm of QUANTA, which is the smallest and most basic components of beings.

2. Point:- It has been shown that quantum constructors are not inanimate-dead elements, on the contrary, they are living-conscious elements and have a system that increases and develops exponentially like all living things. This method is called Quantization.
3. Point:- The quantum power begins to grow and develop by the folding method called quantization and forms the proton-neutron-electron triplet 12-13 billion years ago. Then, by combining them, about a hundred chemical elements (atoms) are formed, which make up nature. Then, substances such as water, salt and mica, called molecules, are formed from the combinations of these atoms and the natural system emerges. Thus, a system of evolution-growth emerges from lower-levels to higher-levels.
4. Point:- Everything is made with energy, and the origin and source of energy is only quanta. Energy is transferred from quanta elements to atomic elements such as proton-neutron-electron. Then there is transfer from atoms to molecules. It is then transferred from molecules to super-systems in the form of cells, bodies, etc. All these transfers take place with information and the quantum system migrates to the systems that form the most ergonomic structure. They function as traffic signs that direct the flow of information energy. Thus, an integrated sub-system – super-system structure emerges in nature.
5. Point:- One point is very important in these sub-system-super-system relations: that no system can be eternal or very long-lasting. Since nature is in a constant state of change and transformation, no higher-level being can have an eternal life. If the entities formed become eternal, the quantum elements are imprisoned within these eternal beings, and the creation of new higher-level beings is prevented, because they are all imprisoned. Therefore, all beings have a cycle of birth and death.
6. Point: -Death is not an annihilation. It is to return to enter into a blending with the universal system in order to participate in the cycle of development of nature and our world in a better direction. There is nothing in nature that does not change. The

reason for change-transformations is that the natural system is in a constant evolution. In order for evolution to continue, entities must be disassembled after a certain lifetime, blended back into the natural system, and thus reorganized with newer information. If there is no death, the natural system is blocked, because the energy in nature is blocked by beings with fixed lives. In other words, the change-transformation called time disappears. However, time is formed by the fact that energy is in a constant current.

7. Point:- If time had not changed, our world would have stopped in a way consisting of combinations of atoms and molecules 4 billion years ago. There was no age of bacteria, no insects, no dinosaurs, no mammals. Therefore, we humans could not be formed.
8. Point:- There is nothing in nature that does not change. This includes what we call the "creative" system. For this reason, the quantum system, which constitutes the beginning of the natural system, also undergoes changes along with the higher-level systems they create. For this reason, the universe is constantly evolving.
9. Point:-Information is recorded in the chemical composition and physical tissue of the entities and is transmitted to lower-level systems and maintained for generations. There can be no such thing as extinction because atoms change and transform to update and maintain information. Nothing can be done without knowledge. Our information is stored in the cells in our body, the information of the cells is stored in their atoms, and the information of the atoms is stored in the quantum system within them. Thus, the knowledge of doing and creating something in nature is based on the quantum system. For this reason, the quantum system does not remain constant, but is constantly changing and transforming according to the information developed in nature. However, the God of the holy books is fixed and unchangeable. Since knowledge is constantly increasing and developing in nature, how does God remain unchanging? Doesn't it have interaction with entities? Since it is certain that information is recorded and processed in atoms by genomes, which are books of the creator, can there be another book called the holy book? Moreover, is a holy book sent to each nation in its own language compatible with the creativity of the natural system?

10. A person who denies his cells and the quantum system, which equips him with information-generating and creative properties, and seeks his creator in a "very large" system, betrays his creative system. In nature, the constructive-force is at the base, because energy is at quanta. Humans, on the other hand, have placed the power system at the top. Since there is no such thing in nature, humanity lives in complete ignorance, harming both itself and nature (Fig 72).

Figure 72: God is not a frightening being that punishes those who do not obey the biblical commands He has sent through His messengers. God is the realm of quanta within us that structures our bodies according to our intentions and behaviours, that why God is misrepresented to us.

Nature consists of lower-level and higher-level structures, and thus an integrated system emerges that is dependent on each other. The rules that apply at such levels are published by Feibleman (1954) under the title "Theory of Integrative Levels" and outline the "lower-level - higher-level" relations. Among them, the most important are the following:

- i. Each level carries a new feature in addition to that of the level(s) below it.
- ii. The degree of complexity increases towards the higher-levels.
- iii. A disorder that occurs at any level affects all other related levels.

- iv. In every system, the higher-level is dependent on the lower-level; The higher-level indicates the direction (target) to the lower-level.
- v. In the formation of any level, the power of creation is at lower-level; It is obliged to show high-level targets.

In order to achieve the intended goals, chemical compositions must be changed. The transformation of molecules into each other occurs through the creation of energy gradients. The same method applies to the transformation of elements to each other. Therefore, by creating various small environments within the cells, micro-environments are created in which the molecules will be able to decompose into their atoms; Then, by creating smaller micro-environments in which atoms are converted to each other, the changes required by existence are obtained.

The transformation of atoms into each other is not done by cells, but by atoms (and therefore by the subatomic elements within them) based on the perception and behavior of atoms, because the power of constructive-force generation and transfer is always in the sub-systems. Cells only make energy gradient changes, creating the information (force field) from where the energy should flow from where to where; The subatomic elements inside the atoms also obey that force field, flowing from one atom to another, causing the atoms to transform into each other.

A word of caution: Targeting cells cannot be done with words. If a person tries to do what he wants to do with determination, this becomes a process of targeting the cells. Therefore, those who try to do something with determination and patience reach a state to do that job after a while, because the cells have made the necessary arrangements in the body during that time and that person is in a position to do that job.

At the Chapter 6 of this book the story of a much larger-scale effort is given, that is, millions of years, of a group of living things living in the terrestrial environment is given as a result of a structure suitable for living in a marine environment. That development is natural-scientific proof that the scriptural view of creation is completely wrong.

There is nothing in nature that does not undergo change, because everything begins with the most basic element of life called quanta. This constituent power system is the most basic element of vitality, which is defined as "elementares WirkungsQUANTUM" within beings and corresponds to the concept of SOUL. Since quanta are the most basic element of life, everything in nature takes place in the form of their reproduction. This is called quantization. Atoms are products of this quantization. Molecules are formed by the combination of atoms, cells are formed by the combination of molecules, and the whole world of living things, including humans, is formed by the combination of cells. The lifespan of these growing systems is also limited, and every upper system created at the end of certain processes is again separated into its parts, and in accordance with the changing conditions, the particles are re-combined according to new information, and a gradually developing-evolving nature emerges and a universal life system emerges. This system is called a dynamical system and operates according to the principles of dynamical systems physics, which is summarized as "information & self-organization". Therefore, the basis of this system is the "birth-death-cycle". Thus, an evolution in the style of lower-level – higher-level has emerged. The power of making and creating always belongs to its lower-level elements, that is, the cell builds the body, the body cannot construct cells. We can't make a cell, but cells build thousands of different bodies according to their genetic information.

There is a development in nature. This creativity has constructed the nature grounding on knowledge. Nothing in nature occurs randomly or unconsciously. All constructions are made according to information, and this information is reflected and recorded in the chemical composition of the entities. For this reason, every living thing strives to pass on this genetic information to the next generation. Sex and love are typical images of these impulses. Yes, the creator has books. One of these books is the geological layers, which are the ARCHIVE PAGES of the earth, where it is explained how and when the world and life were created. (The other is the genetic coding written on the chromosomes of every living thing.) If you can read and evaluate these two books together, you will understand creativity. Otherwise, you will always believe in different books invented by the class of dynasties at the top,

and you will be divided, fighting with each other, crawling in the way that suits the money-fathers.

If the almighty creator wanted to send a book to people, couldn't he send a book that could never be destroyed and would be read and understood by everyone? Why didn't he send such a book, but sent different books to different states (nations)? Moreover, this creator said that he would accept some tribes close to him and protect their descendants and make them rich. Is not all this a fraud in which the scriptures are defined by the rulers of the state according to their own views in order to make the people obey them?

How every being in nature is formed is engraved in its chemical structure. In other words, the creator of the natural system recorded every event-every transaction in the chemical structure of that being. That is why we say that "the Creator has books and they are written in quantum language".

The only factor that prevents humanity from consciously developing within the natural system is the misinformation given to people by those at the top. The constructive-directing power in nature originates from the quantum system within us, that is, there is an internal power system in nature, and it affects and directs all beings. However, humanity has been put into a dead end because a class of dynasties (those at the top) who have taken over the administration have placed a view of life in the subconscious of people (by ingraining in traditions and customs) that the direction in nature is in a Supernatural power system and that they are the representatives of this Supernatural power system.

The concept of the so-called holy book was introduced by the Sumerians 5 thousand years ago. The Sumerians accepted a social rule of "after the kingdom descended from heaven". Notice that "the king does not descend from heaven", the kingdom descends from the sky. The reason why they have such a belief is to ensure that humanity's humanoid gods sitting in the sky pledge allegiance to the rulers by sending them behavioral information like a holy book after creating humanity. It is written in the holy books that "a holy book is sent to every community in its own

language". In this way, humanity is divided into many different societies and people are directed as a flock.

Humanity has been deceived for thousands of years. What is this deception?

A view of life in which nature and the world are created and governed by an omniscient Supernatural Power, that people should live according to the words of their saviors, to whom this holy power sent Holy Books, and that those who live by obeying the provisions of the Bible will go to HEAVEN when they die, and those who do not will remain in HELL forever.

All the societies of the western world were in such a deception 3-4 centuries ago too. But they saved themselves from this delusion by a recovery spurt they called RENAISSANCE AND REFORMATION. Realizing that there could be no omniscient and Bible-sending holy system, they paved the way for creating knowledge and making life easier by doing new things with that information. They facilitated the dissemination of information with an invention that facilitated the transfer of information, such as the printing press. The western world, which increases its economic and political power by creating knowledge, begins to dominate the whole world, dominates the societies of the Americas, Africa, Asia and Australia continents, and imperialism is initiated.

While the Western world facilitated the creation and development of knowledge through renaissance-reform, the Ottoman Sultans, who ruled us, exhibited a dictatorship that prevented the people from acquiring knowledge and awakening, causing the state and the people to become increasingly poor. The prosperity of a society depends on the productive potential of its people. How could the ignorant public produce efficiently? Due to this ignorance, the Ottoman state collapsed. Atatürk, the founder of the Turkish Republic, sees that the salvation of the society will be ensured by not expecting a savior. He made great reforms and established the Republic of Turkey, which raised knowledgeable, resourceful and self-confident people.

The Republic of Turkey, founded by Atatürk, takes its place among the few countries in the world in a really short time. The transformation of the Republic of Turkey into

such a developing country is not welcomed by the western states that seek imperialism. They start political initiatives that will ensure that the Turkish Republic is governed with the Ottoman mentality again. The most effective of these attempts is, of course, to collapse the EDUCATION SYSTEM. Schools such as Village Institutes (Köy Enstitüleri), which enable the people to be educated as knowledgeable and productive individuals, are closed, and schools that focus on religious knowledge, such as imam-hatip schools, which have nothing to do with production, are gradually increased.

Why do governments want the people to become religious?

Let the people attribute their misery to a divine test,

Don't rebel for better conditions and a comfortable life,

Let them be exploited as long as they live, since they are led to believe that they will be rewarded when they die.

Numerous advantages are given to those in power, such as those who die in wars believe that they will go to heaven as MARTYRS.

Until 5,000 years ago, all of humanity spoke an agglutinating language. 5,000 years ago, the nomads of Eastern Europe, called YAMNAYA, formed European languages, which is a fragmented language, and in the following centuries, they tried to introduce the members of this language group as a noble group called ARIAN as a generation that would rule all humanity.

Knowledge varies according to the profession, a blacksmith has knowledge such as how to make a sickle and knife, a miner has knowledge about how to obtain iron mine, an agronomist has knowledge such as which plants to plant and when, which types of plants can grow in which soil. Therefore, there are thousands of different professions in a society (hundreds in the past) today. But society is governed by a person who has knowledge of which of these professions?

Humanity wants to know how nature and the world came into being and developed, and how this was done by whom(s). ARCHIVE-PAGES records and

ASTROPHYSICS data show that nature and the world were started 13 billion years ago by the most basic elements of life called QUANTUM, the number of which is calculated as 10 to the power of hundred-odd, and that these basic elements of life started to form the universe by forming higher-level systems such as proton-neutron-electron with the combination method called QUANTIZATION. Quanta create the INFORMATION & SELF-ORGANIZATION system of nature and the world by investing in a development called evolution by promoting the INFORMATION-based systems that form the most ergonomic structures. Since scientists still do not use such a parameter as KNOWLEDGE in any formulation and continue to see beings as UNCONSCIOUS robots, they mislead humanity, therefore they are in betrayal of humanity.

The ARCHIVE-PAGES of the Earth are the true works of the Creator. They are recorded in the layers of the earth. They are data that have been transferred to a language that people can understand by scientists from various nations for 4-5 centuries with tremendous efforts. They are understood and interpreted in the same way by every nation. Archive-pages show that formations in nature develop depending on their potential to create KNOWLEDGE. Biblical religions, on the other hand, command people to act according to dogmatic information that is believed to have been sent from a divine being. For this reason, the creation of new things by creating new knowledge in societies under the influence of the Bible has been limited.

The most effective way to bring down a nation is to lower the quality of education. This method has been successfully applied in our country for the last 60 years. Shouldn't we make an accounting of conscience by remembering the educational changes that have been carried out with the closure of the Village-Institutes (Köy Enstitüleri) and the increasing number of Imam-hatip-schools, and taking into account the following points?

The behaviour of those who govern our society to encourage the teaching of religion in schools is a crime against humanity.

When you instill religious knowledge and traditions based on a holy book in your children, you attach a label such as "you are a Jew, you are a Muslim" to them as soon as they are born. This information is recorded in the brain structure as special chemical compounds, and children have to behave according to those chemical compositions.

Wouldn't you feel guilty if children under the influence of these different religious views were to engage in jihad-work with the intention of fulfilling Allah's commandments, to detonate a suicide bomb that would kill hundreds of people, and if your child died in that explosion in order to go to Paradise?

People are not considered minors until the age of 18, because by that time their logical evaluation is not fully developed and they act according to the directions of others. For this reason, in education up to the age of 18, children should not be given any knowledge other than the positive sciences that are accepted by everyone, because information that is not accepted by everyone is not objective. For this reason, it is a betrayal of humanity and society to give teachings that vary from society to society, such as religious lessons, in primary and secondary education.

9. CHAPTER- CONCLUSION

Our goal is to live peacefully and happily!

So why can't we lead such a life?

Because we are given a wrong purpose of life.

Where is the mistake?

On the target shown.

What is the stated goal: "The life of this world is temporary; the real life is in the other world."

Showing such a goal is aimed entirely at ensuring that rulers frighten the people with punishments of hell, employs them to earn a living with the least amount of things, but they themselves live in abundance.

For this reason, a peaceful and happy life system cannot be created.

For centuries, all of humanity, including scientists, has been conditioned and blinded by the concept of time in accordance with a static system view of nature, misinterpreting time and causing people to create false information about life.

1. While innocent people are dying every day, when no one's life is safe,
2. While the rights-legality system does not work;
3. While inflation-unemployment continues to increase day by day;
4. While it has been shown that the source of all our social problems is the dependence on the static system.

I protest against the fact that scientists, especially clergymen, and those we believe to be "intellectuals" still continue to deal with leaves and cannot see the forest.

Since the society is a business-and-professional environment, the issue of what service the clergy provide to the society comes to the fore. The concept of the afterlife is based on the belief that the Sumerians designed according to their view of the world and life, that heaven is an imaginary heavenly country above the firmament, and hell is a fiery environment world from which underground volcanoes emerge. Life can only form on planets called the habitable belt around stars such as the sun. Today, the sky and space are known in considerable detail. There is no other world in the solar system where man can live on any other planet other than Earth. If there is a planet that has the possibility of life on the planets of other stars, that planet will have its own world of living things, and there will be no place for those who live on our earth. Because the genetic information of each being is formed according to the environmental conditions in which that entity was born and developed. These are natural-scientific facts, so the clergy represent a group that has been deceiving people for centuries and therefore has contributed nothing to the life of society.

There is a life system based on the cycle of birth and death, and a natural system that is in constant change and transformation. It is the task of scientists to define this system, to explain how it works, and to help regulate the functioning and

organization of the social system according to the principles of this natural system. As long as scientists who define themselves as naturalists, physicists, chemists, biologists, geologists, paleontologists, physicians, etc., do not fulfill this task, no one will be able to prevent the religious merchants who peddled the knowledge of the natural system builder of 3-4 thousand years ago from carrying out these works, and all the blame for this will be on the naturalist scientists.

The system of formation and development in nature has been completely misrepresented to us. Namely: Everything in nature is under the control of its components. As long as the components protect the structure they have created and keep that structure alive, that system survives, otherwise it disintegrates.

If this is the case, why don't people take an active role in making things go well in the social systems to which they belong, but leave the management of society to those they call leaders and endowed with extraordinary powers?

For thousands of years, humanity has been trying to leave a better living environment for them by accumulating property and bequeathing it to their children. In the natural system, cells acquire the most appropriate information for the natural environment and apply the method of bequeathing them to their offspring. Thanks to this method, the information-forming potential has been steadily increased over billions of years, reaching an enormous level such as life that started with bacteria, amoeba, maggots, insects, fish, dinosaurs, mammals, humans. In order for our children to have a better future, what should we bequeath to them: Property or the knowledge of "the cause of our problems and the way to solve them"?

Life requires being active. But activity is controlled by information. Whatever kind of information is given, the entity behaves according to that information. Since people have been informed for 4 thousand years that creativity comes from a sacred system outside the body, that disasters will befall them if they do not live by obeying its commands, and that natural disasters occur for this reason, people live and exhibit their activities by praying, worshiping, and sacrificing to this external creator. However, creativity is of quantum origin, and quanta prefer systems that create the best information and organize according to that information. Those who give false

information to people are always the people who are rulers of the society, because they make their living by exploiting the people at the bottom. Those who make a living by marketing the afterlife are at the top of these.

The maker and director of bodies are within them; cells. We convey our purpose to them. But it is the cells that decide whether to go to that goal or not. Because cells have to behave by taking into account billions of factors in nature. There are about 100 billion cells in our brain, and each cell evaluates 50-60 thousand different factors and transfers that information to another person. In this way, communication between billions of cells at the speed of light begins, and a decision emerges: To do it or not!

As explained in the archive-pages data, everything in nature begins with the smallest building blocks of beings, very ephemeral and very mobile subatomic elements. Coming together in the higher-level systems to achieve a longer life and a more comfortable life has been their main goal. Thus, interactions are carried out with the ever-growing higher-level system formations to create more and more ergonomic structures. In other words, the universe is evolving. Humanity, on the other hand, plays a role as one of the most important players in this process and is in a situation that will affect the future of the life system in our world.

There is nothing in nature that is not based on mutual interaction. The task of building society is the task of us humans. So no one has the luxury of saying, "I don't agree with your view, you go your way, I go my way", because we're all in the same "boat," and if that ship sinks, we all sink.

This is the greatest irrationality that people do, and the reason for this irrationality is that they have traditionally been conditioned by a wrong view of life. That mistake is the view of nature that the formations in nature are not carried out by mutual interactions between the entities themselves, but by a holy power-system outside them.

Our behaviours is usually determined by subconscious data. Subconscious data is also transmitted by traditions and customs. Societies that are forbidden by their belief-systems to question whether their customs and traditions are beneficial or harmful are doomed to be forever exploited by those at the top.

In nature, every being gets its energy and nutrients from its internal components: Bodies get their energy from their cells; cells are made up of molecules; molecules are made up of atoms; In atoms, they get from the quantum system. In any higher-level system, there is no energy or nurturing property.

Since there is no power and energy at the rulers, they misrepresent the system in nature, inflict a mental poisoning and make the people zombies. Zombies, on the other hand, are easily fooled. Since the formation of the subconscious takes place in infancy-childhood, people are given religious information starting from this stage, and this information is of divine origin, their accuracy should never be doubted or questioned; otherwise, they will burn in the fire of hell, etc. Such a belief system was certainly put forward by someone at the top so that they could herd the people like a herd (Fig 73).

Figure 73: Community life is a system of partnership between members of business and professions.

Unemployment is very common,

We are going crazy because of the traffic problem;

The pension we receive is decreasing every day with inflation;

We can't safely leave our car on the street, brats scratch, deflate tires;

The sadness of the deaths of our acquaintances in traffic accidents is painful;

Enlisting in the military is tantamount to inviting death, because we are overwhelmed by terror;

When we see children begging on street corners, we are heartbroken;

Tap water is undrinkably dirty;

In winter, coal dust increases so much that the air we breathe burns our throats;

We couldn't fish because the seas are a hotbed of garbage and pollution;

We are overwhelmed by hearing noise from the surroundings instead of bird-song;

No fruit has the same taste that we had in our childhood anymore, because they are all genetically modified.

We can't sleep comfortably at night because of stress;

There is no justice and legality in society, and the discomfort caused by this makes people crazy;

The interrelation-regulating factor called morality has been nullified, no one treats anyone normally;

Televisions, radios and newspapers do not give any peaceful news, on the contrary, news of catastrophic destruction is received every day;

All TV movies and series are full of illogical scenarios; it makes the audience think worse;

Internet viruses are driving us crazy;

Fraud in online shopping is increasing;

Fear of bombs in crowded places;

Fear of being raped or robbed in a secluded place;

Fear of being arrested at home in the morning;

Fear of our workplace closing;

Fear of our child being kidnapped;

Help, we want to be saved.

All of humanity wants to be saved. But because we are dependent on the rulers at the top, we can't get rid of it. We are always kept alive in fear, because fear comes from addiction. We are dependent on someone at the top, and that person at the top always finds different methods of intimidation to keep us dependent all the time.

Will we not be able to create a peaceful living environment? Of course, we will. Here is the solution formula:

How the balance and order in nature is formed begins to be enlightened after the 1980s. In 1983, German physicist H. Haken put forward the mathematical and physical formulations of the formation and development of nature with a system called SYNERGETIC, which means "processing together", and in (2000) he laid the foundation of the physics of dynamical systems, which is summarized as "information & self-organization".

While it means "Synergetic = Processing together", it means "Information & self-organization". In other words, assets operate according to the information they will generate. This is where the problem begins, because in the system called SOCIETY, the people are thought of as a herd, and the management and organization are left entirely to someone called the savior.

For centuries, a false view has been presented to the public. Since what is sown is reaped, the same mistake persists. The biggest mistake is that the people see themselves as a herd and are looking for a leader who will shepherd them.

However: "Community life" is a system of partnership between different business and professions. Balance in society can only be created through the mutual interaction of representatives of business and professional representatives. It is impossible for it to be created by someone from above. We are experiencing this situation right now, farmers are troubled, shopkeepers are troubled, students are troubled, teachers are troubled, those who are not troubled are only those we choose to govern us, that is, those at the top.

A healthier and happier life can only be realized automatically by people who grow up as individuals with a job and profession, mutually exchanging service products. Since no leader can create a fair balance and order between thousands of different businesses and professions, they blame each other when things start to get out of hand.

The main reason why humanity has lived in problems has been to leave the management of society to someone, such as the leader at the top or the king, who is believed to represent the "sacred office". Two points need to be emphasized here: The first point is that there is no such authority or system as "holiness" in nature. The concept of holiness is written in Sumerian documents that it was a cover invented by the Sumerians for the people to pledge allegiance to their leaders. The second point: In nature, the "leader" exists only in herd life, while in social systems such as colonies, there is a democracy-like system of partnership based on service-exchanges. This has been proven in bees and ants. The "bee queen" is not a leader, but a "fragrance" emitter representing the colony system, it should be considered like a flag.

The property of society belongs to the people. But what kind of people? People who know that society is a partnership between business and professional members and therefore acquire a job or profession suitable for their ability and access the right of partnership in society. This is a rule of nature, and it is written in the data of archive pages, because cells specialized in certain subjects and partnered with each other to initiate multicellular life.

Every person is different. This difference is necessary and necessary for the fulfillment of the duties to be undertaken in social life. Therefore, it is not possible to compare people with each other. Each person is superior to the other people around him with one feature. Taking into account these characteristics of people, each individual should be educated and made to have a profession. In other words, society is formed through education: A system of organization cannot be established among the members of the business and profession in that society without each person receiving a job and vocational training corresponding to his natural abilities. People

who have the knowledge that they own the society will never act in a way that will harm the society.

We are people who live on this earth and therefore "travel in the same boat". And humanity lives "unconsciously" as puppets manipulated by their money-fathers at the top, turning the world into hell. The only reason for this is that "he does not know the cause of the problems"

Because for 4,000 years, people have been taught a life with the concept of "state", not the concept of "society", and the state has been seen as a part of the homeland owned by a group at the top. As such, people were told that the management of the society should be in the hands of a person at the top, and the societies were directed and managed by the Authority-Dependent Organization (ADO) system. The harms of Authority-Dependent Organization have been shown in a previous chapter. Since imperialism is a typical top-down system, it is the main source of conflicts between states. In other words, it is obvious that the source of all social problems of humanity is the system managed from above.

In this case, the main goal of people is to ask, "What is the cause of our social problems? How should societies be governed?"

In today's world, there are no longer clear borders between states, all the peoples of states are in relations and dependence on each other. Technology has advanced to such an extent that a member of a state, through a friend in another state, can perform a very harmful function to the people of that state. For this reason, all the people of the world turned into people traveling in the same boat. In this case, it is necessary to prepare a common "DECLARATION OF WORLD CITIZENSHIP" for all humanity, which can be accepted by everyone.

Conflict of interest: The author declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement: Data supporting these findings are available within the article or upon request.

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